

Ring1b:
Translational
Control and
Knockout
Phenotypes
of a **PcG**
Core Protein
Erwin A. Boutsma

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Translational Control and Knockout
Phenotypes of a PcG Core Protein**

Cover: colonies of mouse embryonic stem cells on the verge of death, as a result of genetic inactivation of the Ring1b gene and subsequent loss of Ring1b protein. The DNA in the nuclei is stained blue, Ring1b is stained red. Wildtype embryonic stem cells express Ring1b in such large quantities, that the staining would be red, with hardly any blue shining through (not shown).

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Ring1b: Translational Control and Knockout Phenotypes of a PcG Core Protein

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Voor Laura

Nature, properly understood in a scientific way, is deeply beautiful and unfailingly interesting.
It's worth putting in some honest effort to understand it properly.

Richard Dawkins, 'A Devil's Chaplain'

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¹ Due to the fact that this thesis describes two lines of research that are quite different in nature, the author chose to discuss them into two separate introduction/discussion chapters

Chapter 1

Introduction & Discussion

Polycomb group proteins:
orchestrating development by
modifying histones

The saddest aspect of life right now is that science gathers knowledge faster than society gathers wisdom.

Isaac Asimov

Polycomb group proteins: orchestrating development by modifying histones

From the earliest discovery of Polycomb group (PcG) proteins in *Drosophila melanogaster* until the recent detailed descriptions of these proteins' role in histone modification, it has been clear that Polycomb group proteins play key roles in development. Acting in multimeric complexes, they exhibit their function to silence specific areas of the genome by modifying histone tails on amino acid residues. Polycomb group proteins are now found to be critically involved in control of cell proliferation, the coordinated silencing of one of the X-chromosomes (X₁) in female somatic cells, maintenance of stem cell identity in both early development as well as in adult life, and orchestrating developmental processes during embryogenesis. The subject of this thesis, PcG protein Ring1b, is believed to be critically involved in the latter three processes, as will be discussed in this chapter.

Early Polycomb knockout studies

The chromatin-associated Polycomb group (PcG) proteins, consisting of dozens of different proteins, were first identified in genetic screens for homeotic transformations in *Drosophila melanogaster* (fruit fly). They were named after the *Drosophila* gene *Polycomb*. Other genes, among which are *Polyhomeotic*, *Posterior sex combs*, *Sex combs on midleg*, *Pleiohomeotic*, *Sex combs extra*, and *enhancer of Zeste*, were soon identified to belong to the same group, based on a common feature: when knocked out, flies failed to develop normally during embryogenesis. More specifically, these proteins were found to repress *Homeotic* genes – also called *Hox* genes – whose exact spatial and temporal expression determines the establishment of the body plan and segmentation. Characteristically, the absence – or, as was found later, overexpression or ectopic expression – of a PcG gene results in abnormal spatial and temporal expression of one or more *Hox* genes, resulting in the formation of extra body parts, deformed body parts or mislocalization of body parts, as many of the PcG genes' names indicate. This so-called ectopic expression of PcG genes is attributed to the failure of proper gene silencing in PcG mutants (reviewed in Muller and Kassisi, 2006). In mammals, being much more complicated

organisms, the phenotypes were less well-defined. No extra legs or double heads are formed in PcG knockout mice, but instead one can for example observe extra vertebrae or costae in mice lacking a PcG gene. For example, the mammalian homologue of *Posterior sex combs*, *Bmi1*, was found to have posterior transformations, mainly along the anteroposterior axis of the skeleton (van der Lugt et al., 1994). In addition, these mice have an ataxic gait, sporadic seizures and a low bodyweight. Usually, they do not grow older than three months and more often only one month. Perhaps the most interesting phenotype of these mice is a proliferation defect in the hematopoietic system. The mice have a strongly reduced hematopoietic cell count as well as a diminished response to mitogenic stimuli. As we will see in a paragraph below, this was the first time a PcG gene was implicated in cell proliferation.

In mammals, often a second or even third homologue of the *Drosophila* counterpart is identified. *Mel18*, also called *PCGF2*, is a close homologue of *Bmi1* and also the later-on found gene *MBLR* (*Mel18 and Bmi1-like repressor*) is now considered a homologue (Akasaka et al., 2002). Strikingly, although *Mel18* and *Bmi1* are quite similar (70 percent identical on gene

level), exhibit almost the same phenotype (Akasaka et al., 1996), and appear to have at least partially overlapping roles, they cannot fully compensate for one another (Akasaka et al., 2001). Recent findings suggest, that *Mel18* is capable of downregulating *Bmi1* expression levels (Guo et al., 2007; Guo et al., 2007). However, the mechanisms underlying this are unclear.

Many other Polycomb group proteins have been studied using a knockout mouse model. Mammalian *Polycomb* homologue *M33* was the third PcG protein identified in mammals, causing homeotic transformations of the axial skeleton, and sternal and limb malformations in the developing embryo when absent (Core et al., 1997). Like the *Bmi1* and *Mel18* knockout mice, a proliferative defect of somatic cell types – e.g. lymphocytes and fibroblasts – was found in *in vitro*, again linking PcG proteins to proliferation. In the same year, the mammalian homologue of *Polyhomeotic*, *MPh1*, was inactivated in mice; this again led to developmental defects, among which were posterior skeletal transformations and many defects in neural crest-derived tissues (Takahara et al., 1997). In addition, these mice died shortly before birth. Genetic inactivation of *Ring1a*, a mouse homologue of *Drosophila dRING* gene, also caused skeletal malformations, mainly of the axial skeleton (Mar Lorente et al., 2000). In this study, it was demonstrated that apparently in some cases heterozygosity of a PcG gene is sufficient to cause developmental defects, since *Ring1a*^{+/-} mice also exhibited mild skeletal abnormalities. Transcription factor YY1, based on its interactions (genetic as well as physical) with other members of the PcG protein family also considered to be a PcG protein (Garcia et al., 1999; Lorente et al., 2006; Satijn et al., 2001), shows the same effect: heterozygosity of the null mutation leads to neurological defects and subsequent behavioral abnormalities in a subset of mice. Affar and co-workers found that, like many PcG proteins, the precise protein

level of YY1 is critical. Phenotypic analysis of YY1 mutant embryos expressing approximately 75 percent, 50 percent, and 25 percent of the normal YY1 levels, identified a dosage-dependent requirement for YY1 during late embryogenesis (Affar el et al., 2006). However, different from the PcG members described above, the double null mutation causes peri-implantation lethality (Donohoe et al., 1999).

Prenatal death is not uncommon under PcG members, however. Ablation of mammalian PcG members *RYBP* (Pirity et al., 2005), *Eed* (Faust et al., 1998), *EZH2* (O'Carroll et al., 2001) and the subject of this thesis, *Ring1b* (Voncken et al., 2003), all lead to embryonic death, often with striking similarities between them on the histological level. Particularly interesting is the similarity between the *EZH2*, *Eed* and *Ring1b* knockout mice, since, as we will see in a paragraph below, these proteins are believed to be in different biochemical complexes. *EZH2*, *Eed* and *Ring1b* mutants all die during gastrulation, the process that separates the three germ layers (ectoderm, mesoderm and endoderm) in the developing embryo. We demonstrated earlier, that in *Ring1b* null mutants, the epiblast fails to expand normally and the mesoderm does not migrate anteriorly. Moreover, a clear delay in development of extraembryonic structures accompanies the delay in development of the embryo itself. This condition is very reminiscent of both the *Eed* and *EZH2* mutant phenotypes.

Many more PcG genes await knockout mouse models. Not only for phenotypical analysis, but also for primary knockout cell lines derived from these mice, which have proven to be valuable tools to verify specific functions of PcG members. Also, genetic interactions between PcG members – as was already demonstrated for *Ring1a/Ring1b* (de Napoles et al., 2004; Endoh et al., 2008; our own unpublished *in vivo* observations), *Bmi1/Mel18* (Akasaka et al., 2001), *Bmi1/Ring1b* (Voncken et al., 2003), *Ring1a/YY1* (Lorente et al., 2006), and several

others – can lead to new ideas about functional collaborations and redundancies between PcG members.

Control of cell proliferation by PcG proteins

In the paragraph above it was stated that many PcG proteins were found to be involved in cell proliferation-related processes. Initially, this was mainly based on observations in PcG knockout embryos exhibiting proliferative defects in for example the hematopoietic system, but in 1999 our group found a strong mechanistic involvement of PcG protein Bmi1 in cell proliferation (Jacobs et al., 1999). Primary mouse embryonic fibroblasts lacking Bmi1 undergo premature senescence, which correlated with strong upregulation of tumor suppressors p16^{Ink4a} and p19^{Arf}, both encoded by the tumor suppressor locus *Ink4a/Arf*. Genetic inactivation of *Ink4a/Arf* dramatically reduces the proliferative defects seen in *Bmi1*-deficient mice, indicating that *Ink4a/Arf* is a critical *in vivo* target. This was no surprise in itself, because Bmi1 was first isolated as a factor cooperating with c-myc in the formation of lymphomas in mice, identifying *Bmi1* as a proto-oncogene (van Lohuizen et al., 1991). But the functional link between *Bmi1* and an established tumor suppressor locus was the first time a PcG protein was associated with tumorigenesis. After these discoveries, Bmi1 has been implicated in many more tumors, mainly those derived from hematopoietic lineages, but also in the brain, as will be discussed in more detail in a paragraph below. In one study by Kanno and co-workers, a close homologue of Bmi1, Mel18, was found to have the opposite effect, seemingly classifying it as a tumor suppressor (Kanno et al., 1995). However, this experiment was done with overexpression constructs and a reporter plasmid harboring a putative, but not widely accepted Mel18 DNA binding site. The observed effect could be an artefact of the highly artificial experimental setup, lacking the proper cellular context.

Only recently has Ring1b also been implicated in cellular proliferation, when Calés and co-workers crossed a *Ring1b* conditional knockout mouse with an MxCre transgenic mouse line, resulting in ablation of Ring1b in the hematopoietic compartment (Cales et al., 2008). Ring1b was found to be correlated with both stimulating as well as inhibiting hematopoietic proliferation, dependent on lineage commitment. Inhibition concerns early myeloid progenitors and is conferred through negative regulation of cell cycle inhibitor p16^{Ink4a}. Stimulation concerns myeloid and lymphoid lineage-committed precursors of B-cell lineages and is mediated through negative regulation of cell cycle promoters cdc6 and Cyclin D2. As might be expected, inactivation of the *Ink4a/Arf* locus only rescued the decreased proliferation of early progenitors, not of the more committed cells.

Several other PcG proteins were found to be more or less critically involved in cell proliferation (for a comprehensive list, see Sparmann and van Lohuizen, 2006). For example, next to Bmi1, Mel18, Cbx7 and Cbx8 are all capable of repressing the *Ink4a* locus as well (Dietrich et al., 2007; Gil et al., 2004). MPH1 and Eed were found to have proliferative effects independent of *Ink4a/Arf*. Reduced expression of Eed causes marked myelo- and lymphoproliferative defects, indicating that eed is involved in the negative regulation of lymphoid and myeloid progenitor cells, but expression of p16^{Ink4a} and p19^{Arf} remained unaltered in Eed mutants (Lessard et al., 1999). EZH2 and RYBP have strong correlations with cancers as well, the latter being able to stabilize well-known tumor suppressor gene *p53* (Chen et al., 2008). EZH2 is a SET domain protein, capable of transferring methyl groups to specific residues on histone tails, and was found to promote, among others, prostate cancer (Varambally et al., 2002), myelomas (Croonquist and Van Ness, 2005), breast cancer (Ding et al., 2006), and ovarian carcinomas (Lu et al., 2007). EZH2 expression in

Figure 1. Epigenetic marks on histone tails: the histone code

The picture shows half a nucleosome core particle, consisting of histone H2A, H2B, H3 and H4, with a DNA strand wrapped around them (thick black line). Each of the histones has a 'tail', which can be modified by attaching small peptides (Ub, ubiquitin) or molecules (me, methyl; Ac, acetyl) to them. The combination of these histone tail marks is called the histone code and is believed to function as an instruction to either compact local chromatin structure, or make it more open and accessible. The histone code also provides both Polycomb complexes (PRC 1 and PRC2) a way to communicate with one another, although members of these complexes do not physically interact. Of special interest in this respect is the trimethyl mark on lysine 27 (K27) of H3, which is set by PRC2 member EZH2 and associated with repressed genes in somatic cells. The H3K27me3 mark is recognized by PRC1 member M33, recruiting the PRC1 complex to the chromatin. The ubiquitin mark on lysine 119 of H2A is set by PRC1 member Ring1b, the subject of this thesis, and also associated with repression of local genes. The acetyl marks on several histone tails can be removed by HDACs associated with PRC2 members, generally involved in the early stages of repression. The only mark in the figure not associated with repression, is the H2BK123Ub (K120 in mammals) mark, set by the Rad6/Bre1 ligase complex. This mark is mainly associated with active genes. The picture only shows some of the modifications and catalytic proteins involved.

these tumors is associated with poor prognosis and metastases. Nowadays, EZH2 is considered to be a prognostic marker in several types of malignancies (Kleer et al., 2003).

Repression of PcG complexes by chromatin remodeling

Soon after the discovery of PcG genes, it became clear that PcG proteins exert their function by

remodeling chromatin, granting local access to the transcriptional machinery or not. The way PcG proteins go about this remodeling, has long been unclear. Over the past decade, an intriguing landscape of many different marks on histone tails has emerged, specific combinations of which are now referred to as a 'code', leading to a certain transcriptional state of local genes (figure 1). Chromatin remodeling PcG protein complexes

come in several biochemically distinct flavors in mammals, often acting in concert with one another. Polycomb Repressive Complex 2 (PRC2), also termed the initiation complex, harbors Eed, SuZ12, EZH1 and EZH2 (Sewalt et al., 1998; van Lohuizen et al., 1998). Another complex, PRC1 or sometimes called maintenance complex, consists of Ring1b/Rnf2, Bmi1, M33, MPh1, RYBP and homologues, but also transcription factors such as YY1 and E2F6 (Trimarchi et al., 2001; Levine et al., 2002). Over the last decade, however, it has become clear that this two-complex model is oversimplified. Many different compositions of the complexes occur, often dependent on the cellular context. The reason that people today still refer to PRC1 and PRC2 is, that none of their members physically interact, thus creating two groups within the Polycomb group of proteins. Several enzymatic functions have been linked to Polycomb complexes, among which are histone deacetylation (Tie et al., 2001; van der Vlag and Otte, 1999; Xia et al., 2003), histone methylation (Cao and Zhang, 2004; Cao et al., 2002; Kuzmichev et al., 2002) and histone ubiquitination (Fang et al., 2004; Wang et al., 2004). It is thought that extensive modification of histone tails determines local chromatin structure, either by influencing chromatin structure directly or by recruitment of modifying factors, such as PcG proteins.

Histone deacetylation was the first remodeling activity identified of PcG proteins towards chromatin. Several histone deacetylases (HDACs) specifically bound *in vivo* and *in vitro* with PRC2 member Eed, and the deacetylating activity co-immunoprecipitated with PRC2, but not PRC1 (van der Vlag and Otte, 1999). Histone deacetylation generally leads to repression of local genes. Currently, administration of HDAC inhibitors is under investigation as anticancer treatment, since these inhibitors correlate with reduced levels of EZH2, H3K27me_{2/3}, and concomitant loss of clonogenic survival of cultured acute myelogenous leukemia (AML) cells (Fiskus et al., 2006).

Second, histone methylation was discovered. The field of histone methylation is a complex one, with many lysine amino acid residues in different histone tails that can be methylated, often even double or triple methylated. It is now generally believed, that PcG mediated silencing mainly balances around the dimethyl and trimethyl marks on lysine 27 of histone H3 (H3K27me_{2/3}). Recently identified demethylases remove this silencing signal (Agger et al., 2007; De Santa et al., 2007; Lan et al., 2007; Lee et al., 2007), whereas PRC2 member EZH2 sets the mark, in complex with Suz12 and Eed (Cao et al., 2002; Kuzmichev et al., 2002; Kirmizis et al., 2004). Repressed genes only contain these histone marks, which are associated with silencing, whereas transcribed genes contain only histone marks associated with activity. Although this black-and-white situation is generally true, in some cases, notably in embryonic stem (ES) cells, both marks can be found at the same time, resulting in so-called bivalent chromatin domains. Especially in these cells the interplay between active and repressive marks is tightly regulated, as will be discussed in more detailed in a paragraph below.

Many reports state that EZH2 is the histone methyl transferase responsible for setting the H3K27me₃ mark, but recently it was found that EZH2 homologue EZH1 is also capable of acting as a methyl transferase *in vitro* and *in vivo* (Shen et al., 2008). Depletion of EZH1 in EZH2 null cells convincingly abolishes residual methylation on H3K27 and derepresses H3K27me₃ target genes. This again stresses the partially overlapping function, but by no means redundancy, of PcG protein homologues.

There's a well-established genetic interplay between PRC1 and PRC2, but no evidence has been found as of yet that any of their members interact with each other. However, protein crystallization experiments between the chromodomain of PRC1 member M33/Pc and H3K27me₃ revealed, that the EZH2 catalyzed

histone mark H3K27me3 is recognized by M33, providing a mechanism of communication between the two complexes (Fischle et al., 2003). In chapter 3, we show with immunofluorescent stainings and microarray analysis that genetic inactivation of Ring1b has no effect on transcript levels of EZH2 or the levels of H3K27me3 in ES cells. This suggests that apparently there's no negative feedback mechanism from PRC1 to PRC2, or H3K27me3 to PRC1 in ES cells.

Finally, ubiquitination was added to the list of PcG activities towards histones. Wang and co-workers found that PRC1 member Ring1b was responsible for the long-known monoubiquitination of histone H2A at lysine 119, also referred to as H2AK119u1 (Wang et al., 2004; our own *in vivo* observations). In subsequent studies it was proposed that this chromatin mark may be involved in transcriptional repression by Polycomb proteins, since global loss of monoubiquitinated H2A coincided with activation of developmental genes and enhanced the rate of differentiation (Wang et al., 2004; Cao et al., 2005). Further experimental evidence to support this idea came when loss of Ring1b mediated monoubiquitination of H2A was linked to the release of poised RNA polymerase II and subsequent derepression of target genes in ES cells (Stock et al., 2007). This important finding may provide a first explanation for the mechanism of gene repression by PcG proteins via histone modification. A more recent association of the H2AK119u1 mark with repression, is the finding that in early embryos, the paternally imprinted *Kcnq1* cluster organizes a higher-order repressive nuclear compartment, characterized by the local presence of the non-coding RNA (ncRNA) *Kcnq1ot1*, both PRC1 and PRC2 proteins, and the repressive histone mark H3K27me3 (Terranova et al., 2008). In addition, recent findings in *Drosophila melanogaster* showed that H2A monoubiquitination by Ring1b homologue dRING requires dKDM2, a demethylase that normally mediates H3K36me2

demethylation, an effect that is associated with repression of target genes (Lagarou et al., 2008). More on the mechanism of Ring1b monoubiquitination will be discussed in the final paragraph.

Ring1b is necessary for maintenance of stem cell identity

Over the past few years, a lot of attention has gone to the role of PcG silencing mechanisms in embryonic stem cells. These cells are pluripotent, meaning that they are not yet committed to a certain lineage and can divide indefinitely as long as they retain their stem cell identity. Loss of this identity is referred to as differentiation, a process initiated by external stimuli that cause derepression of genes involved in lineage commitment. Several genome-wide analyses by our group and others clearly demonstrated that PcG protein complexes act selectively on genes related to growth and development (Tolhuis et al., 2006; Schwartz et al., 2006; Lee et al., 2006; Boyer et al., 2006; Bracken et al., 2006; Endoh et al., 2008). Importantly, PcG protein complexes occupy genes involved in initiation of differentiation in embryonic stem cells (Boyer et al., 2006), and co-occupy a significant subset of genes with established embryonic stem cell regulators Nanog, SOX2 and Oct4 (Lee et al., 2006; Loh et al., 2006). Both Oct4 and Nanog are critical transcription factors for maintenance of stem cell identity; loss of either one of them unequivocally leads to deregulated differentiation, whereas ectopic expression of Oct4 can block differentiation (Chambers et al., 2003; Mitsui et al., 2003; Nichols et al., 1998). Therefore, Nanog and Oct4 are considered to be hallmarks of pluripotency. Several possible functional links between these proteins and PcG proteins were found, the first by Wang and co-workers, who co-purified Oct4, YY1 and Ring1b with stem cell specific protein Rex1 from ES cells (Wang et al., 2006). Second, in ES cells PRC2 members were found to be localized to the *Oct4* and *Nanog* promoter, suggesting

a direct role for PcG proteins in regulating the expression of Oct4 and Nanog (Pasini et al., 2007). In this study, PRC2 member SuZ12 was found to dissociate from Oct4-bound promoters upon downregulation of Oct4 as a result of initiation of differentiation. Finally, the PRC2-mediated repressive H3K27me3 histone mark has been found at the *Oct4* promoter in more differentiated cells, suggesting that PcG proteins are involved in direct repression of stem cell regulators in differentiated cells (Azuares et al., 2006).

It is now generally believed that Ring1b, as the PRC1 catalytic subunit setting the repressive H2AK119u1 mark, and being necessary for perinatal survival in mice, is critically involved in the process of repressing genes involved in initiation of lineage commitment. In 2007, it was experimentally demonstrated by Leeb and Wutz for the first time that Ring1b-deficient ES cells are prone for differentiation (Leeb and Wutz, 2007). Several studies followed, all showing strong correlations between the presence of Ring1b-containing PRC1 complexes and maintenance of stem cell identity. Endoh and co-workers showed, that upon induction of differentiation by GATA6, Ring1b target genes in mouse ES cells are derepressed and Ring1b localization to target loci is decreased (Endoh et al., 2008). Chapter 3 of this thesis shows results that are consistent with these ideas. Genetic inactivation of Ring1b in mouse ES cells facilitated a differentiation-prone phenotype by deregulation of, among others, TGF β signaling, cellular communication and cell cycle pathways. The fact that many functionally different pathways are switched on simultaneously, indicates that there's a global derepression of development-related genes resulting in simultaneous lineage commitment in different directions, a process that clearly should not occur *in vivo*. Importantly, retained expression of stem cell regulators Oct4 and Nanog, as well as alkaline phosphatase, indicates that Ring1b deficient ES cells maintain important ES cell

characteristics. The fact that Oct4 and Nanog are still present whereas Ring1b is not, and the observation that lineage commitment has started, is in itself a clear example of abnormal rather than scheduled differentiation of these ES cells. Boyer and co-workers already found by comparative analysis with genome-wide Ring1b binding data in mouse ES cells, that Ring1b is involved in transcriptional regulation of key developmental genes, such as *Bmp7*, *Gata3* and *Msx* (Boyer et al., 2006). Notably, by directly repressing these extracellular downstream effector components of differentiation-related pathways, such as *Bmp7* and *Id3* of the Bmp/TGF β signaling pathway, and *Col4a2*, *Gja1* and *Ccnd2* of the cellular communication pathways, Ring1b may have an important role in influencing lineage choice and other developmental events. For example, expression of extracellular matrix (ECM) protein Col4a2 was shown to induce mesodermal differentiation of ES cells *in vitro*, while repression of *Bmp7* at the dorsal site of zebra fish gastrula was shown to allow cellular migration as is required for limb development (von der Hardt et al., 2007; Nishikawa et al., 1998).

Our earlier *in vivo* studies regarding loss of *Ring1b* can be superficially explained by the observation that loss of *Ring1b* leads to unscheduled differentiation. In *Ring1b* knockout embryos, several developmental markers are misexpressed at early gastrulation stages, extraembryonic mesoderm is over-represented, epiblast has expanded improperly, and embryonic growth is delayed (Voncken et al., 2003). The latter can also be contributed to strongly increased apoptosis upon loss of *Ring1b*, as we also observed in primary mouse embryonic fibroblasts (MEFs) and ES cells *in vitro*. Even cultured in the presence of apoptosis-inhibitors or immortalizing oncogenes, these cells would not survive more than a few passages. The early embryonic lethality of *Ring1b* null mice is partially rescued in a *Ink4a/Arf*-knockout background, one of

the PcG transcriptional targets (Bracken et al., 2007; Jacobs et al., 1999), resulting in the delay of embryonic death of about 4 days (Voncken et al., 2003). Since relief of the *Ink4a/Arf*-mediated antiproliferative block only bypasses the proliferative defects induced by loss of Ring1b, this also underscores the importance for Ring1b in regulating developmental genes during early embryogenesis.

Only a subset of Ring1b bound genes is derepressed following deletion of Ring1b in ES cells, suggesting that additional mechanisms mediate silencing of other Ring1b target genes, as demonstrated in chapter 3 of this thesis and by others, who show that only part of the PcG bound genes are deregulated after RNAi-mediated depletion of PcG proteins in human embryonic fibroblasts and in *Eed* or *SuZ12* deficient ES cells (Bracken et al., 2006; Pasini et al., 2007; Boyer et al., 2006). Partial derepression could also be explained by functional redundancy by *Ring1a*, which like Ring1b possesses ubiquitin E3 ligase activity towards histone H2A, although with much less efficiency (de Napoles et al., 2004; Cao et al., 2005; Wei et al., 2006). In addition, it has been known for several years now that the composition of PRCs can vary among tissues and different developmental stages (Squazzo et al., 2006; Kuzmichev et al., 2005; de Napoles et al., 2004; Pasini et al., 2007). Therefore, Ring1b might not be essential in every promoter-bound PcG repressive complex, although detailed analyses on this assumption have yet to be conducted.

How exactly PRC1 proteins are specifically targeted to development-related loci is unclear, since the PcG-recruiting Polycomb Responsive Elements (PREs) – specific DNA sequences of up to 600 base pairs in *Drosophila*, recognized by PcG complexes – have not been found in mammals (reviewed in Ringrose and Paro, 2007). Initially, it was thought chromatin marks set by PRC2 recruit PRC1 to chromatin, but recent discoveries challenge this model. Francis and

co-workers demonstrated that compaction of chromatin by Polycomb group proteins requires nucleosomes but not histone tails, which of course contain the H3K27me3 mark (Francis et al., 2004). Although it is unclear to what extent this holds true, at the very least it demonstrates there must be alternative mechanisms. For example, it has been proposed that recruitment of PcG-silencing complexes could be mediated through interactions with site-specific DNA-binding factors, with the aforementioned stem cell specific transcription factors like Rex1 or Oct4 as likely candidates. A third, intriguing possibility is provided by Elderkin and co-workers, who showed that Mel18 is responsible for targeting Ring1b towards its substrate, lysine 119 of histone H2A (Elderkin et al., 2007). Whereas Ring1b is required for E3 ligase function, Mel18 appears to target the complex to H2AK119, since specific RING domain mutants of Mel18 retained the ability to dimerize with Ring1b, but failed to localize to H2AK119. Still, this experiment lacks data showing physical binding of the dimer to H2A, which leaves several alternative explanations open.

Another interesting observation from our Ring1b binding/expression study in ES cells, comes from a comparative analysis of our expression profiling data with recently published global chromatin-state maps generated of mouse ES cells. This revealed that Ring1b almost exclusively binds to genes with GC-rich promoters (so-called CpG-islands, often acting as promoter themselves). Tanay and co-workers already showed a strong correlation between promoters with highly conserved CpG islands and SuZ12 binding domains in human ES cells, providing yet another correlation between PRC1 and PRC2 in ES cells (Tanay et al., 2007). Genes with CpG islands are associated with active H3K4me3 histone marks or with bivalent domains. These bivalent chromatin domains – containing histones with both the H3K4me3 mark, associated with active genes, and the

H3K27me3 mark, the PRC2 mark associated with silenced genes – were proposed to be involved in setting developmental genes in a sort of inactive but standby state, rather than completely silencing them, to keep the genome flexible enough to quickly switch to a certain lineage during differentiation. Both the active as well as the repressive mark would already be present, to poise local genes for any transcriptional state (Bernstein et al., 2006; Stock et al., 2007; Mikkelsen et al., 2007; Azuara et al., 2006). Although this may be true, Mohn and colleagues found that bivalency is not restricted to ES cells (Mohn et al., 2008). Looking at histone methylation status and promoter occupancy during differentiation from ES cells to neural progenitor cells and finally to committed neurons, they see no significant differences in the strong correlation between bivalent domains and CpG islands. Over 80 percent of the bivalent promoters contain CpG islands, irrespective of the cell type, indicating that promoter sequence composition rather than lineage commitment may be critical for bivalency. Importantly, a significant subset of bivalent is lost, and new bivalent domains are formed at every differentiation step, indicating that a bivalent state is highly dynamic during differentiation.

To make things even more complicated, our comparative analysis even revealed that a considerable number of Ring1b bound genes with an active H3K4me3 mark are mainly repressed in ES cells. This is again in agreement with findings by others, both in ES cells and more committed cells like embryonic fibroblasts and neural progenitor cells (NPCs) (Bracken et al., 2006; Lee et al., 2006; Breiling et al., 2004; Barski et al., 2007; Guenther et al., 2007). The absence of H3K27me3 at these promoters means that Ring1b can apparently be recruited independently from PRC2, the PcG complex that sets the H3K27me3 mark. This suggests that Ring1b acts more like a modulator of transcriptional activity of bivalent

genes in ES cells and, even more interesting, more committed cells, rather than a silencer. This might be a PRC1-independent function of Ring1b, although that is speculation at this moment.

X-chromosome inactivation requires PcG proteins

A very interesting branch of PcG research concerns the X-chromosome. Silencing of one X-chromosome in female somatic cells is a necessary mechanism to compensate for the fact that female somatic cells have two copies of the X-chromosome, as opposed to male somatic cells, that have only one. This feature is also known as dosage compensation. As explained in detail in a recent review (Wutz and Gribnau, 2007), the inactive X-chromosome (X_i) is silenced by packaging the entire chromosome into transcriptionally inactive heterochromatin. The *Xist* (X-inactive specific transcript) gene on the X-chromosome plays a key role in both initiation and maintenance of inactivation. It encodes a 17 kb non-coding RNA (ncRNA) that coats the X-chromosome, initiating silencing. (Intriguingly, expression of the *Xist* gene on another chromosome leads to silencing of that chromosome.) Initially, *Xist* is expressed at low levels from both chromosomes. During the inactivation process, the future active X-chromosome (X_a) ceases to express *Xist*, whereas the future X_i increases *Xist* RNA production. The silencing of genes along the X_i occurs after coating the chromosome by *Xist* RNA. Compared to the X_a , the X_i has high levels of DNA methylation, H3K9 methylation and H3K27 trimethylation (H3K27me3), and low levels of histone acetylation and H3K4 methylation. These chromatin marks are all associated with gene silencing. Additionally, a histone variant called macroH2A is exclusively found on the X_i .

Initial reports suggested that PcG proteins Eed and EZH2 are involved in initiation of X-chromosome inactivation, since they are

enriched on the inactive X-chromosome during early stages of inactivation (Chadwick and Willard, 2003; Mak et al., 2002; Silva et al., 2003; Hernandez-Munoz et al., 2005). However, shortly after that, it was shown that mouse embryos deficient for the PcG protein Eed are still capable of initiating and maintaining X-chromosome inactivation, arguing against such a mechanism (Kalantry and Magnuson, 2006; Schoeftner et al., 2006). Instead, it was now proposed that PcG proteins might protect the inactive X-chromosome from reactivation as a result of differentiation (Kalantry et al., 2006). Only very recently, a 1.6 kb ncRNA termed RepA was identified to reside on the inactive X-chromosome. RepA directly binds to Polycomb group protein EZH2, thereby recruiting PRC2 to the X_i (Zhao et al., 2008). RepA deletion was found to abolish both Xist induction and trimethylation on lysine 27 of histone H3 (H3K27me3) along nucleosomes of the X-chromosome, suggesting Polycomb group proteins do play a role in initiation of X-inactivation. Still, these observations remain correlations, since no study has been able to completely dissect the mechanisms underlying X-chromosome inactivation, enabling a crucial experimental setup with only the putative necessary components for X-inactivation and the X-chromosome itself. The link with PRC1 members, including Bmi1 and Ring1b, is even less clear and sometimes contradictory. A recent report found that Ring1b is dispensable in the initiation of X-chromosome silencing by Xist (Leeb and Wutz, 2007), which is in disagreement with earlier findings suggesting that Ring1b is involved in initiation of X-inactivation, based on transient association of Ring1b with the inactive X-chromosome (Fang et al., 2004). Apart from the discussion about the precise moment at which PRC1/Ring1b jumps in to contribute to X-chromosome inactivation, there is a strong correlation between monoubiquitination of histone H2A on the

X-chromosome and X-chromosome silencing. Therefore, it is conceivable that PRC1 does play a role in X-chromosome silencing.

Ring1b and Bmi1 in neuronal development

Arguably one of the most important changes in the way we think about PcG proteins, is that they were found to not only repress *Hox* genes, but many other genes that are involved in proliferation and development. This helped us greatly to understand how PcG proteins orchestrate development of tissues and organs during embryonic development. The organ that has had a lot of attention as a model organ for PcG mediated control of development, is the central nervous system. Previously, we have shown that *Bmi1* knockout mice have a smaller cerebellum, an effect that is even stronger in compound knockout mice, harboring two *Bmi1* null alleles and one *Ring1b* null allele (Voncken et al., 2003e; van der Lugt et al., 1994). Therefore, we decided to look at the absence of *Ring1b* only in the Central Nervous System (CNS), as described in chapter 4. We used our conditional knockout model of *Ring1b* and a mouse expressing the *Cre* transgene under the control of the *Nestin* promoter (N_{Cre}). The *Nestin* gene is expressed from E7.5 and can be detected in many proliferating CNS regions. Notably, at E15.5 and P0 expression is observed throughout the developing cerebellum and in the ventricular and subventricular areas of the developing telencephalon (Tronche et al., 1999; Dahlstrand et al., 1995).

The cerebellum – also referred to as ‘small brain’ or hindbrain – is the region of the brain located in the inferior posterior part of the head and is macroscopically distinct from the cerebrum. The cerebellum plays an important role in the integration of sensory perception and motor control. In order to coordinate motor control, there are many neural pathways linking the cerebellum with the cerebral motor cortex and the spinocerebellar tract, which provides information on the position of the body.

Cerebellar abnormalities often lead to disorders in fine movement, equilibrium, posture, and motor learning, rather than paralysis, which is in agreement with the idea that the cerebellum integrates these functions.

Given the important functions of the cerebellum, the severe phenotype of the *Ring1b* full knockout – embryonic lethality, as discussed in an earlier paragraph – and the failure of embryonic stem cells to maintain pluripotency, it is somewhat surprising to find that the *Ring1b* CNS null mutant is viable, although they are born in submendelian ratios and usually die within a month after birth. Macroscopically these animals clearly suffer from neurological defects. Histological inspection of their brains reveal two major defects: a reduced size of the cerebellum and a foliation defect in the cerebellum, both of which will be discussed in more detail in this paragraph. In addition to these observations, *Ring1b* CNS null mice exhibit progressive growth retardation which is also observed in animals deficient for *Bmi1*. It has been assumed that *Bmi1* knockout mice are smaller due to systemic *Bmi1* absence, but the CNS-specific *Ring1b* knockout argues that the activity of PcG in the CNS alone could determine body size. This is not unprecedented: conditional deletion of *Gli2*, one of the main downstream targets of developmental morphogen Sonic Hedgehog (Shh), in the cerebellum causes a reduction in total body weight and leads to problems in coordinating muscle movement, like the *Bmi1* and *Ring1b* deficient mice (Corrales et al., 2006).

Although it is tempting to compare the cerebellar phenotypes of the *Bmi1* knockout, *Ring1b* CNS knockout, and the *Bmi1/Ring1b* compound knockout mice, one should be careful in drawing conclusions from these comparisons. Their reduced cerebella may seem similar on the macroscopic level, histological analysis revealed important differences. In the case of *Bmi1* deletion, most striking are the absence of neurons and improper arborization of dendrites in the molecular layer (van der

Lugt et al., 1994). The *Ring1b* null cerebellum is characterized by a foliation defect, lacking an anterior fissure resulting in the fusion of two lobules. These are notable differences, suggesting that *Bmi1* and *Ring1b* may have different roles in the development of the cerebellum. However, arguing against this different role, is the finding that Shh governs cerebellar foliation (Wechsler-Reya and Scott, 1999; Corrales et al., 2006; Corrales et al., 2004; Lewis et al., 2004), and the fact that *Bmi1* has previously been implicated in Shh signaling in the cerebellum (Leung et al., 2004). We and others proposed before, that *Bmi1* is induced by Shh to prevent expression of the *Ink4a/Arf* genes, which will allow the cerebellar granule neuron precursors (CGNPs) to proliferate (Leung et al., 2004; Bruggeman et al., 2005).

Foliation patterns in the cerebellum vary between species and even within different mouse strains (Inouye and Oda, 1980; Wahlsten and Andison, 1991; Cooper et al., 1991). Since our mice were in a mixed FVB/B6 background, one might argue that the observed fusion of lobules II and III might have been the result of combining the foliation patterns of two different strains. However, the control animals never displayed such fusions nor has it been described for any mouse strain before, making it highly unlikely that differences between strains account for the *Ring1b* cerebellar null phenotype. It was proposed that foliation occurs in distinct phases (Corrales et al., 2006). The original smooth-surfaced cerebellar anlage is divided by four fissures into the five cardinal lobes. After birth, these lobes separate further into (sub)lobules. In mice, cerebellar development is largely completed within the third postnatal week, but in humans cerebellar development takes much longer. This is further illustrated by the fact that the External Granular Layer (EGL) – found on the exterior the cerebellum producing granule neurons – persists for approximately fifteen months. Notably, defects in cerebellar foliation in

humans are associated with a number of clinical abnormalities, including Fukuyama congenital muscular dystrophy, Joubert's syndrome and Walker-Warburg syndrome (Demaerel, 2002). Although different syndromes in many aspects, they share clinical characteristics specific for cerebellar function, like a lack of control of muscle movement, coordination problems, seizures, speech problems, and abnormal breathing patterns. This underscores the importance of proper cerebellar foliation.

The exact position of the fissures is determined by an unknown mechanism, but the number and extent of folia that arise are dose-dependently regulated by Shh induced CGNP proliferation (Corrales et al., 2006; Lewis et al., 2004; Wechsler-Reya and Scott, 1999; Corrales et al., 2004). Shh is secreted by the large Purkinje neurons, located in the Purkinje layer, the middle layer of the cerebellar cortex. Mice lacking Purkinje neurons do not secrete Shh, are impaired in EGL formation and concomitantly in foliation (Caddy and Biscoe, 1979; SIDMAN et al., 1962; Wetts and Herrup, 1982; Smeyne et al., 1995). Shh stimulates progression through the cell cycle by activating Cyclin D1 and Cyclin D2 through the induction of N-Myc on the transcriptional level (Ciemerych et al., 2002; Kenney et al., 2004). Knoepfler and co-workers used an *NCre* conditional knockout system for *N-Myc* to specifically address the effect of loss of *N-Myc* in the brain. This revealed, among other characteristic abnormalities, reduced CGNP proliferation, perturbation of foliation, and a markedly reduced cerebellar mass (Knoepfler et al., 2002). The main difference between the Gli family of transcription factors – believed to be the main downstream effectors of Shh signaling – and N-Myc lies in the fact that Shh signaling effects on the former is more general, whereas the effects on the latter seems restricted to immature, proliferating precursor cells in the proliferative zone of the cerebellum (Altaba, 1999). Of note, N-Myc can generally only be detected during cerebellar growth.

At this moment, the link between the Shh signaling pathway and *Ring1b* is not based on experimental evidence but mere correlation. However, the foliation defects in *Ring1b* CNS null mutants strongly suggest perturbation of Shh signaling during development of *Ring1b* null brains, possibly through the Gli family of transcription factors or through N-Myc. To investigate this possible link between Shh signaling and *Ring1b*, it would be worthwhile to analyze Gli1 expression patterns in the *Ring1b* null cerebellum, since Gli1 is often used as a readout for Shh signaling (Corrales et al., 2006). However, we should keep the possibility open that there might be other possibilities than a direct Shh-related effect, such as signaling through HGF-Met (Ieraci et al., 2002), BDNF-Trk (Schwartz et al., 1997) or BMP (Qin et al., 2006), and via transcription regulated by Math1 (Ben Arie et al., 1997) or Zic1 (Aruga et al., 1998). Finally, the foliation defect could also be accounted for by a possible connection between *Ring1b* and the homeodomain-containing transcription factors Engrailed-1 (*En-1*) and Engrailed-2 (*En-2*). Engrailed-1 and Engrailed-2 are both implicated in foliation and mutations in either gene causes a strong reduction in cerebellar size. Their expression pattern is partially overlapping, but after birth Engrailed-2 becomes exclusively expressed in the cerebellum (Davidson et al., 1988). Specific deletion of *En-1* evokes severe or mild cerebellar defects, depending on the mouse strain used. In the mild case, anterior defects in foliation occur (Wurst et al., 1994). Removal of *En-2* is associated with defects in the foliation of the vermis and hemispheres and altered parasagittal banding patterns (Millen et al., 1994; Kuemerle et al., 1997). More interestingly in this situation is the observation by Baader and co-workers, who showed that the *En-2* transgenic mouse also has foliation defects and smaller cerebellar size (Baader et al., 1999; Baader et al., 1998). In a candidate approach, we found *En-1* and *En-2* to be strongly upregulated

in many parts of the *Ring1b* null brains, except for the cerebellum, where only *En-1* showed a minor increase in expression level. Since we were unable to confirm these observations – based on quantitative real-time PCR (qPCR) – with histological stainings, possibly due to antibodies that were unable to detect Engrailed protein levels in our experimental setup, we have to be careful in drawing conclusions from them. However, assuming the observations are in fact indicative of derepression of *Engrailed* genes in the cerebral hemispheres due to *Ring1b* ablation in the brain, it is remarkable that the cerebral hemispheres did not show any abnormalities while Engrailed levels were five- to sixty-fold increased in the hippocampus (*En-1* and *En-2*), as well as the dorsal (*En-1* and *En-2*) and frontal (*En-2*) cortex. Just as surprising, whereas the cerebellum develops foliation defects in the absence of *Ring1b*, *En-1* and *En-2* expression seems to be hardly affected in the cerebellum.

There are several possible explanations for this. First, the induction of Engrailed genes in the cerebellum because of *Ring1b* absence might be subtle and beyond the detection levels of our qPCR system. It is not unprecedented that a minor increase or decrease in protein levels of developmental genes are capable of evoking an effect. For example, this has been reported for the *Oct4* and *Nanog* embryonic stem cell markers. A subtle increase in Engrailed-2 expression levels could induce *Ring1b* null-like phenotypes, as demonstrated by the *En-2* transgenic mouse mentioned earlier. Second, since we did not do stainings at different time intervals, we might be looking at a time point where Engrailed induction does not evoke a response in the brain. It is known that Engrailed expression is tightly regulated, both in a spacial as well as a temporal manner. *En-1* is induced in the region of the cerebellar anlage at the one somite stage whereas *En-2* is found slightly later at the five somite stage (Davidson et al., 1988; Davis and Joyner, 1988; Davis et al., 1988;

McMahon et al., 1992). Perhaps one would not find elevated Engrailed levels at earlier time points in *Ring1b* null brains. The third and final possible explanation is perhaps the most likely one: the cerebellar foliation defect might not be caused by Engrailed upregulation but mediated through one of the other mechanisms mentioned before. Either way, it remains puzzling why such a clear and strong induction of *Engrailed* genes in parts of the cerebral hemispheres does not immediately seem to affect cerebral morphology and function. However, it has been reported that the Engrailed genes are in fact implicated in the cerebral hemispheres, such as in the mesencephalic dopaminergic neurons forming the substantia nigra (Alberi et al., 2004), and in the serotonergic and noradrenergic neurons of the dorsal raphe nucleus and locus caeruleus (Simon et al., 2005). Therefore, it would be interesting to investigate whether these areas are affected in the *Ring1b* knockout brain. Furthermore, generation of *Ring1b;En-1* or, perhaps more interesting, *Ring1b;En-2* compound knockout mice might reveal whether or not there is a genetic interaction.

We believe that the second clear phenotype of the *Ring1b* CNS null mutant, the reduced size of its cerebellum, might be caused by a decreased proliferation potential of neural stem cells. Although we and others stated before that *Ring1b* interaction partner *Bmi1* might be induced by *Shh* signaling to prevent expression of the *Ink4a/Arf* genes, which will allow CGNPs to proliferate, we found that in the absence of *Ring1b*, *Ink4a/Arf* is derepressed in all areas of the brain, including the cerebellum. Derepression of *Ink4a/Arf* is usually associated with growth arrest or impaired growth, which could explain the reduced size of the *Ring1b* null cerebellum. As discussed in a paragraph before, a fine-balanced link between *Ring1b* and the *Ink4a/Arf* locus has already been established in hematopoietic lineages (Cales et al., 2008). In chapter 4 of this thesis, we demonstrate,

although not as detailed as Cales and co-workers have for the hematopoietic system, such a link between Ring1b and *Ink4a/Arf* in neural tissue. Co-deletion of the *Ink4a/Arf* locus in cultured Ring1b knockout Neural Stem Cells (NSCs) fully rescues the growth arrest we observed in Ring1b null NSCs alone. This indicates that at least part of this – rather remarkable, since the *in vivo* phenotype is relatively mild – arrest can be contributed to derepression of the Ink4a/Arf tumor suppressors. However, it should be taken into consideration that the *Ink4a/Arf* locus is extremely sensitive to stress, especially when cells are transferred from hypoxic *in vivo* conditions to oxygen-rich environments. It will be interesting and probably essential to cross our *NCre;Ring1b* knockout mice with *Ink4a/Arf* deficient mice, and analyze its relative contribution to the *Ring1b* null phenotypes under *in vivo* conditions.

The derepression of *Ink4a/Arf* in *Ring1b* null brains suggests that Bmi1 needs Ring1b as a co-factor to keep the *Ink4a/Arf* genes repressed. However, two alternative scenarios, independent of Bmi1, also provide possible explanations. First, p16^{ink4a}, activated by Ring1b, is an inhibitor of the Cyclin D/CDK complexes, leading to markedly reduced cellular proliferation; its ectopic expression might compromise the mitogenic activity of Shh. Second, p19^{arf} controls proliferation through modulation of p53 activity and directly regulates the activity of N-Myc homologue c-Myc, which has also been demonstrated to be involved in cerebellar development. Both of these pathways might affect CGNP proliferation and foliation (Zindy et al., 2006; Datta et al., 2004; Qi et al., 2004).

Ring1b: an E3 ubiquitin ligase at the heart of PcG protein complexes

PcG protein Ring1b is often referred to as a 'core protein' of PRC1. It turns up in almost every PRC1-like complex that is identified, suggesting it has a function in many different processes that require PcG proteins. It is one

of few PRC1 members to be essential for life in knockout mouse studies, its ablation leading to a gastrulation arrest after approximately six days of gestation (Voncken et al., 2003). In addition, several *in vitro* studies revealed an absolute requirement of Ring1b protein to maintain cell viability and stem cell identity (Terranova et al., 2008; Leeb and Wutz, 2007; Miyagishima et al., 2003; chapter 3 of this thesis). Finally, Ring1b appears to harbor an IRES in its 5' UTR, enabling it to be translated under conditions when normal protein synthesis is impaired or blocked (discussed in chapter 2 & 5 of this thesis). Taken together, it is no surprise that over the past years much of the attention of the PcG research field has shifted towards Ring1b. The function of Ring1b, however, remained elusive until it was found to be responsible for the long-known monoubiquitination of histone H2A at K119 (Wang et al., 2004). As discussed in the earlier paragraphs, H2AK119ub1 has a strong and long-standing correlation with transcriptional silencing, H3K27me3 histone marks, and X-chromosome silencing. Moreover, not only H2A seems to be a Ring1b target for monoubiquitination, but also H2A.Z, a variant histone which has been associated with a wide variety of cellular processes, although its precise function is unclear (Sarcinella et al., 2007). In 2008, Creyghton and co-workers first implicated H2A.Z in cellular differentiation (Creyghton et al., 2008). They used chip-on-ChIP analysis to map H2A.Z enrichment in murine ES cells to the promoter regions of genes with roles in organ development, cell differentiation, and cell fate commitment. Notably, 93 percent of these target genes were also found to be occupied by SuZ12 in previous studies, with a similar and characteristic spatial patterning (Boyer et al., 2006). In neural precursors (NP) they found a similar promoter enrichment, but on a different set of genes. These genes were relatively active and the majority did not have SuZ12 bound to them, which led the authors to postulate that PcG and H2A.Z co-occupation of promoters is

a hallmark of ES cells. Furthermore, they show that H2A.Z enriched genes display an overall tendency to become derepressed in H2A.Z-deficient ES cells, and that H2A.Z deficient ES cells fail to differentiate normally. Together, these data suggest that interplay between PcG proteins and H2A.Z has an important role in mediating cell fate transitions. Since the significance of Ring1b as an H2A.Z E3 ubiquitin ligase was not tested in this study, it would be very interesting to try to link H2A.Z monoubiquitination status in Ring1b deficient ES cells, primary cells and knockout embryos, to the results described in the study of Creighton and co-workers.

Ring1a, Bmi1 and Mel18 have been reported to form heterodimers with Ring1b, each influencing its E3 ligase activity. In case of Ring1b/Ring1a and Ring1b/Bmi1 heterodimers, the E3 ligase activity was enhanced *in vitro* as compared to Ring1b alone (Cao et al., 2005), whereas Ring1a and Bmi1 alone did not have any E3 ligase activity towards H2AK119 (Wang et al., 2004). Mel18 was found to have a different, but intriguing function, targeting the Ring1b/Mel18 heterodimer to its substrate, lysine 119 of H2A, as discussed in more detail in a previous paragraph (Elderkin et al., 2007). However, there seems to be disagreement over the role of contributing factors in the E3 ligase activity of Ring1b. For example, Cao and co-workers found that removing Bmi1 from an *in vitro* complex of Ring1b, Ring1a and Pc3, and substituting it for close relative Mel18, abolished ligase activity completely. This is clearly not what we and others have found, that Ring1b is capable of functioning as an E3 ligase on its own as well as together with Ring1a. Moreover, two independent studies report functional redundancy of Ring1a. We found that Ring1a can substitute for Ring1b in *in vitro* ubiquitination assays without compromising efficiency (Buchwald et al., 2006), and De Napoles and co-workers found functional redundancy *in vivo* of Ring1a in H2A

monoubiquitination (de Napoles et al., 2004). They show that in Ring1a/Ring1b double null female ES cells, all H2AK119ub1 marks in the cell were abolished, whereas in Ring1b null cells, the mark was retained on the inactive X-chromosome only. This immediately raises the intriguing possibility that Ring1a is capable of setting the H2AK119u1 mark on the inactive X-chromosome on its own, but not anywhere else. However, how exactly this specificity is organized, is still unclear.

In 2006, we and others determined the structure of the Bmi1/Ring1b heterodimer (Buchwald et al., 2006; Li et al., 2006). In the structure the arrangement of the RING-domains of both proteins is similar to that of another H2A E3 ligase, the BRCA1/BARD1 complex. Heterodimerization depends on the N-terminal arm of Ring1b that embraces the Bmi1 RING-domain. Mutation of a critical residue in the domains responsible for interaction between the E2 conjugating enzyme and Ring1b shows that the catalytic activity resides in Ring1b. Moreover, the N-terminal RING-domains of both proteins, through which the interaction takes place, are sufficient for E3 ligase activity *in vitro*.

An interesting observation on Ring1b/Bmi1 autopolyubiquitination came from Ben-Saadon and co-workers. They found that, upon heterodimerization with Bmi1, Ring1b generates mixed K6-, K27-, and K48-based polyubiquitin chains, a modification they found to be required for monoubiquitination of H2A *in vitro* (Ben Saadon et al., 2006). This type of polyubiquitination is atypical and not the K48-type of canonical polyubiquitination associated with protein degradation. Instead, Ring1b requires K6, K27, and K48 of ubiquitin for efficient autopolyubiquitination. They propose that this new form of autopolyubiquitination may regulate Ring1b activity towards H2A. The mechanism of function of these polyubiquitin chains can be via alteration of the protein structure, or via serving as a recognition

element enhancing its binding to specific locations.

The emerging importance of ubiquitination in PcG function was further strengthened by the finding that Bmi1 can be monoubiquitinated as well, as a part of the E3 ubiquitin ligase complex consisting of Spop and Cullin3, that together ubiquitinate histone MacroH2A, a histone variant specifically localized to the inactive X-chromosome (Hernandez-Munoz et al., 2005). More recently, it was found that another Ring1b interaction partner, RYBP, can also be monoubiquitinated, a process that is enhanced by the presence of Ring1b (Arrigoni et al., 2006). Moreover, RYBP binds to uH2A, the substrate for Ring1b's E3 ligase activity

in association with gene silencing processes. These were all observations, unfortunately, a functional explanation has not yet been found.

Over the past two decades the field of PcG research has evolved from segmentation studies in flies to massive genome-wide approaches and detailed histone-remodeling experiments today. Although the picture of how PcG proteins – and Ring1b at the heart of it – exhibit their function has become much more clear, there is still a lot to be investigated. From the missing knockout mouse models to the exciting new data on elusive histone codes and non-coding RNAs, the Polycomb group still holds much to be discovered.

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Chapter 2

Introduction & Discussion

Control of protein levels by
specific sequences in
a transcript's UTRs

Life is short, so break the rules, forgive quickly, kiss slowly, love truly, laugh uncontrollably, and never regret anything that made you smile.

Twenty years from now you will be more disappointed by the things you didn't do than by the ones you did. So throw off the bowlines. Sail away from the safe harbor. Catch the trade winds in your sails. Explore. Dream. Discover.

Mark Twain

Introduction: Control of protein levels by specific sequences in a transcript's UTRs

Control of translation in eukaryotic cells is a very complicated and multi-layered process that involves hundreds of proteins. A strong link with cancer has emerged over the last decade, since many cancer cells have deregulated translation machineries, and several translation initiation factors and ribosomal proteins have oncogenic properties. To date, three different mechanisms for protein synthesis can be distinguished in eukaryotic cells, one of which is by far the most common (canonical scanning) and two are more rare (ribosomal shunting and internal ribosome entry). This chapter will mainly focus on internal ribosome entry, since Chapter 5 of this thesis describes the discovery of an IRES in the 5' UTR of Polycomb group protein Ring1b.

Canonical scanning

Under normal circumstances, it is thought that translation of the vast majority of transcripts occurs via the mechanism of canonical scanning (figure 1A), a process that has been well-characterized over the past decades (Kozak, 1989). Initiation starts with the recognition of the 7-methyl guanosine cap (M⁷GpppN or m⁷G) at the 5' end of mRNAs by the translation initiation complex, eukaryotic initiation factor 4F (eIF4F) (reviewed in Gingras et al., 1999). The eIF4F protein complex is a heterotrimer consisting of eIF4G – a scaffolding protein – and eIF4E – the actual cap binding unit – and eIF4A – a dead box RNA helicase. eIF4F is associated with the 40S subunit of the ribosome via eIF3, which itself consists of eleven different subunits. The 40S subunit consists of the 18S rRNA and at least 33 proteins. Most rate-limiting factors and initiation-regulating mechanisms in translational control are found in the binding of the 40S subunit to the mRNA transcript. This is also called the scanning subunit since it is responsible for scanning the 5' part of the transcript in the 5' to 3' direction for an AUG in an appropriate context. Once it encounters this start signal, all initiation factors dissociate, the 60S ribosome subunit binds the 40S subunit and elongation starts. Elongation is preceded by binding of the initiator tRNA Met-tRNA^{Met}

to the 40S subunit. Each ribosome has three binding sites for tRNA: the A-, P-, and E-sites (short for aminoacyl-tRNA, peptidyl-tRNA, and exit, respectively), which transfer the amino acids to the growing polypeptide chain.

Circularization of the mRNA, achieved by association of both the poly-A tail binding protein (PABP) and the cap-binding protein eIF4E with eIF4G, greatly enhances translation. In an elegant experiment using atomic force microscopy (AFM), it was demonstrated that the purified yeast homologues of eIF4G, eIF4E and PABP alone were sufficient to circularize capped and polyadenylated RNA (Wells et al., 1998).

Termination of translation occurs when the ribosome encounters the stop codon. The newly synthesized polypeptide chain then dissociates from the ribosome and the ribosome becomes available for initiation of translation of another protein again.

Ribosomal shunting

A second mechanism by which transcripts can be translated into proteins is ribosomal shunting, also called discontinuous scanning. Thought to be very rare in eukaryotic cells, many things are unclear about the precise factors involved in this process. The mechanism has initially been described for heat shock

protein 70 (hsp70) (Yueh and Schneider, 2000), after which a few other proteins were found to be translated via this process, including cellular inhibitor of apoptosis 2 (cIAP2) (Sherrill and Lloyd, 2008) and beta-site amyloid precursor protein-cleaving enzyme 1 (BACE1) (Rogers, Jr. et al., 2004). It is thought that the process of ribosomal shunting is identical to that of canonical scanning up until the scanning phase. The ribosomal subunits then encounters a stable RNA hairpin-containing structure that halts the scanning process or even makes the ribosome detach from the transcript; this site is referred to as the cap proximal shunt donor. This arrest is followed by intramolecular shunting of the ribosomal subunit to a landing site – the AUG proximal shunt acceptor – downstream of the stable RNA structure responsible for blocking the scanning. The factors involved in this shunting process are not known, but it was found that RNA sequences immediately downstream of the RNA hairpin are complementary to 3' sequences of the 18S ribosomal subunit RNA. It was proposed, that the 18S subunit binds both these sequences and the 40S subunit to provide a recruiting mechanism back to the transcript after the arrest (Chappell et al., 2006). Now the ribosome resumes scanning again until the next start codon is encountered, after which the ribosomal shunting mechanism is again identical to that of canonical scanning.

Internal Ribosome Entry

Another minority of transcripts however, do not follow either one of these mechanisms. In 1988, two groups found that picornaviruses (e.g. encephalomyocarditis virus and poliovirus) use a mechanism independent of the 5' cap site of a transcript (Jang et al., 1988; Pelletier et al., 1988). Instead, a highly structured 5' untranslated region (UTR) was found to be able to recruit the translational machinery on its own (figure 1D). The element was named internal ribosome entry site (IRES) and is since

then found in many viruses and, later on, also cellular RNAs. An IRES is usually several hundreds of nucleotides long, harboring strong and multiple hairpin loops capable of blocking scanning of the transcript by the 40S ribosome subunit (reviewed in Hellen and Sarnow, 2001; Vagner et al., 2001; Martinez-Salas et al., 2008). A second common feature of IRESes is the existence of several unused AUGs upstream of the IRES or residing in the IRES, sometimes even one or more small open reading frames. Generally speaking, an IRES circumvents many inhibiting or modulating mechanisms in translation, since it does not need a cap site and can therefore do without eIF4E, the highly conserved cap binding subunit of the eIF4F translation initiation complex essential for cap dependent translation, and the eIF4E binding domain of eIF4G (explained in more detail below). This makes an IRES a favorable means of translation initiation by proteins involved in key regulatory processes, whose presence is required under circumstances where normal (cap-dependent) translation is halted. Not only does the IRES provide a way of continuing translation, it might also play a role in enhancing translation under certain conditions or it can function as an extra regulatory layer. Supporting the latter possibility is the finding that internal ribosome entry is not restricted to uncapped transcripts only. Several viral and cellular transcripts have been found that are actually capped, but have 5' UTRs with a significant secondary structure and that do not require eIF4E for translation. Most notably, these include mRNAs from hepatitis C virus (Tsukiyama-Kohara et al., 1992), fibroblast growth factor 2 (Vagner et al., 1995), and the c-myc transcription factor and proto-oncogene (Nanbru et al., 1997). Interestingly, translation of the latter two cellular genes can be enhanced by eIF4E overexpression – indicating cap-dependency – as well as by shutting down cap-dependent translation (Kevil et al., 1995; Rosenwald et al., 1995).

Figure 1. Cap-dependent and IRES-mediated translation under different conditions

(A) Cap-dependent translation can progress, since 4E-BP is phosphorylated and cannot prevent association of eIF4G with eIF4E. The black line depicts an RNA strand with its poly-A tail, the AUG start codon and the m⁷G cap. Note the scaffolding function of eIF4G, the binding of PABP (Poly-A binding protein) to eIF4G, and the eIF3 link with the 40S ribosomal subunit.

(B) Cap-dependent translation is halted, since the eIF4E binding domain of eIF4G is cleaved off by a viral protease (2Apro or 3Cpro).

(C) Cap-dependent translation is halted, because 4E-BP is dephosphorylated and can therefore bind to eIF4E, preventing the association of the latter with eIF4G.

(D) IRES-mediated translation is cap-independent and does not need eIF4E nor the eIF4E binding domain of eIF4G. Therefore, IRES-mediated translation can progress even in the presence of viral proteases and hypophosphorylated 4E-BP. Note the IRES trans-acting factors (ITAFs), associating with both the IRES and the scaffolding protein eIF4G.

Recently a striking difference between cap-dependent and IRES-independent translation – also named internal initiation – was discovered. As mentioned earlier, cap-dependent translation is usually greatly enhanced by PABP/eIF4E/eIF4G-mediated circularization of the RNA. In a recent study it was found,

that efficient IRES-mediated translation of c-myc and BiP does not require PABP or intact eIF4G; the poly-A tail alone seems to be enough for efficient translation (Thoma et al., 2004). Translation of these transcripts was not impaired after depletion of PABP from HeLa extracts, leading to the conclusion that the

PABP/eIF4G bridging complex is dispensable for IRES-mediated stimulation of translation by the poly-A tail of the transcript. More research is necessary, however, to provide a better basis for these controversial findings.

To date, several dozens of cellular proteins have been found that have an IRES in their 5' UTR enabling them to be translated under circumstances when cap-dependent translation is impaired. For example, VEGF and Hif1 α have IRESes that are induced by oxidative stress (Stein et al., 1998; Lang et al., 2002), IRES-mediated translation of cat-1 is induced by amino acid starvation (Fernandez et al., 2001), the recently found p53 IRES seems to become more active during DNA damage (Grover et al., 2008; Yang et al., 2006), and the c-myc IRES is specifically active during apoptosis (Stoneley et al., 2000), genotoxic stress (Subkhankulova et al., 2001) as well as G₂M transition (Kim et al., 2003). In Chapter 5 of this thesis, we add another protein to this growing list. Polycomb group protein Ring1b was found to also harbor an IRES in its 5' UTR, one that is unusually small and highly active under all conditions tested.

The role of eIF4E

Of the dozens of eukaryotic initiation factors involved in translation, 4E is the least abundant and therefore found to be the rate-limiting factor in translation experiments (Duncan et al., 1987). Inhibition of eIF4E leads to a strong decline in cap-dependent translation in the cell, as was demonstrated by depletion of eIF4E in cell-free extracts. In the same experiment, translation was fully restored by addition of recombinant eIF4E (Svitkin et al., 1996). The low abundance of eIF4E makes it an attractive target for regulatory mechanisms, controlled by both the cell as well as by foreign agents or viral proteins. Indeed, cellular regulatory mechanisms for eIF4E activity were found at the transcriptional level, by phosphorylation and by binding to inhibitory proteins.

eIF4E was found to be strongly upregulated at the transcriptional level in mouse embryonic fibroblasts by treatment with growth factors and subsequent logarithmic growth of the cells (Rosenwald et al., 1993). A correlation in different stages of the cell cycle was found between mRNA levels of myc and eIF4E during this treatment. It was proposed that upregulation of eIF4E was likely to be necessary in fast-growing tumor cells. Indeed, several studies have pointed to strong correlations between elevated mRNA levels of eIF4E, tumor progression and malignant transformation (Schmidt, 2004; Mamane et al., 2007). Moreover, stable myc overexpression results in increased levels of eIF4E, and eIF4E and myc cooperate in B-cell lymphomagenesis (Ruggero et al., 2004). Several myc binding sites (E-boxes) were identified in the eIF4E promoter (Jones et al., 1996).

Dephosphorylation of eIF4E was found to be directly related to translation rates. More specifically, heat-shock induces rapid dephosphorylation of eIF4E and a strong decline in translational activity (Duncan et al., 1987). Of note, the opposite effect is less unambiguous, although in most cases phosphorylation of eIF4E on Ser209 by Mnk1 kinase seems to promote translation (Waskiewicz et al., 1999), and in case of several tumor cell lines to be even essential for translation (Silva and Wendel, 2008; Wendel et al., 2007). Interestingly, the Mnk1/2 kinases are dispensable in mice, making them an interesting target for anti-cancer therapies (Ueda et al., 2004). In a study where translation rates were investigated after the recovery of human kidney cells from hypertonic stress, hypertonic shock caused inhibition of protein synthesis and disaggregation of polysomes (Vries et al., 1997). This was associated with the dephosphorylation of several initiation factors and ribosomal proteins, among which was eIF4E. The return of cells to isotonic medium rapidly promoted the phosphorylation of eIF4E, promoted polysome assembly and

increased translation rates. Interestingly, using an inhibitor of Mnk1, it was shown that *de novo* initiation of translation and formation of the eIF4F initiation complex did not require eIF4E phosphorylation. The functional consequences of the phosphorylation state of eIF4E in translational control is therefore far from complete.

Perhaps the most interesting way of inhibiting eIF4E and therefore also global protein synthesis, is by its binding to inhibitory factors. The arguably best-characterized family of these is the 4E binding protein (4E-BP) family. These small (10 – 12 kDa) and tough (heat and acid resistant) proteins compete with eIF4G – the scaffolding subunit of eIF4F – for binding to eIF4E. Phosphorylation of 4E-BPs prevents their binding to eIF4E, allowing eIF4E to associate with eIF4G instead, resulting in initiation of translation. Overexpression of 4E-BPs, generating a lot of hypophosphorylated 4E-BP and massive binding to eIF4G, results in inhibition of cap-dependent translation by preventing the formation of eIF4F. Cap-independent translation is not affected (Poulin et al., 1998). Thus, 4E-BP phosphorylation strongly stimulates translation. Several proteins, among which are tumor suppressors (p53), hormones (insulin), growth factors (EGF, IGF, PDGF) and cytokines (TNF α), have been identified to promote 4E-BP phosphorylation, but as many factors have been identified promoting 4E-BP dephosphorylation (Constantinou and Clemens, 2005; reviewed in Mamane et al., 2006), indicating there's a strictly controlled balance between stimulating and inhibiting translation.

Several inhibitors have been identified acting in the 4E-BP pathway, of which rapamycin is perhaps the best known. Remarkably, dependent on the mRNA one looks at and the cell type one uses, rapamycin can be either a potent inhibitor of cap-dependent translation or no inhibitor at all (Pedersen et al., 1997), but in most cases the former is true and as such it is often employed

in experimental settings (Beretta et al., 1996). Rapamycin acts intracellularly by binding to FKBP12, an immunophilin with peptidyl-prolyl cis-trans isomerase (PPIase) activity, and subsequently to mTOR (mammalian target of rapamycin), inactivating it. Several inhibitors of mTOR, a kinase downstream of the Akt pathway and capable of stimulating translation by phosphorylating 4E-BP, are promising candidates for anti-cancer therapies, some of which are currently undergoing clinical trials (Mamane et al., 2006; Garcia-Maceira and Mateo, 2008; Smolewski, 2006; Mita et al., 2003; Shor et al., 2008).

An interesting final way of targeting the eIF4E subunit, is indirectly. Certain viruses employ proteases that cleave off the eIF4E binding domain of eIF4G (figure 1B & D), thereby preventing association of eIF4E with eIF4G, and as a consequence blocking the assembly of the eIF4F initiation complex (Haghighat et al., 1996). These proteases, which are also useful in experimental settings, are discussed in more detail below.

Viral IRESes

Since viral proteins themselves are often translated via IRESes, viruses would greatly benefit from shutting down cap-dependent translation in a cell, leaving the host's ribosomes fully available to the virus. Indeed, all picornaviruses and many other viruses have been found to harbor IRES-driven transcripts. In fact, IRESes were first identified in picornaviruses (Pelletier et al., 1988). None of the transcripts of these viruses has a capped 5' end, ruling out cap-dependent translation. Since then, a complex picture of cap-independent translation strategies by viruses has become apparent (reviewed in Martinez-Salas et al., 2008). Among others, viral IRESes have now been identified in poliovirus (Pelletier et al., 1988), hepatitis A virus (Glass et al., 1993), encephalomyocarditis virus (Jang et al., 1988), cricket paralysis virus

(Wilson et al., 2000), human immunodeficiency virus (Buck et al., 2001), and Kaposi's sarcoma-associated herpes virus (Bielecki and Talbot, 2001).

Picornaviruses, being the first organism in which viruses were identified, have been a well-studied model organism for IRESes since then. Their genome consists of 7000 – 8500 nucleotides in a single-strand RNA molecule enveloped by a capsid. The genome is a single open reading frame (ORF) flanked by extensive 5' and 3' UTRs of up to 1200 nucleotides. Their IRESes are generally between 300 and 500 nucleotides long and located in the 5' UTR, exhibiting significant secondary structure and containing numerous unused AUG codons. Remarkably, these two features are generally considered to be inhibitory for translation. Translation of picornavirus transcripts however is very efficient, even when cap-dependent protein synthesis is abolished (Belsham and Sonenberg, 1996).

To hijack the host cell's cap-dependent translation machinery, viruses use several different strategies. As mentioned above, some viruses (e.g. rhinovirus, poliovirus) employ proteases (protease 2A or 3C, also referred to as 2Apro and 3Cpro) that cleave off the eIF4E binding domain of eIF4G, preventing the assembly of the eIF4F initiation complex and efficiently shutting down protein synthesis (Haghighat et al., 1996). Experiments in HeLa cells with 2Apro and 3Cpro under the control of a tetracycline promoter led to rapid apoptosis (Calandria et al., 2004). 2Apro and 3Cpro are interesting tools in molecular biology, since they only cleave off the subunit responsible for cap-binding, leaving the rest of the complex intact, including the domain in eIF4G responsible for binding to eIF3, the initiation factor that recruits eIF4G to the 40S ribosomal subunit. Recently, it was established that 2Apro and 3Cpro not only act as proteases, but also have a positive effect on viral RNA stability, translation, negative-strand

initiation and replication in HeLa cells. The authors propose that since other viral proteins were not required for the observed effects, it is likely that cellular proteins modified by 2Apro mediate these effects (Jurgens et al., 2006).

Another method of shutting down cap-dependent translation used by certain viruses, is to influence signaling pathways culminating at eIF4E, by changing the phosphorylation status of eIF4E or 4E-BP. As explained above, hypophosphorylated forms of eIF4E and hyperphosphorylated forms of 4E-BP stimulate translation (figure 1A). Infection with both encephalomyocarditis virus (EMCV) and poliovirus inhibit 4E-BP1 phosphorylation (Gingras et al., 1996). Dephosphorylation of 4E-BP1 temporally coincided with the shutdown of protein synthesis by EMCV. Infection with adenovirus and influenza virus also causes dephosphorylation of eIF4E (Kleijn et al., 1996). In this study, a strong temporal correlation with the moment of virus entry into the host cell was established. However, as is the case with EMCV and poliovirus, the precise mechanisms by which the viruses go about this dephosphorylation, remains unclear. Interestingly, a recent study demonstrated that human cytomegalovirus (HCMV) infection activates signaling in the mTOR kinase pathway, causing hyperphosphorylation of 4E-BP and promotion of cap-dependent translation (Kudchodkar et al., 2006). Although this effect is the opposite of what many viruses with IRES-drive transcripts do, it might give a clue in what direction we should look to unravel the viral mechanism that changes the phosphorylation status of 4E-BP during infection.

Cellular IRESes

Shortly after the identification of the first viral IRESes, a cellular IRES was found in the 5' UTR of the GRP78 (78 kDa glucose-regulated precursor, also known as immunoglobulin heavy chain binding protein, BiP, or steroidogenesis-activator polypeptide) (Macejak and

gene name	species	IRES size (nt)	function/involved in
AML1/RUNX1	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	1561	proliferation ¹
Apaf-1	<i>Mus musculus</i>	583	apoptosis
AQP4	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	284	membrane channel
BCL2	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	1137	apoptosis
c-myc	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	393	proliferation, differentiation
Cat-1	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	224	amino acid transporter
Cyclin D1	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	209	cell cycle control
ELG1	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	460	genome stability maintenance
FGF1	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	434	proliferation
FMR1	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	252	RNA metabolism
Hif1 α	<i>Mus musculus</i>	257	cellular metabolism
hSNM1	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	918	exonuclease
IGF2	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	121	proliferation
Kcna4	<i>Mus musculus</i>	1197	voltage-gated potassium channel
L-myc	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	52	proliferation, differentiation
LEF1	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	1167	differentiation
c-myb	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	150	proliferation
MYT2	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	156	topoisomerase
n-myc	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	320	proliferation, differentiation
NRF	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	637	inflammation inhibitor
ODC1	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	303	amino acid metabolism
p27kip1	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	152	cell cycle regulation
DAP5	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	306	translation initiation factor ²
PDGF2/c-sis	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	1022	proliferation
PIM1	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	396	proliferation
RBM3	<i>Mus musculus</i>	22	translation regulation
Utrn	<i>Mus musculus</i>	506	cytoskeleton
XIAP	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	162	inhibition of apoptosis

¹ The TEL-AML1 fusion protein is involved in childhood leukemias

² eIF4G family member implicated in stimulating cap-independent translation

Table 1. An alphabetic list of a selection of experimentally verified cellular IRESes found in mammals

Sarnow, 1991). Subsequent studies tried to find indications about the extend of IRES-regulated cellular proteins. An interesting first indication was that five percent of all mRNAs remained associated with polyribosomes during poliovirus-induced shutdown of cap-dependent translation (Johannes et al., 1999).

The authors stated that it is likely that many of these mRNAs are translated via IRES-mediated mechanisms. A more recent study finds three percent in MCF7 cells during TRAIL-induced apoptosis (Bushell et al., 2006). Nowadays it is believed that as many as ten percent of all cellular proteins harbor IRES-like structures in

their 5' UTR (Stoneley and Willis, 2004; Spriggs et al., 2005). It is unclear, however, how many of these transcripts absolutely require their IRES, or how many transcripts use the IRES merely as an additional regulatory layer. A constantly updated list of independently verified cellular IRESes can be found on the net: <http://iresite.org> (Bonnal et al., 2003), and a selection of cellular IRESes is depicted in Table 1 on the next page.

Whereas for viruses the benefit of IRES-driven transcripts is quite clear, for cellular transcripts this is less obvious. Why would an organism invest in complicated 5' UTRs and alternative translation mechanisms, when there is no apparent cellular infrastructure to efficiently use them? The answer comes from a number of well-established cellular IRESes, whose function was characterized under specific circumstances where cap-dependent translation is stopped. These circumstances include viral infection, reduced amino acid availability, high temperature, genotoxic stress, mitosis, and oxidative stress. It is now generally believed, that cells often use IRESes to support translation of certain vital proteins under conditions that normally only favor cap-dependent mechanisms of translation (figure 1D).

The c-myc IRES is probably one of the best-characterized cellular IRESes. Since the c-myc transcript is capped and translated in a cap-dependent manner as well, it was immediately assumed that the c-myc IRES provided an extra regulatory element rather than an exclusive translation mechanism. Subsequent studies revealed that the c-myc IRES is active during mitosis (G₂M transition) (Pyronnet et al., 2000) and apoptosis (Stoneley et al., 2000). In the latter study, it was demonstrated that c-myc was still translated when more than 90 percent of the HeLa cells were apoptotic as a result of administration of TRAIL (tumor necrosis factor-related apoptosis-inducing ligand). In 1996 c-myc was the subject of a study in which a

first relationship between cancer and an IRES was established. A mutation was found in the c-myc IRES, corresponding with up to 25-fold increase in the amount of c-myc protein in different cell lines derived from patients with multiple myeloma (Paulin et al., 1996). This was not accompanied by a mutation in the c-myc ORF or by an increase in the overall levels of c-myc mRNA, but there was a 3.4-fold increase in the amount of c-myc mRNA associated with polysomes, indicating enhanced translation rather than enhanced transcription.

Another interesting example of a gene employing IRES-mediated translation strategies under difficult circumstances, is the cationic amino acid transporter (cat-1). Cat-1 facilitates the uptake of the essential amino acids arginine and lysine. It was demonstrated that amino acid starvation causes accumulation and increased translation of cat-1 mRNA from its IRES element, resulting in a 58-fold increase in protein levels and increased uptake of arginine (Fernandez et al., 2001). From a biological perspective this makes perfect sense: when the nutrient supply is limited, activation of IRES-mediated translation of mammalian mRNAs results in the synthesis of proteins essential for cell survival.

A final intriguing example of a cellular IRES comes from an initiation factor itself, the eIF4F scaffolding subunit eIF4G. In 1996, an IRES was identified in the 5' UTR of the most abundant of both eIF4G proteins (encoded by different genes), eIF4GI (Gan and Rhoads, 1996), which was later characterized in more detail (Byrd et al., 2002; Gan et al., 1998). In 2002, another group challenged this claim and showed that what was previously thought to be an essential polypyrimidine tract (PPT) in the eIF4GI IRES, was actually an essential part of a cryptic promoter, possibly encoding a truncated isoform of eIF4GI (Han and Zhang, 2002). The authors showed binding of C/EBP β , Sp1 and Ets transcription factors in the cryptic promoter and found no evidence for

IRES activity in their own dicistronic vectors. In 2005, however, it was reported that eIF4GI contains a cap-dependent IRES, adding to the confusion (Byrd et al., 2005). The authors attribute previous contradictory findings to confusion over the different eIF4GI open reading frames and isoforms, and show convincing evidence that eIF4GI is controlled by both cap-dependent as well as IRES-mediated mechanisms. They find that eIF4GI is expressed from several distinct mRNAs, generated from cryptic promoters and via alternative splicing. Several transcripts contain the IRES element, but the IRES was not confined to the 5' UTR. However, the 5' UTR did enhance IRES activity *in vivo* and seemed to play a role in initiation codon selection. Spectacularly, whereas IRES activity was found to be cap-dependent, it was activated by 2Apro-mediated cleavage of eIF4GI. In line with this finding, it still was able to promote translation during poliovirus-infection. So eIF4GI needs a cap to be present on its transcript, but can do without the cap-binding subunit of the eIF4F initiation complex.

These findings show there's still a lot we don't know about alternate translation mechanisms, but there is now growing evidence that certain genes employ multiple strategies of translation initiation, dependent on the conditions in the cell. Also, the eIF4GI story warned us for the first time that stringent test procedures are necessary to validate the claim that a certain gene harbors an IRES.

Structure/function relationships

One of the greatest goals in initial IRES research was to find a common motif or structure for all IRESes. Now it's clear such a thing does not exist. IRESes do share some common features, however. It is clear, that for an IRES to function, it needs an RNA sequence capable of folding back to itself and form a complex three-dimensional structure that can be recognized by IRES Trans-Acting Factors (ITAFs, explained

in more detail below). For this structure to be stable and function as a barrier for the eIF4A helicase subunit of the eIF4F initiation complex, the RNA sequence must contain relatively many guanine and cytosine nucleotides. (Since promoter regions often also contain GC-rich regions called CpG islands, this is a difficulty in identifying novel IRESes.) Also, it appears to be of less importance than in transcripts translated via canonical scanning, for the initiator codon to be in an appropriate context. In many cases it has been reported that a certain IRES-bearing transcript does not start translation from an initiator codon with a proper Kozak consensus sequence (GCCRCCAUGG; where R is a purine, and AUG the translation initiation codon). It was suggested that the structure of the IRES and its influence on the ribosome ultimately determines the initiator codon to be used, rather than the nucleotides in the close proximity of the AUG used (Spahn et al., 2004). Based on computer predictions, a common IRES structure containing a Y-shaped pseudoknot stem-loop structure followed by a smaller stem-loop for at least part of an IRES was proposed (Le and Maizel, Jr., 1997), but there's still a lack of experimental verification and exceptions are also known. Most of the known structure/function relationships nowadays come from the many studies that describe site-directed mutagenesis analyses of specific IRESes. These findings give a very mixed image. Sometimes conserved regions are dispensable, in other cases single mutations can completely abolish IRES function. Unfortunately, due to a lack of common motifs, it has to be concluded that these data are generally only useful for that particular gene.

Several classes or types of – mainly viral – IRESes have been introduced, but due to the number of different types and the lack of more than two or three members of every type, the use of such a system is questionable. For certain viruses within the same species or subtype, however, common structures have actually been found.

These consist of complex stem-loop structures, pseudoknots, polypyrimidine tracts and loose regions (reviewed in Martinez-Salas et al., 2008). Interestingly, some highly infectious viruses such as foot-and-mouth disease virus (FMDV) have developed compensatory mutations to counteract mutations within an IRES sequence to maintain the predicted structure of the IRES, suggestive of strong dependency on three-dimensional structure rather than nucleotide sequence (Martinez-Salas et al., 2001). Picornaviruses seem to have IRESes with a modular organization, with each module separated from other modules by loose regions with less conservation between species (Pilipenko et al., 2000). Every domain is suggested to have a distinct function in the IRES. For example, domains 4 and 5 are capable of binding to eIF4G, eIF4B, eIF3 and polypyrimidine tract binding protein (PTB), but were found to be insufficient to start translation. In this model, every domain is necessary but not sufficient to initiate protein synthesis.

Probably most of today's knowledge of a structure/function relationship in an IRES came from two studies in which a cryo-EM structure was determined of the cricket paralysis virus (CrPV) IRES attached to the human 40S ribosomal subunit and the yeast 80S ribosome (Spahn et al., 2004; Schuler et al., 2006). It was proposed before that CrPV skips the initiation phase and jumpstarts translation directly to elongation, being able to recruit the entire ribosome and necessary elongation factors via its IRES. CrPV would then position the first codon directly into the ribosomal A site, which is highly unusual because initiation normally starts from the P-site. The cryo-EM studies confirm this idea, showing that the CrPV IRES in fact functions as an RNA-based translation factor, interacting directly with the 40S and 60S subunits as well as with components of the A-, P- and E-sites. The interactions induce conformational changes in both the IRES as well as in the ribosome.

For cellular IRESes, the picture is even less clear. One interesting difference between viral IRESes and cellular IRESes, is their difference in size. Whereas viral IRESes are generally between 400 and 1500 nucleotides long, cellular IRESes can be as small as 176 nucleotides (FGF2) and are rarely longer than 800 nucleotides. A second shared feature between viral IRESes and cellular IRESes is that in many cases both harbor a polypyrimidine tract, albeit slightly more often in viruses than in cells (Bushell et al., 2006). In general, cellular IRESes do not share structural motifs or sequences, not even between homologues, which makes analysis difficult. For example, the *myc* family of proto-oncogenes – consisting of c-*myc*, N-*myc*, and L-*myc* – all harbor IRESes in their 5' UTR (Jopling et al., 2004; Jopling and Willis, 2001; Stoneley et al., 1998), but their IRESes are not at all similar in structure nor in sequence. Computational predictions (mFold software) combined with experimental evidence (RNase treatment) revealed, that the L-*myc* IRES is small and relatively compact, whereas the c-*myc* IRES is much larger and more open, and is predicted to have a very different structure (West et al., 1998). The authors suggested that IRESes of cellular transcripts that also use cap-dependent translational mechanisms, like the *myc* family of genes, have a less rigid – hence more dynamic and possibly less conserved – structure to facilitate traditional canonical scanning.

A third, important difference between viral and cellular IRESes in terms of structure/function relationship, is that cellular IRESes often retain part of their function when parts of the IRES are deleted. In line with this finding, individual pieces of a cellular IRES often have a certain capacity left to promote translation initiation. Both of these observations imply that their function/structure relationship is not as rigid as in viral IRESes (Le Quesne et al., 2001).

In some assays, binding of small sequences within the cellular IRES to components of the

translational machinery have been demonstrated. For example, only 9 nucleotide long sequences within the IRESes of the cellular proteins Gtx and Rbm3 are capable of promoting internal initiation (Chappell and Mauro, 2003; Chappell et al., 2000). They also bind to the 40S ribosomal subunit in cell-free assays. It was suggested that these short sequences in the IRESes can directly bind to complementary sequences (nucleotides 1132-1124) in the 18S rRNA, which is a part of the 40S ribosomal subunit. Supporting this idea, which has not been tested yet, is that the part of the 18S rRNA responsible for the interaction, is exposed on the outside of the ribosome and therefore thought to be accessible. Remarkably, a synthetic multimer of the 9 nt sequence, cloned in the original IRES, enhanced the activity of the IRES 570-fold, but a naturally occurring identical sequence in the FGF2 IRES has no apparent effect and can be deleted without influencing IRES activity (Bonnal et al., 2003).

It has now become clear that there's no such thing as 'the' mechanism by which IRESes act as translation initiators. Supporting this idea are the great differences in three-dimensional structure, nucleotide sequence, length, requirement of ITAFs (see below), and requirement of initiation factors. Especially the latter is striking: studies with specific inhibitors and dominant negative mutants have shown, that CrPV does not need any of the members of the eIF4F complex (eIF4E, eIF4G, eIF4A) and eIF3 and eIF2, whereas HCV needs only eIF3 and eIF4, and EMCV and most cellular IRESes can only do without eIF4E (Svitkin et al., 2001; Chard et al., 2006).

IRES trans-acting factors

One of the most remarkable features of schematic drawings of IRES-mediated translation, is the high number of question marks and lack of detail in the drawing. Although many proteins were found to interact with IRESes, in many cases there's no clear functional explanation and the interaction was not experimentally

coupled to a known function *in vivo*.

IRES Trans-Acting Factors (ITAFs) are referred to as proteins specifically interacting with IRESes to stimulate or inhibit internal initiation, possibly exerting cell-type-dependent or condition-dependent specificity. ITAFs probably act as RNA chaperones, keeping the IRES in a certain conformational shape or attached to the eIF4A/eIF4G complex (figure 1D). This definition includes most initiation factors, although this is highly dependent on the conditions and the type of viral or cellular IRES, as we have seen in the previous paragraphs.

One of the first indications that also non-initiation factors might be involved in IRES-mediated translation, came from a study in which HeLa cell extracts enhanced the activity of a picornavirus IRES in a cell-free translation system (Dorner et al., 1984). This led to the conclusion, that certain cells contain essential trans-acting factors for IRES-mediated translation, although in this study no specific candidates were mentioned yet. This came in 1991, when a group discovered the interaction between polypyrimidine tract binding protein (PTB), then known as p57, with the IRES of foot-and-mouth disease virus (Luz and Beck, 1991). As mentioned before, many viral and cellular IRESes harbor polypyrimidine tracts. PTB was found to bind to two distinct sites within the IRES, which have as the only common sequence a UUUC motif. Another group, however, recently identified (CCU)_n as a PTB binding motif being present in a large subset of cellular IRESes (Spriggs et al., 2005). The PTB/IRES interaction was further characterized by different groups, leading to an intriguing picture of different dependencies. For example, the wildtype EMCV IRES was perfectly capable of functioning without PTB, but when a stretch of adenines in the 5' UTR of the transcript was made slightly longer from 6 to 7, the IRES became fully dependent on PTB (Kaminski and Jackson, 1998). Even more confusing, PTB seems to be able to either inhibit or stimulate IRES

activity of the cellular protein BiP, which was shown to bind PTB through the central region (nucleotides 50 - 117) of the BiP 5' UTR (Kim et al., 2000). Addition of purified PTB to a cell-free system and overexpression of PTB in COS7 cells inhibited BiP IRES-dependent translation, but depletion of endogenous PTB or addition of a PTB siRNA enhanced the translational initiation directed by the BiP IRES.

After the identification of PTB as an ITAF, many other ITAFs that interact with specific IRESes were found. These include hnRNPC (Sella et al., 1999), poly (rC) binding protein (PCBP1) (Evans et al., 2003), La auto-antigen (Costa-Mattioli et al., 2004), upstream of N-ras (UNR) (Tinton et al., 2005), and far upstream element binding protein 2 (FBP2) (Lin et al., 2008). A recent study on ITAFs for the myc family of IRESes revealed four new candidates: G-rich RNA sequence binding factor 1 (GRSF-1), Y-box binding protein 1 (YB-1), polypyrimidine tract binding protein-associated splicing factor (PSF), and p54nrb (Cobbold et al., 2008). All four ITAFs were shown to positively regulate the translation of c-, L-, and N-myc *in vivo* and *in vitro*. This is remarkable, since former characterization of the myc IRESes revealed hardly any structural or sequence relationship between the three (West et al., 1998). Even more remarkable, protein synthesis from the BAG-1 and Apaf-1 cellular IRESes was not affected by YB-1, GRSF-1, or PSF levels *in vivo*, suggesting that these three ITAFs are specific to the myc IRESes. Earlier, three members of the poly (rC) binding protein family, PCBP1, PCBP2 and hnRNPK, were also found to bind the c-myc IRES, adding up to a total of seven ITAFs for c-myc (Evans et al., 2003). The authors also showed, that UNR, which was previously identified as an ITAF involved in IRES-mediated translation by rhinovirus, poliovirus, and Apaf-1 (Boussadia et al., 2003; Mitchell et al., 2001), stimulated c-myc IRES activity threefold when added in combination with PCBP1, PCBP2 or hnRNPK. Interestingly, the mutated version of the c-myc IRES prevalent in

patients with multiple myeloma, bound hnRNPK more efficiently *in vitro* and was stimulated by hnRNPK to a greater extent *in vivo*.

The binding of hnRNPC to the platelet-derived growth factor 2 (PDGF2) IRES is one of the few that is linked to a biological function, although the details are still unclear. PDGF2 has an IRES that becomes more active during differentiation (Bernstein et al., 1997). In nondifferentiated cells, the entire 5' UTR is required for maximum IRES activity, but during differentiation a 630-nucleotide fragment within the central region of the 5' UTR is sufficient. Interestingly, hnRNPC was found to specifically bind to this region important for IRES-activity during differentiation (Sella et al., 1999). hnRNPC binding activity to the IRES is mostly nuclear in nondifferentiated cells, whereas in differentiated cells its binding activity is associated with the ribosomal fraction. The authors suggest that these characteristics may constitute the major difference between relatively strong IRESes, such as those seen in some viruses, and IRESes serving as translational modulators.

Another interesting approach is a genome-wide search for predicted structure similarities between the IRES of X-linked inhibitor of apoptosis protein (XIAP) as a model IRES structure, and sequences in 5' UTRs (Baird et al., 2007). Three new IRESes were found based on this approach, located in the 5' UTRs of Aquaporin 4 (AQP4), ELG1 and NF-kappaB repressing factor (NRF). The structures of the AQP4 and ELG1 IRESes have limited similarity to the XIAP IRES; however, they share trans-acting factors that bind the XIAP IRES. The authors therefore confirm the emerging idea that cellular IRESes are not defined by overall structure, as viral IRES often are, but are instead mainly dependent on trans-acting factors for their function.

The Ring1b IRES

In Chapter 5 of this thesis, we demonstrate the first Polycomb group protein that harbors an IRES in its 5' UTR, providing a new level of

post-transcriptional regulation of a PcG protein complex member. With a minimal length that still retains IRES function of only 91 bp, the IRES is unusually small. This has implications for its ability to function as an RNA chaperone, since its size puts some limits to what extent it can wrap itself around the ribosomal subunits and initiation factors, as was reported for CrPV (Spahn et al., 2004; Schuler et al., 2006). Yet, it is more active than several other cellular IRESes known to date and much more active than the EMCV IRES used in the same experimental settings. Ring1b seems to be largely dependent on the presence of the IRES for its translation, as Ring1b translation is clearly impaired when the IRES is not present in overexpression assays. Cryptic promoter activity was excluded by showing lack of expression of downstream open reading frames in promoterless constructs. Finally, we show a software-predicted secondary structure, consisting of two stem-loops followed by a large, asymmetric Y-shaped structure. Point mutations and deleting the second stem-loop resulted in a decline in activity, whereas the substitution of a nucleotide creating a complementary base pair stabilized the structure, slightly enhancing activity. The striking similarity between the predicted structures of the human and mouse Ring1b IRES underscores the importance of the IRES in Ring1b translational control.

Arguably the most striking feature of the Ring1b IRES is that it seems to be sensitive to the absence of an intact translation initiation complex, since it is much less active when the eIF4E binding domain is cleaved off of eIF4G by viral protease 2A. This observation suggests the Ring1b IRES is to some extent dependent on cap-dependent translational mechanisms. The reason for this could be indirect, in that the Ring1b IRES needs a trans-acting factor that is translated in a cap-dependent manner, but it is currently unclear which factor this could be. Another possible explanation comes from ribosome shunting, a discontinuous

scanning mechanism that in result resembles IRES activity but requires a m⁷guanosine cap. However, shunting requires shunt donor and acceptor sequences to enable scanning ribosomes to bypass mRNA sequences in the 5' UTR, none of which were found in the Ring1b 5' UTR. Finally, it could be that our tests on the Ring1b IRES sensitivity to 2Apro were biased towards a condition under which the IRES is actually sensitive to 2Apro. If indeed the IRES functions as an extra regulatory element rather than the most important way for Ring1b to be translated, it could be that the IRES' sensitivity is dependent on ITAFs not present in the experimental conditions we used. Of course this is speculation and more experiments are needed to verify this possibility.

Of note, cap-dependent IRES translation is not unprecedented. As described earlier, eIF4GI – the most abundant of the two eIF4G proteins – itself was found to harbor a cap-dependent IRES, with no clear shunt donor and acceptor sequences (Byrd et al., 2005). Whereas eIF4GI IRES activity was found to be cap-dependent, it was actually activated by 2Apro-mediated cleavage of eIF4GI protein. Taken together, this suggests that the IRESes of eIF4GI and Ring1b may represent a special subclass of IRES sequences which in part require cap-translation initiation factors for optimal translation.

For many cellular proteins with an IRES a functional link between the IRES's activity and the function of the protein were found. In case of Ring1b, this is somewhat more difficult, since no clear function of Ring1b has been established, apart from its E3 ubiquitin ligase activity. We speculate that the reason why Ring1b mRNA harbors an IRES, is because Ring1b protein needs to be present in a cell under all circumstances, and the IRES provides a backup system under circumstances where cap-dependent translation is impaired. After testing many primary cell types, tumor cell lines and live tissue, we found no cell type with low levels or lack of Ring1b protein. All cells and tissues

tested have readily detectable levels of Ring1b protein. Also, our previous work indicated that Ring1b knockout mice die early in gestation, with severe defects in the mesoderm and deregulated hox gene expression (Voncken et al., 2003), suggesting a vital function for Ring1b already in early embryo development. The presence of an IRES might ensure translation of Ring1b in the early embryo under stress conditions such as low oxygen or limited amino acid availability.

Another possible explanation for the need for Ring1b protein to be present at all times comes from differentiation studies with mouse embryonic stem (ES) cells. Recent genome-wide studies show that PcG proteins are critically involved in keeping differentiation-related genes silent in ES cells (Endoh et al., 2008; Boyer et al., 2006; Lee et al., 2006). Since Ring1b seems to play an essential role in PRC1 and early embryo survival, lack of Ring1b might compromise PRC1 function, leading to unregulated differentiation of stem cells, possibly resulting in cell death. This stem cell based explanation is further supported by the many reports that implicate Bmi1, a Ring1b interaction partner and regulator of Ring1b's ubiquitin E3 ligase activity, in stem cell self-renewal (Iwama et al., 2004; Lessard and Sauvageau, 2003; Leung et al., 2004; Molofsky et al., 2003).

The apparent permanent need for Ring1b could be related to its known enzymatic function at the heart of PRC1, acting as a E3 ubiquitin ligase for monoubiquitination of histone H2A. We and others have shown by protein crystallography, that Ring1b and Bmi1 strongly interact via their RING finger domains as well as via the Ring1b N-terminal tail, which wraps around Bmi1 (Buchwald et al., 2006; Li et al., 2006). Together these proteins form an active E3 ligase heterodimer, capable of monoubiquitinating H2A more efficiently than Ring1b alone. Truncated versions of both proteins, including the RING finger domains

and small adjacent sequences, were shown to be sufficient for heterodimerization, catalytic activity and substrate recognition (Buchwald et al., 2006), which leaves more than half of each protein for interaction with other proteins. Since PcG proteins act in large multimeric complexes, it is likely PcG members other than Bmi1 also provide a layer of regulation of Ring1b's E3 ligase activity. This is supported by the finding that an *in vitro* translated PRC1 core complex containing Ring1A, Ring1b, Bmi1 and Pc3 leads to higher levels of uH2A than Ring1b alone (Cao et al., 2005), suggesting a synergistic effect of PRC1 on H2A monoubiquitination. Importantly, only lack of Ring1b abolishes H2A monoubiquitination (Wang et al., 2004), indicating PRC1 without Ring1b cannot monoubiquitinate H2A. Indeed, loss of Ring1b results in rapid deubiquitination of H2A and apoptosis (Endoh et al., 2008b, Van der Stoop and Boutsma, unpublished observations). There has been a long-standing correlation between decreased levels of uH2A and apoptosis (Mimnaugh et al., 2001; Marushige and Marushige, 1995), which might point to the idea that a minimal level of uH2A is necessary for cell survival. This again supports the idea that Ring1b protein needs to be present under all circumstances, a requirement that could possibly be met by the presence of the newly found IRES.

The Ring1b IRES in the 5' UTR might also confer increased stability of the mRNA, providing a pool of Ring1b transcripts on standby. Increased stability is a common phenomenon to highly structured RNA, both with specific sequences in the 5' untranslated region as well as in the 3' untranslated region (Suay et al., 2005). Indeed, the Ring1b 3' UTR can be very large – fragments of up to 3.5 kb were found in the online databases – and specific stretches of up to 1 kb are remarkably conserved between mouse and human, just as its 5' UTR. Increasing Ring1b mRNA stability in this way could point to a mechanism through which the presence

of Ring1b protein is secured by very different means than by maintaining translation, namely by providing a pool of Ring1b mRNA when general transcription is halted.

Taken together, it is very likely that Ring1b protein needs to be present under virtually all circumstances. This idea is now strongly supported by the fact that Ring1b can be translated via its IRES under conditions when traditional cap-dependent translation is

impaired, but also by the possibility that the presence of highly structured UTRs in the Ring1b mRNA contribute to its stability and therefore provide a stock of Ring1b mRNA when transcription is impaired. Further experiments on the exact events following the disappearance of Ring1b protein from a cell, preferably via a controlled experimental setup using conditional genetic inactivation, should give more insights into the role of Ring1b in the cell.

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Chapter 3

Stable maintenance of mouse embryonic stem cells requires Ring1b

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Everyone should raise their head every once in a while and take a look around, to see what's going on. It's called *life*, and you can miss it if you don't open your eyes.

Benjamin Sisko, Star Trek Deep Space Nine episode 'The Visitor'

Ubiquitin E3 Ligase Ring1b/Rnf2 of Polycomb Repressive Complex 1 Contributes to Stable Maintenance of Mouse Embryonic Stem Cells

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Polycomb repressive complex 1 (PRC1) core member Ring1b/Rnf2, with ubiquitin E3 ligase activity towards histone H2A at lysine 119, is essential for early embryogenesis. To obtain more insight into the role of Ring1b in early development, we studied its function in mouse embryonic stem (ES) cells. We investigated the effects of Ring1b ablation on transcriptional regulation using *Ring1b* conditional knockout ES cells and large-scale gene expression analysis. The absence of Ring1b results in aberrant expression of key developmental genes and deregulation of specific differentiation-related pathways, including TGF β signaling, cell cycle regulation and cellular communication. Moreover, ES cell markers, including *Zfp42/Rex-1* and *Sox2*, are downregulated. Importantly, retained expression of ES cell regulators *Oct4*, *Nanog* and alkaline phosphatase indicates that Ring1b-deficient ES cells retain important ES cell specific characteristics. Comparative analysis of our expression profiling data with previously published global binding studies shows that the genes that are bound by Ring1b in ES cells have bivalent histone marks, i.e. both active H3K4me3 and repressive H3K27me3, or the active H3K4me3 histone mark alone and are associated with GC-rich promoters. However, deletion of *Ring1b* results in deregulation, mainly derepression, of only a subset of these genes, suggesting that additional silencing mechanisms are involved in repression of other Ring1b bound genes in ES cells. Therefore we conclude, that Ring1b is essential to stably maintain an undifferentiated state of mouse ES cells by repressing genes with important roles during differentiation and development. These genes are characterized by promoters with high GC content and bivalent histone marks or the active H3K4me3 histone mark alone.

Introduction

PcG proteins have initially been identified in *Drosophila* as transcriptional repressors required for correct expression of *homeotic (Hox)* genes. By means of chromatin remodeling, PcG proteins

maintain stable gene repression to ensure proper embryonic development. In mammals, two biochemically and functionally distinct PcG core complexes have been identified (reviewed in Lund and van Lohuizen, 2004). Mammalian Polycomb repressive complex 1 (PRC1) consists

of close homologues of the *Drosophila* PRC1 core members Ph, Pc, Psc and dRing (Lund and van Lohuizen, 2004; Ringrose and Paro, 2004). Ring1b/Rnf2, the mouse homolog of dRing, acts as a ubiquitin E3 ligase towards histone H2A at lysine 119 resulting in mono-ubiquitinated H2A (uH2A) (Wang et al., 2004; Buchwald et al., 2006). EZH2/Kmt6, a methyltransferase that trimethylates histone H3 at lysine 27 (H3K27me3), acts in complex with Suz12 and Eed, constituting Polycomb repressive complex 2 (PRC2) (Cao et al., 2002; Kuzmichev et al., 2002; Kirmizis et al., 2004). Recently, it was reported that close homolog EZH1 exhibits a contrasting repressive role (Margueron et al., 2008), since EZH1 was capable of compacting chromatin in the absence of methyltransferase cofactor SAM. Another group found EZH1 to be able to act as a methyltransferase *in vitro* and *in vivo* as well, a role previously only attributed to EZH2 (Shen et al., 2008). In addition, depletion of EZH1 in *EZH2* null cells abolishes residual methylation on H3K27 and derepresses H3K27me3 target genes.

PRC1 and PRC2 do not physically interact, but the EZH2 catalyzed histone mark H3K27me3 is recognized by PRC1 member Pc, providing a mechanism of communication between the two complexes (Fischle et al., 2003). Furthermore, PRC1 binding to chromatin requires PRC2, although PRC2-independent recruitment of PRC1 is also reported (Hernandez-Munoz et al., 2005; Schoeftner et al., 2006). Recently, a report indicated that there might be two classes of bivalent chromatin domains (i.e. with both repressive H3K27me3 and active H3K4me3 marks) in ES cells: those with both PRC1 and PRC2, and those with only PRC2 (Ku et al., 2008). Bivalent domains with both repressive complexes appeared to be functionally distinct as they were found to more efficiently retain H3K27me3 upon differentiation and show stronger conservation of chromatin state.

Proper expression of PRC2 proteins is essential during early embryonic development, since

mice lacking one of these proteins die due to gastrulation defects (Faust et al., 1995; Pasini et al., 2004; O'Carroll et al., 2001). In contrast, PRC1 members appear to be more important during later stages of development, with the clear exception of Ring1b, which evokes an early embryonic lethal phenotype similar to PRC2 null mice (van der Lugt et al., 1994; Takihara et al., 1997; Akasaka et al., 1996; Voncken et al., 2003; del Mar et al., 2000). PcG proteins were shown to be important for self-renewal and maintaining pluripotency of ES cells (Valk-Lingbeek et al., 2004; Pasini et al., 2007; Boyer et al., 2006). ES cells are derived from the inner cell mass of pre-implantation blastocysts (Evans and Kaufman, 1981). ES can self-renew and maintain a pluripotent, undifferentiated state under the right conditions *in vitro*, while retaining the capacity to differentiate into every cell type required during development *in vitro* and *in vivo* when reintroduced back into a host blastocyst (Beddington and Robertson, 1989). Genome-wide and candidate-based studies revealed that PcG proteins maintain this undifferentiated state of ES cells through direct repression of developmental genes (Tolhuis et al., 2006; Boyer et al., 2006; Lee et al., 2006; Bracken et al., 2006; Squazzo et al., 2006). Developmental genes are largely associated with bivalent histone marks and are silent or expressed at very low levels in ES cells (Azuara et al., 2006; Bernstein et al., 2006; Mikkelsen et al., 2007). Bivalent domains tend to resolve during development (Bernstein et al., 2006; Azuara et al., 2006; Mikkelsen et al., 2007). Therefore, it is suggested that this bivalent chromatin state poises genes for transcriptional activation (loss of H3K27me3) or prolonged repression (loss of H3K4me3 or both marks) during later developmental stages. Only recently it was shown that Ring1b-mediated uH2A deposition at repressed bivalent genes restrains a poised RNA polymerase II (RNAPII) configuration (Stock et al., 2007). Conditional deletion of Ring1b and subsequent loss of uH2A from the

promoter and coding region results in release of poised RNAPII and gene derepression. More evidence for a direct role of uH2A in negative transcriptional regulation was found by another group, which investigated the role of histone H2A E3 ligase 2A-HUB in repressing chemokine genes in human monocytes (Zhou et al., 2008). They show that the presence of uH2A in the promoter-proximal region physically blocks recruitment of FACT, thereby causing RNAPII-dependent transcription elongation to pause. Intriguingly, recent findings in *Drosophila melanogaster* showed that H2A monoubiquitination by Ring1b homolog dRING requires dKDM2, a demethylase that normally mediates H3K36me2 demethylation (Lagarou et al., 2008). The authors also found a new Polycomb repressive complex (dRING associated factors, dRAF), that harbors dRING, PSC (the *Drosophila* homolog of mammalian Bmi1 and Me18) and dKDM2. They state that dRAF thus removes an active mark from histone H3 and adds a repressive one to H2A, leading to stronger repression of target genes.

To explore the role of Ring1b in regulation of gene expression during early development, we analyzed genome-wide changes in gene transcription following deletion of Ring1b in ES cells. Hereto, we employed an inducible knockout system and performed a genome-wide screen using microarrays to identify genes governed by Ring1b. We identify several processes and pathways differentially regulated in *Ring1b*-deficient ES cells, which are implicated in differentiation and embryogenesis. Importantly, we find that *Ring1b*-deficient ES cells retain expression of key stem cell regulators Oct4 and Nanog. Finally, by comparing our expression data with previously published global binding studies, we find that Ring1b preferentially represses genes with high-GC content promoters and bivalent or H3K4me3 histone marks. This suggests that Ring1b has an important role in maintaining an undifferentiated state of ES cells. Furthermore,

this study provides more insight in the characteristics of the genes that are under direct transcriptional control of Ring1b in ES cells.

Results

Generating Ring1b conditional knockout mouse embryonic stem cells

To gain insight in the role of Ring1b in ES cells, we generated *Ring1b* conditional knockout mouse ES cells. Previously, we have shown that deletion of the RING finger domain of Ring1b, encoded by exon 3 and 4, generates a functional null allele (Voncken et al., 2003). *Ring1b* conditional knockout (*Ring1b*^{-/lox}) ES cells were then generated by a second targeting round in *Ring1b*^{+/-} ES cells (Voncken et al., 2003) using a targeting vector, which introduced loxP sequences flanking these exons (Figure 1A; details in Materials and Methods). To generate inducible *Ring1b*^{-/lox} ES cells, we targeted a 4-hydroxytamoxifen (4-OHT) inducible R26CreER^{T2} construct (Cre-recombinase fused to a mutated ligand binding domain of the human estrogen receptor) to the ROSA26 locus of *Ring1b*^{-/lox} ES cells, hereafter named *Ring1b*^{-/lox};CreER^{T2} ES cells. The presence of loxP sequences in the genomic locus of Ring1b did not alter the expression of Ring1b in ES cells. Accordingly, *Ring1b*^{-/lox} and *Ring1b*^{-/lox};CreER^{T2} mice developed indistinguishable from wild type mice (E.B, M.v.L, unpublished results).

Addition of 4-OHT to the culture medium resulted in recombination of the *Ring1b* conditional allele in *Ring1b*^{-/lox};CreER^{T2} ES cells and subsequent depletion of Ring1b protein as was shown by Southern and Western blot analysis (Figure 1B, 1C). We observed cellular detachment and apoptosis concurrent with an increase in cells with a differentiated phenotype after deleting Ring1b in *Ring1b*^{-/lox};CreER^{T2} ES cells, but not in similarly treated *Ring1b*^{+/-};CreER^{T2} control ES cells. Based on Annexin V staining followed by flow cytometric analysis, about 83% of all *Ring1b*^{-/lox};CreER^{T2} ES cells were undergoing

Figure 1. Generating *Ring1b* conditional knockout ES cells

(A) Schematic overview of the *Ring1b* locus targeting strategy in mouse *Ring1b*^{+/−} ES cells. The wild type *Ring1b* allele is shown with main restrictions sites, introns and exons, in the targeted genomic region. The *Ring1b*^{loxHyg} allele was generated by targeting a floxed exon3+4/Hygromycin replacement vector to the wild type *Ring1b* locus of the *Ring1b*^{+/−} ES cells. The hygromycin cassette allowed for selection after the initial targeting and was removed by transiently expressing adenoviral Cre to generate the conditional *Ring1b*^{lox} allele. Acute loss of Ring1b from *Ring1b*^{lox} ES cells was induced by adding 4-OHT to the medium to activate CreER^{T2} (Cre-recombinase fused to a mutated ligand binding domain of the human estrogen receptor (ER), targeted to the ROSA locus, not shown) resulting in deletion of exons 3 and 4, represented as the *Ring1b*^{Del} allele. Exons are indicated by white boxes with the corresponding exon number, loxP sequences by black triangles, and HYG indicates the hygromycin cassette. Main restriction sites are indicated (H=HindIII, E=EcoRI, X=XhoI) as well as the location of the 5'end probe used for Southern blot analysis.

(B) Southern blot analysis of HindIII digested genomic DNA of *Ring1b*^{lox/lox};CreER^{T2} ES cells showing recombination of the *Ring1b*^{lox} allele following treatment with 4-OHT for the indicated time in days. The 5'end probe visualizes the conventional knockout allele (5 kb), the conditional lox allele (7 kb) and the recombined *Del* allele (4 kb). (C) Western blot analysis showing loss of Ring1b protein and uH2A in *Ring1b*^{lox/lox};CreER^{T2} ES cells following treatment with 4-OHT for the indicated time in days. Tubulin serves as a loading control.

apoptosis four days following 4-OHT treatment (data not shown). Of the adherent population only 15% was Annexin V positive, compared to 5% of the untreated population (data not shown). We therefore focused our studies on the immediate early effects of the first days

following Cre-mediated deletion of *Ring1b* in the viable, adherent ES cells.

Ring1b is required for monoubiquitination of H2A in ES cells

Since Ring1b is a ubiquitin E3 ligase for histone

Figure 2. Deletion of Ring1b results in loss of uH2A but not H3K27me3

Examples of immunofluorescence stainings in *Ring1b*^{-lox};*CreER*^{T2} ES cells showing loss of uH2A (A), but not H3K27me3 (B) in cells that have lost Ring1b four days following 4-OHT treatment.

H2A at lysine 119, we studied the effect of Ring1b deletion on the levels of uH2A. Western blot analysis showed that uH2A levels decreased to almost undetectable levels after deletion of Ring1b from *Ring1b*^{-lox};*CreER*^{T2} ES cells (Figure 1C). In addition, immunofluorescence stainings confirmed that uH2A was lost in ES cells that had lost Ring1b expression (Figure 2A). The same held true for mouse embryonic fibroblasts (MEFs) derived from *Ring1b*^{-lox};*CreER*^{T2} mouse embryos, which showed no uH2A immunofluorescence staining in *Ring1b*-negative cells (Supplementary Figure S1). Immunofluorescence stainings for H3K27me3,

Figure S1. Loss of uH2A after deletion of Ring1b in MEFs

Example of immunofluorescence stainings of *Ring1b*^{-lox};*CreER*^{T2} MEFs, 6 days following 4-OHT treatment showing loss of uH2A in MEFs that have lost Ring1b.

the Polycomb repressive mark set by PRC2 member EZH2, showed that this mark was present in all cells (Figure 2B). These results confirm that Ring1b is the main E3 ligase for monoubiquitination of H2A in both mouse ES cells and MEFs and suggest that deletion of Ring1b does not affect H3K27 trimethylation.

Ring1b deficiency affects expression of other PRC1 core members

Studies in *Drosophila*, mouse and human cells have shown that PcG genes themselves are PcG protein binding targets, suggesting auto-regulation within the PcG family (DeCamillis et al., 1992; Lee et al., 2006; Boyer et al., 2006). We therefore examined the effect of Ring1b deletion on other PRC1 and PRC2 members in ES cells. Microarray analysis (described in

Figure 3. Downregulation of protein levels of PRC1, but not PRC2, following Ring1b deletion in ES cells

Western blot analysis of total cell protein extracts (A) or nuclear extracts (B) of *Ring1b*^{-lox};*CreER*^{T2} ES cells shows that deletion of Ring1b results in downregulation of Phc1/Mph1 and Bmi1 protein levels, but not of EZH2, Eed or H3K27me3 levels following treatment with 4-OHT for the indicated number of days.

more detail in the following section) showed that the transcript levels of *Ring1b* and *Phc1/Mph1* were significantly downregulated over time, with a corresponding decrease in protein levels (Figure 3A). Interestingly, PRC1 member Bmi1 was derepressed transcriptionally in the absence of Ring1b, but its protein levels were downregulated, suggesting that Bmi1 is post-transcriptionally regulated by Ring1b (Figure 3B). This is consistent with observations by others (Leeb and Wutz, 2007), and may be

explained by the fact that interaction between Bmi1 and Ring1b protects both proteins from ubiquitin-mediated degradation (Ben Saadon et al., 2006). The effect of loss of Ring1b on other PRC1 core members may explain the severity of the *Ring1b* knockout phenotype compared to knockout models of other PRC1 members (van der Lugt et al., 1994; Takihara et al., 1997; Akasaka et al., 1996; Voncken et al., 2003; del Mar et al., 2000). Other Polycomb group genes of which the transcription had increased significantly were *Epc1*, *Phf1*, and *Phc2* (data not shown). No effects were observed on the protein or transcript levels of PRC2 members *EZH2* and *Eed*, or the levels of H3K27me3, which is in agreement with the immunofluorescence analysis (Figure 3A, 3B). The effect on PcG protein and transcript levels after loss of Ring1b is in agreement with an earlier study performed in established *Ring1b*-deficient ES cells, with the exception of the transcriptional downregulation of *Phc1* (Leeb and Wutz, 2007). This might therefore reflect an indirect effect of acute loss of Ring1b in ES cells. These results suggest that deletion of *Ring1b* affects the transcript and protein levels of members of PRC1, but not of PRC2, and underscores the importance of Ring1b for PRC1 stability.

Regulation of developmental processes through derepression of Ring1b bound genes

To obtain insight in the genome-wide effects on gene transcription after deletion of *Ring1b* in ES cells, we performed microarray analysis. We analyzed the temporal changes in gene transcription in *Ring1b*^{-lox};*CreER*^{T2} ES cells one to four days after deletion of Ring1b. As a reference, we used *Ring1b*^{+/+};*CreER*^{T2} ES cells similarly treated with 4-OHT to correct for any effects induced by 4-OHT or *CreER*^{T2}. We identified 2365 differentially regulated genes, i.e. genes that were significantly ($p < 0.05$ according to the Rosetta-error model, for details see Materials and Methods) up- or

Figure 4. Gene expression profiling in Ring1b-deficient ES cells

(A) Expression profiling data clustered by the software program Genesis shows regulation of gene expression ($p < 0.05$) after deletion of Ring1b in mouse ES cells over time.

(B) Heatmap of the statistically overrepresented GO categories, as identified by BiNGO analysis. The color scale bar represents the relation between the color intensity and the level of significance ($-\log_{10}(p\text{-value})$).

(C) Graph representing the number of all upregulated (red) and downregulated (green) genes ($p < 0.05$).

(D) Graph representing the number of up- (red) or downregulated (green) Ring1b bound genes specifically (Boyer et al., 2006).

(E) qPCR validation of microarray data for a selection of genes. Time indicates number of days of 4-OHT treatment.

F

	% Up	# R1b bound	% Down	# R1b bound
gluconeogenesis	40 (2/5)	1	60 (3/5)	0
cell cycle	62 (24/39)	4	38 (15/39)	0
organ development	63 (36/57)	14	37 (21/57)	1
nucleosome assembly	93 (13/14)	8	7 (1/14)	0
organ morphogenesis	80 (37/46)	16	20 (9/46)	0
reg of cellular phys	100 (109/109)	32	0 (0/109)	0

Figure 4 (continued)

(F) Table showing the significantly enriched GO categories and the percentage (numbers between brackets) of up- or downregulated genes and the number of Ring1b bound genes per GO category (the ones most-downstream in the GO-tree).

downregulated (7%; 2365/31769; Figure 4A, 4C). The reliability of the microarray data was confirmed by quantitative real-time PCR analysis (qPCR) on a selection of 18 genes (Figure 4E).

To gain insight into the processes that are deregulated in absence of Ring1b in mouse ES cells, we analyzed the deregulated genes based on their ontology classification. To this end, we employed the gene ontology (GO) tool BINGO to determine which GO categories are statistically overrepresented. By mapping the predominant functional GO categories in a hierarchical graph BiNGO facilitates insight in the hierarchical structure and relations between the ontologies (Maere et al., 2005). We found that the outliers were involved in various processes, of which the most downstream in the GO-tree were: 'organ development', 'organ morphogenesis', 'nucleosome assembly', 'regulation of cellular physiological processes', 'glyconeogenesis', and 'cell cycle' (Figure 4B). These data confirm that Ring1b is involved in regulating cell cycle, developmental and chromatin-related processes and indicate that deletion of *Ring1b* affects glyconeogenesis and the regulation of cellular physiological processes. Given that loss of Ring1b affects the undifferentiated state of ES cells, the regulated processes are likely to include genes that are deregulated due to indirect effects.

By using a genome-wide ChIP-on-chip analysis Boyer and colleagues identified genes that are

bound by Ring1b in mouse ES cells (Boyer et al., 2006). By combining our microarray expression data with the data from this Ring1b binding study, we were able to determine which genes were direct transcriptional targets of Ring1b. Of the 1219 Ring1b bound genes, identified by Boyer and colleagues, 1078 were represented on our microarray. Remarkably, we found that only a subset of 141 Ring1b bound genes had significantly changed expression (13% (141/1078)). These genes were predominantly upregulated, which is in agreement with Ring1b being a transcriptional repressor (Figure 4B, 4C). The partial derepression implies that other regulatory mechanisms are active at the other Ring1b target genes in addition to Ring1b, and reflects that a subset of genes is deregulated due to indirect effects of loss of *Ring1b* in ES cells. Next, we assessed which of the deregulated genes within an overrepresented GO category (most down-stream in the GO-tree) were bound by Ring1b. We found that on average 30% of the deregulated genes within an enriched ontology was bound by Ring1b, in particular in the ontologies organ development and morphogenesis, nucleosome assembly, and regulation of cellular physiological process (Figure 4F). This was substantially higher than what would be expected considering that only 6% (141/2365) of all deregulated genes was bound by Ring1b. This indicates that Ring1b is involved in direct transcriptional regulation of a substantial large fraction of the deregulated genes in these ontologies. Together, these data suggest that Ring1b is specifically important for dynamic repression of developmental, chromatin-related, cell cycle and metabolic genes in ES cells.

Regulation of specific differentiation-related pathways in Ring1b-deficient ES cells

The analysis based on the ontology classification shows that absence of Ring1b results in aberrant expression of genes involved in developmental and various cellular processes.

Symbol	EntrezID	Regulation	bound	Symbol	EntrezID	Regulation	bound
Focal Adhesion				TGFbeta signaling			
<i>Actg2</i>	11464	up	no	<i>Amhr2</i>	110542	down	ND
<i>Actn3</i>	11474	down	no	<i>Bmp7</i>	12162	up	yes
<i>Capn2</i>	12334	up	no	<i>Bmpr1a</i>	12166	up	no
<i>Capn5</i>	12337	down	no	<i>Cul1</i>	26965	up	no
<i>Ccnd1</i>	12443	up	no	<i>Id1</i>	15901	up	no
<i>Ccnd2</i>	12444	up	yes	<i>Id2</i>	15902	up	no
<i>Col4a2</i>	12827	up	yes	<i>Id3</i>	15903	up	yes
<i>Grb2</i>	14784	down	no	<i>Lefty1</i>	13590	up	no
<i>Ilk</i>	16202	up	no	<i>Mapk3</i>	26417	down	ND
<i>Nras</i>	18176	down	no	<i>Nodal</i>	18119	up	no
<i>Pdgfc</i>	54635	up	ND	<i>Pitx2</i>	18741	up	no
<i>Pten</i>	19211	up	no	<i>Thbs1</i>	21825	up	no
<i>Rras2</i>	20130	down	no	Cell cycle			
<i>Shc2</i>	216148	down	ND	<i>Anapc10</i>	68999	up	no
<i>Thbs1</i>	21825	up	no	<i>Ccnd2</i>	12444	up	yes
<i>Vegfa</i>	22339	down	no	<i>Cdc20</i>	107995	up	no
<i>Zyx</i>	22793	up	no	<i>Cdc27</i>	217232	up	no
Gap junction				<i>Cdc7</i>	12545	down	no
<i>Itpr1</i>	16438	down	no	<i>Cdkn1c</i>	12577	up	yes
<i>Adcy2</i>	210044	up	yes	<i>Chek1</i>	12649	down	no
<i>Csnk1d</i>	104318	up	no	<i>Cul1</i>	26965	up	no
<i>Edg2</i>	14745	down	no	<i>Gadd45a</i>	13197	down	no
<i>Gja1</i>	14609	up	yes	<i>Gadd45g</i>	23882	up	yes
<i>Grb2</i>	14784	down	no	<i>Mcm6</i>	17219	down	no
<i>Nras</i>	18176	down	no	<i>Sfn</i>	55948	up	ND
<i>Pdgfc</i>	54635	up	ND	<i>Smc1l2</i>	140557	down	no
<i>Rras2</i>	20130	down	no	Adherens junctions			
<i>Actn3</i>	11474	down	no	<i>Actn3</i>	11474	down	no
<i>Baiap2</i>	108100	up	no	<i>Baiap2</i>	108100	up	no
<i>Iqgap1</i>	29875	up	no	<i>Iqgap1</i>	29875	up	no
<i>Lmo7</i>	380928	down	ND	<i>Lmo7</i>	380928	down	ND
<i>Mapk3</i>	26417	down	ND	<i>Mapk3</i>	26417	down	ND
<i>Pvrl4</i>	71740	down	no	<i>Pvrl4</i>	71740	down	no
<i>Vcl</i>	22330	down	no	<i>Vcl</i>	22330	down	no

Table 1. A selection of the deregulated genes and corresponding pathways affected in *Ring1b*-deficient ES cells

DAVID Pathway analysis showed deregulated genes in *Ring1b*-deficient ES cells. Shown are the deregulated genes per pathway, their EntrezIDs, the deregulated expression state, and binding of Ring1b to the promoter.

We set out to identify specific pathways that are affected in *Ring1b*-deficient ES cells. To remain unbiased in the analysis of our set of outliers, we used the bioinformatics tool DAVID, which uses information of well-defined pathways available in the KEGG pathway database (<http://david.abcc.ncifcrf.gov>). Interestingly, we found that the identified pathways have roles in development and differentiation of ES cells. A selection is listed in Table 1 on the next page. Most revealing was the identification of the TGF β signaling pathway of which Bmp/Id signaling (derepressed Bmp7, Bmpr1a, Id1, Id2, and Id3) and Nodal/Pitx2 signaling (derepressed Nodal, Pitx2) were suggested to be transcriptionally upregulated upon loss of *Ring1b*. Genome-wide binding studies have identified that PcG proteins are associated with members of the TGF β signaling pathway and show PcG dissociation from the genes that were derepressed following differentiation (Boyer et al., 2006; Lee et al., 2006). These data support a role for Ring1b/PcG in direct repression of TGF β signaling in ES cells.

In agreement with the GO classification analysis, we found altered expression of several components of the cell cycle pathway. Changes in cell cycle regulation have been observed following differentiation of ES cells, characterized by amongst others activation of the pRb-E2f controlled G1 checkpoint, which is inoperative in ES cells (Burdon et al., 2002; White et al., 2005). In line with this, key cell cycle regulators involved in activation of the G1/S checkpoint (derepressed *Cdkn1c*; downregulated *E2f1*, *Cdc7* and *Mcm6*) were transcriptionally deregulated. However, deregulation of other key cell cycle genes suggest promotion of S phase (derepressed *Ccnd2/Cyclin D2* and *Cul1*), G2/M arrest (derepressed *Gadd45g* and *Sfn/14-3-3-sigma*) or bypass of G2/M arrest (downregulated *Gadd45a*) and mitotic exit (derepressed *Cdc20* and *Cdc27*). This could imply that Ring1b has a dual role in cell cycle regulation in ES cells,

which is supported by the observation that Ring1b is involved in direct repression of cell cycle promoting gene *Ccnd2* and cell cycle inhibitory genes *Cdkn1c* and *Gadd45g*.

Various components of cellular communication pathways were deregulated in the absence of Ring1b. These comprise ECM genes (derepressed *Col4a2* and *Thbs1*) involved in focal adhesion, gap junction genes (derepressed *Gja1* and *Csnk1d* and downregulated *Itp1*), and adherent junction pathways, which are linked to the actin cytoskeleton organization (downregulated *Vcl* and *Actn3*, derepressed *Iqgap1*). Several of these genes were reported to change expression during differentiation and development (Schenke-Layland et al., 2007; Yamauchi et al., 2007; Wong et al., 2004).

Summarizing, this suggests that Ring1b deficiency induces changes in cellular pathways, such as Bmp/TGF β signaling, cell cycle regulation, and cellular communication, which strongly suggests a link to differentiation programs in ES cells.

Retained expression of stem cell regulators in Ring1b-deficient ES cells

ES cells, derived from the epiblast of early blastocysts, can self-renew and maintain a pluripotent, undifferentiated state *in vitro* by extrinsic factors, such as LIF and Bmp, and intrinsic factors, including stem cell regulators Oct4 and Nanog (Ying et al., 2003; Boyer et al., 2005; Chambers et al., 2003; Niwa et al., 2000). Upon induction of lineage-specific genes, these stem cell regulators are downregulated through a negative-feedback-loop by not yet understood mechanisms (Niwa et al., 2000; Fujikura et al., 2002; Ying et al., 2003). In line with this, the transcript levels of stem cell specific genes *Sox2*, *Dppa3/Stella* and *Zfp42/Rex-1* were strongly downregulated in Ring1b-deficient ES cells (Boyer et al., 2005; Nakamura et al., 2007). However, qPCR analysis showed that *Nanog* transcript levels had not altered and *Oct4* transcript levels had reduced only to

Figure 5. Ring1b-deficient ES cells retain expression of stem cell specific regulators

Examples of immunofluorescence stainings in *Ring1b*^{-lox}; *CreER*^{T2} ES cells of (A) Oct4 (red) and DAPI (blue), and (D) Nestin (green) and DAPI (blue), either untreated (upper panels) or treated for four days with 4-OHT (middle panels) or three days with RA (lower panels). Histograms represent the distribution of the mean immunofluorescence levels per cell retrieved after quantification of immunofluorescence stainings of Oct4 (B) or Ring1b (C) in *Ring1b*^{-lox}; *CreER*^{T2} ES cells either untreated, or treated for four days with 4-OHT or three days with RA.

(E) Graph representing the number of *Ring1b*^{-lox}; *CreER*^{T2} ES cells either untreated, or treated for four days with 4-OHT or three days with RA that show ubiquitous (black bars) or filamentous (grey bars) Nestin staining.

(F) Alkaline phosphatase activity stainings in *Ring1b*^{-lox}; *CreER*^{T2} ES cells either untreated, or treated for four days with 4-OHT or three days with RA.

about 55% (Figure 4E). Importantly, *Oct4* was not identified as an outlier on the microarray and Western blot analysis showed no significant changes in Oct4 protein levels (Figure 3A). To

examine Oct4 expression in more detail, we also quantified the immunofluorescence levels of Oct4 and Ring1b stainings in individual cells. We compared this to guided neural

differentiation induced by retinoic acid (RA) treatment, which was demonstrated to result in significant downregulation of Oct4 (Minucci et al., 1996). As expected, we found that three days after RA induced neural differentiation Oct4 was completely downregulated, in about 65% of the cells (Figure 5A, 5B). However, whereas four days following *Ring1b* deletion, 81% of all cells were negative for Ring1b, only 5% had lost Oct4 expression (Figure 5A, 5B, 5C). To assess the extent of neural differentiation, we next examined the expression of neuronal-lineage marker Nestin (Cattaneo and McKay, 1990). We found that three days after RA treatment approximately 44% of the cells showed filamentous Nestin staining, compared to 32% of the cells after deletion of *Ring1b* (Figure 5D, 5E). This is remarkable considering the number of cells expressing Oct4. This suggests that expression of lineage markers co-exists with stem cell regulators in absence of Ring1b in ES cells. Finally, we examined the activity of alkaline phosphatase, which is highly expressed in undifferentiated, pluripotent ES cells (Pease et al., 1990). We found that after deleting *Ring1b* a substantial number of cells still showed high activity of alkaline phosphatase compared to RA treated ES cells, which is indicative for a pluripotent, undifferentiated state of ES cells (Figure 5F). Combined, our findings suggest that *Ring1b*-deficient ES cells show features of differentiated cells, while retaining important ES cell characteristics.

Ring1b represses genes that are co-occupied by stem cell regulators Oct4 and Nanog in ES cells
The stem cell-specific transcription factors Oct4 and Nanog control ES cell pluripotency by regulating expression of stem cell specific genes and repression of differentiation-specific genes, of which a subset is co-occupied by PcG proteins (Boyer et al., 2005; Lee et al., 2006; Loh et al., 2006). Considering the retained expression of Oct4 and Nanog, we were interested to see the effect on gene transcription of these

co-occupied genes in absence of Ring1b. We therefore analyzed the changes in expression of genes that were bound by Ring1b (Boyer et al., 2006) and by Oct4 and/or Nanog in mouse ES cells as was identified by Loh and co-workers (Loh et al., 2006). We found that the expression of 25 of the 212 Nanog/Oct4/Ring1b bound genes represented on our microarray was altered in Ring1b-deficient ES cells (Figure 4E). We found that 18 of these 25 genes were derepressed, including *Fgf15*, *Bmp7*, *Gata3*, *Bmi1*, *Msx2*, *Podxl*, *Col4a2*, *Gadd45g*, *Gja1* and *Eif4g3*. This suggests that Ring1b is required to repress a specific subset of Oct4 and Nanog bound genes to maintain a pluripotent, undifferentiated ES cell state.

Ring1b represses bivalent or H3K4me3 marked genes with GC-rich promoters

Ring1b-mediated H2A monoubiquitination was shown to restrain a poised RNAPII configuration specifically at the promoters of bivalent genes, which were derepressed upon loss of *Ring1b* and uH2A (Stock et al., 2007). Therefore, we investigated the chromatin state of the genes that were deregulated in absence of Ring1b in ES cells. Hereto, we used a data set from Mikkelsen and colleagues, who generated genome-wide chromatin-state maps for mouse ES cells, neural progenitor cells (NPC) and MEFs (Mikkelsen et al., 2007). Of 948 of the 1078 Ring1b bound genes (Boyer et al., 2006) represented on our microarray chromatin-state maps were retrieved for the histone modifications H3K4me3 and H3K27me3 (Mikkelsen et al., 2007). Notably, virtually all (99%) of the Ring1b bound genes that were mapped as marked with both H3K27me3 and H3K4me3 or H3K27me3 alone, according to the Mikkelsen-data set (Mikkelsen et al., 2007), were associated with H3K27me3 according to the H3K27me3 mapping data by Boyer et al (Boyer et al., 2006), indicating a strong overlap between the two data sets for this histone mark. The chromatin-state

Figure 6. Derivation of genes bivalent or H3K4me3 marked genes with HCPs in Ring1b-deficient ES cells

Circle graphs show that Ring1b primarily occupies (C) and regulates (D) transcription of genes with high GC content promoters (HCPs) rather than intermediate (ICP) or 'low' (LCP) GC content promoters, compared to the distribution of HCPs in all genes (A) or only the deregulated genes (B) at the microarray ('genome-wide'). (E) Bar graph showing the distribution (percentages) of the chromatin state of HCPs for all genes on the whole microarray ('genome-wide'); only the genes deregulated in absence of Ring1b; Ring1b bound genes; only deregulated Ring1b bound genes in Ring1b-deficient ES cells. Graph shows that Ring1b binds and regulates transcription of bivalent, and to a lesser extent H3K4me3 marked genes (final two columns), in contrast to the genome-wide distribution of these marks on promoters (first two columns).

(F) as (E), but for genes with ICPs. Graph shows that bivalent Ring1b bound genes with ICPs are not deregulated in Ring1b-deficient ES cells.

(G) Boxplot representing Affimetrix array data of RNA expression levels in wild type ES cells (Mikkelsen et al., 2007), for the genes represented in (E). The boxplot shows that the median expression levels of H3K4me3 marked genes on the whole microarray ('genome-wide') are higher compared to the median RNA expression levels of H3K4me3+H3K27me3 marked genes (first two columns). This is similar for genes that are bound by Ring1b (middle two columns), and for Ring1b bound genes that are deregulated in Ring1b-deficient ES cells (last two columns). Black diamond represents median RNA expression level.

Line graph showing changes (log2 ratio) in gene expression of bivalently (H-I) or H3K4me3 (J-K) marked genes bound by Ring1b following deletion of Ring1b in *Ring1b*^{-lox}/*CreERT2* ES cells. Time is indicated in number of days of 4-OHT treatment.

maps also contain information about the GC content of promoters genome-wide. Mikkelsen and colleagues show that genes with high-

GC content promoters (HCP) and H3K4me3 marks generally have 'housekeeping' functions, including replication and basic metabolism,

Figure S2. Ring1b bound H3K4me3 marked genes with GC-rich promoters retain this mark in NPCs and MEFs

Bar graph showing the distribution of the chromatin-state of the Ring1b bound genes with high-GC-content promoters (HCP) in neural progenitor cells (NPC) or MEFs that were marked with either H3K4me3 or H3K4me3+H3K27me3 in ES cells. The graph represents the chromatin state of all Ring1b bound genes that are represented on the microarray ('all'), and only the Ring1b bound genes that are deregulated in *Ring1b* deficient ES cells ('dereg'). These data show that most H3K4me3 marked genes retain this mark in NPCs and MEFs.

while genes with HCP and bivalent marks mainly include key developmental transcription factors, morphogens, and cell surface markers. Genes with low-GC content promoters (LCP) are associated with highly tissue-specific genes. A third class of genes with intermediate-GC content promoter (ICP) was added to ensure discrimination between the HCPs and LCPs.

Comparative analysis showed that about two-third of the promoters genome-wide, i.e. represented on our microarrays, or differentially regulated in Ring1b-deficient ES cells, had HCPs (Figure 6A, 6B). Remarkably, Ring1b almost exclusively associated with and regulated transcription of genes with HCPs (93%; 882/948 and 94%; 119/126, respectively; Figure 6C, 6D). This suggests that Ring1b primarily regulates transcription of GC-rich promoters.

We next analyzed the chromatin state of the

Ring1b bound genes with HCPs. We found that these genes were strongly associated with bivalent marks (74%; 653/882). A similar fraction of deregulated Ring1b bound genes with HCPs was bivalently marked (73%; 87/119; Figure 6E). These deregulated bivalently marked Ring1b bound genes included mostly developmental genes, such as *Bin1*, *Bmi1*, *Bmp7*, *Col4a2*, *Ccnd2*, *En1*, *Gata3*, *Lmx1a* and *Wnt6*, and were predominantly derepressed in absence of Ring1b (86%; 75/87; Figure 6H, 6I). Interestingly, we found that Ring1b was also associated with a considerable number of HCPs with the H3K4me3 mark alone (25%; 218/882; Figure 6E). The lack of repressive H3K27me3 marks at these genes, catalyzed by PRC2, implies that Ring1b might be recruited independent from PRC2 for these genes in ES cells. Of the deregulated H3K4me3 marked Ring1b bound genes with HCPs 66% (21/32) was derepressed, including *Eif4g3*, *Gja1* and *Sgce*, and various histone encoding genes, such as *Hist1h2bn*, *Hist1h2bf*, *Hist1h3i*, *Hist1h4h*, and *Hist1h4f* (Figure 6J, 6K). Not all promoters associated with the active H3K4me3 mark are actively transcribed (Mikkelsen et al., 2007). Considering the fact that Ring1b is a transcriptional repressor, we predicted that the H3K4me3 marked genes with relative low expression levels were bound by Ring1b. We therefore examined the RNA expression levels of these genes in wild type ES cells by using the Affimetrix RNA expression data that was available in the chromatin-state mapping study by Mikkelsen et al. (Mikkelsen et al., 2007). Unexpectedly, Ring1b binding did not correlate with low expression levels of H3K4me3 marked genes, but instead seemed to associate with these actively marked genes indifferent of their level of expression (Figure 6G). Notably, in more committed NPCs and MEFs (89% and 83%, respectively) most of the Ring1b bound H3K4me3 marked genes retain this histone mark and corresponding transcriptional state, according to the chromatin-state maps generated for these cell types (Mikkelsen et al.,

2007) (Supplementary Figure S2). In contrast, of the bivalently marked genes only 11% and 51% retain both histone marks in NPCs and MEFs, respectively (Mikkelsen et al., 2007) (Figure S2), indicating that Ring1b does not act to silence the H3K4me3 marked genes in ES cells or during development. Although we cannot exclude that differentiation-associated changes affect transcription of the Ring1b bound genes, these data suggest that Ring1b predominantly represses bivalent genes, and is also involved in modulating, rather than silencing, the transcriptional activity of genes with the active H3K4me3 histone mark in ES cells. Strikingly, a specific subset of Ring1b bound genes was not affected following Ring1b deletion. This subset contains LCPs, which were all without H3K27me3 or H3K4me3 marks, and bivalently marked genes with ICPs (Figure 6D, 6F). This implies that other mechanisms are involved in regulation of these genes in ES cells.

Summarizing, these data suggest that Ring1b is involved in direct regulation of RNAPII controlled promoters with 'high' GC content and epigenetically distinct histone marks, namely bivalent marks or the active H3K4me3 mark, in mouse ES cells.

Discussion

To investigate the role of Ring1b in mouse ES cells, we employed a conditional knockout system. By performing microarray analysis, we studied the genome-wide changes in gene transcription that occur following *Ring1b* deletion in ES cells. We found that in *Ring1b*-deficient ES cells key developmental genes were derepressed, including a subset of genes bound by stem cell regulators Oct4 and Nanog, suggesting that *Ring1b* deficiency results in activation of the differentiation program. Accordingly, specific differentiation-related pathways were differentially deregulated, including TGF β signaling, cellular communication and cell cycle pathways. Importantly, retained expression of

stem cell regulators Oct4 and Nanog indicates that *Ring1b*-deficient ES cells still have important ES cell specific characteristics. Based on re-analysis of previously published global binding studies performed in mouse ES cells, we found that Ring1b predominantly binds and represses genes with GC-rich promoters. Furthermore, these genes are associated with bivalent domains or the H3K4me3 histone mark alone. We suggest that Ring1b contributes to stable maintenance of pluripotency of ES cells by repressing bivalently or actively marked genes.

We found that Ring1b is required to repress the differentiation program in ES cells, which is consistent with the observation that *Ring1b*-deficient ES cells are prone for differentiation (Leeb and Wutz, 2007). Comparative analysis with genome-wide Ring1b binding data of mouse ES cells (Boyer et al., 2006), indicated that Ring1b is involved in direct transcriptional regulation of key developmental genes, such as *Bmp7*, *Gata3* and *Msx*. This is in agreement with other genome-wide and candidate-based PcG binding studies performed in mouse and human ES cells (Tolhuis et al., 2006; Bracken et al., 2006; Lee et al., 2006; Boyer et al., 2006; Squazzo et al., 2006; Leeb and Wutz, 2007; Azuara et al., 2006; Shen et al., 2008; Ku et al., 2008). Notably, by directly repressing these extracellular downstream effector components of differentiation-related pathways, such as *Bmp7* and *Id3* of the Bmp/TGF β signaling pathway, and *Col4a2*, *Gja1* and *Ccnd2* of the cellular communication pathways, Ring1b may have an important role in influencing lineage choice and other developmental events. For example, expression of ECM protein Col4a2 was shown to induce mesodermal differentiation of ES cells *in vitro*, while repression of *Bmp7* at the dorsal site of the zebra fish gastrula was shown to allow cellular migration as is required for limb development. (von der et al., 2007; Nishikawa et al., 1998). In *Ring1b* knockout embryos, several developmental markers are misexpressed

at early gastrulation stages, extraembryonic mesoderm is over-represented, epiblast has expanded improperly, and embryonic growth is delayed (Voncken et al., 2003). This is in line with the aberrant expression of developmental markers and induction of apoptosis observed in *Ring1b* knockout ES cells. The early embryonic lethality is partially rescued in a *Cdkn2a*-knockout background, one of the PcG transcriptional targets (Bracken et al., 2007; Jacobs et al., 1999), resulting in the delay of embryonic death of about 4 days (Voncken et al., 2003). Since relief of the Ink4a/Arf-mediated antiproliferative block only bypasses the proliferative defects induced by loss of Ring1b, this underscores the importance for Ring1b in regulating developmental genes during early embryogenesis.

The observation that only a subset of Ring1b bound genes is derepressed following deletion of *Ring1b* in ES cells, suggests that additional mechanisms mediate silencing of the other Ring1b target genes. This would be in correspondence with observations by others, who show that only part of the PcG bound genes are deregulated after RNAi-mediated depletion of PcGs in human embryonic fibroblasts and in ES cells deficient for Eed or Suz12 (Bracken et al., 2006; Pasini et al., 2007; Boyer et al., 2006). Partial derepression could also be explained by functional redundancy by Ring1a, which possess ubiquitin E3 ligase activity towards histone H2A, like Ring1b, although with less efficiency (de Napoles et al., 2004; Cao et al., 2005; Wei et al., 2006). In addition, the composition of PRCs can vary among tissues and developmental stages (Squazzo et al., 2006; Kuzmichev et al., 2005; de Napoles et al., 2004; Pasini et al., 2007). Therefore, Ring1b might not be essential in every promoter-bound PcG repressive complex. We found that Ring1b represses genes that are co-occupied by Oct4 and Nanog. This is consistent with earlier reports, which show a role for PcG proteins in repressing a set of developmental genes that are bound by Oct4 and Nanog in ES

cells (Lee et al., 2006; Loh et al., 2006). A possible link between these proteins is provided by Wang and colleagues, who co-purified Oct4, YY1 and Ring1b with stem cell specific protein Rex-1 from ES cells (Wang et al., 2006). In *Drosophila*, PcG-specific sequences (named Polycomb group responsive elements or PREs) mediate PcG repression (Mulholland et al., 2003). However, in mammals, PREs or sequence-specific DNA binding PcG proteins have not been identified. Therefore, one might speculate that recruitment of PcG-silencing complexes to specific genes involves interactions with site-specific DNA-binding factors. This could be the recruitment of the PcG silencing complex to key developmental genes through interaction with stem cell specific factors Rex-1 and/or Oct4 in order to maintain an undifferentiated state of ES cells. This suggestion is supported by the observation that Suz12 dissociates from PcG/Oct4 co-occupied promoters upon downregulation of Oct4 (Pasini et al., 2007). Interestingly, others have found that histone H2A E3 ligase 2A-HUB, but not Ring1b, is selectively required for H2A monoubiquitination and subsequent repression of chemokine genes following recruitment by co-repressor N-CoR in human monocytes (Zhou et al., 2008). Together, this suggests that different site-specific factors are involved in the recruitment of distinct H2A E3 ligases to mediate repression of a specific set of genes.

Ring1b-deficient ES cells retain expression of important stem cell regulators Oct4, Nanog and alkaline phosphatase, which was also observed in other PcG-deficient ES cells (Pasini et al., 2007; Stock et al., 2007; Leeb and Wutz, 2007). Derepression of developmental genes and downregulation of other stem cell markers, such as Rex-1, Sox2 and Dppa3, suggests activation of the differentiation program. During ES cell differentiation, repression of Oct4 and Nanog is essential, considering that ectopic expression of Oct4 can block differentiation, while expression of Nanog is enough to maintain ES cell self-renewal and pluripotency, even in the absence

of extrinsic factor LIF or Oct4 expression (Niwa et al., 2000; Chambers et al., 2003; Hochedlinger et al., 2005). Retained expression of Oct4 and Nanog could indicate that PcG proteins are either directly or indirectly involved in regulation of Oct4 and Nanog. A direct role for PcG proteins in regulating the expression of Oct4 and Nanog has been suggested by Pasini and co-workers, who show that PRC2 proteins bind to the *Oct4* and *Nanog* promoters in ES cells (Pasini et al., 2007). Moreover, the H3K27me3 histone mark has been found at the *Oct4* promoter in more committed cells, suggesting that PcG proteins are involved in direct repression of stem cell regulators in differentiated cells (Azua et al., 2006).

Comparative analysis of our expression profiling data with recently published global chromatin-state maps generated of mouse ES cells showed that Ring1b almost exclusively binds to genes with GC-rich promoters. This is in consistent with a report showing that a strong correlation exists between promoters with highly conserved large CpG islands and Suz12 binding domains in undifferentiated human ES cells (Tanay et al., 2007). Furthermore, our data confirm that PcG proteins are involved in repressing bivalently marked developmental genes in ES cells (Bernstein et al., 2006; Stock et al., 2007; Mikkelsen et al., 2007; Azua et al., 2006). This comparative analysis also revealed that a considerable number of actively transcribed H3K4me3 marked Ring1b bound genes are regulated (mainly repressed) in ES cells. The absence of H3K27me3 at these promoters suggests that Ring1b is recruited independently from PRC2. This is in agreement with other observations indicating that *Xist* RNA, but not PRC2, is required for PRC1 recruitment during X inactivation in differentiating ES cells (Schoeftner et al., 2006), although it is unclear how the recent report describing PRC2 member EZH2 to specifically bind to a sequence in the *Xist* RNA, recruiting PRC2 to the inactive X, fits in this picture (Zhao et al., 2008).

The association of Ring1b to actively transcribed genes is consistent with global and candidate-based binding studies that show overlap between PcG and RNAPII occupancy or association of PcG proteins with expressed genes in mouse and human ES cells, neural progenitor cells and embryonic fibroblasts (Bracken et al., 2006; Squazzo et al., 2006; Lee et al., 2006; Breiling et al., 2004; Pasini et al., 2007). This suggests that Ring1b does not function as a silencer of these genes in ES cells. Moreover, a large subset of actively marked genes retain this mark and corresponding transcriptional state in more committed NPCs and MEFs (Mikkelsen et al., 2007). Thus, rather than poising for activation or prolonged inactivation, as was proposed for the bivalent genes, Ring1b might be required to modulate the transcriptional activity of this subset of actively marked genes in ES cells and during later developmental stages. Only recently, association of Ring1b and uH2A was shown to mediate a silenced state of RNAPII present at promoters and coding regions of bivalent genes (Stock et al., 2007). Dissociation of Ring1b and uH2A from these promoters results in activation of the RNAPII complex without major changes in the levels of PRC2 proteins or association of H3K27me3. In addition, others showed that the presence of uH2A in the promoter-proximal region blocks recruitment of FACT resulting in pausing of RNAPII and inhibition of transcriptional elongation (Zhou et al., 2008). One could speculate that Ring1b-mediated monoubiquitination of histone H2A also interferes with the RNAPII complex at active H3K4me3 marked genes, but how remains to be investigated.

Altogether, our data suggest that Ring1b is important to maintain an undifferentiated state of ES cells through repression of key developmental genes. The finding that this involves direct transcriptional repression of at least two epigenetically distinct sets of genes helps to understand and further explore the

role of Ring1b during development.

Materials and Methods

Generating Ring1b conditional knockout ES cells

The *Ring1b* wild type allele in *Ring1b*^{+/-} ES cells (Voncken et al., 2003) was targeted with a construct containing loxP sequences at the EcoRI site in intron 2 and at the XhoI site in intron 4, followed by a third loxP site enclosing a hygromycin cassette to allow for selection of targeted ES cells. Correct targeting of hygromycin resistant *Ring1b*^{-loxHyg} ES cell clones was confirmed by Southern blot analysis. Next, to obtain *Ring1b*^{-lox} ES clones the hygromycin cassette was removed by transiently expressing adenoviral Cre and subsequently screening for hygromycin sensitivity. Correct removal of the hygromycin cassette in the selected *Ring1b*^{-lox} ES clones was confirmed by Southern blot analysis. Finally, to generate inducible conditional *Ring1b*^{-lox;CreERT2} ES cells a puromycin-selectable R26CreERT2 construct was targeted to the ROSA26 locus. CreERT2 could be activated by adding 200 nM 4-OHT (Sigma, dissolved in absolute ethanol) to the ES cell medium.

Southern blot analysis of HindIII digested genomic DNA and a 5' end external probe in intron 1 to discriminate between the *Ring1b* wild type (11 kb), conventional knockout (5 kb) (Voncken et al., 2003), *lox* (7 kb), and *Del* (4 kb) allele. The *Del* allele follows from deletion of exons 3 and 4 after 4-OHT-mediated activation of CreERT2 in *Ring1b*^{-lox;CreERT2} ES cells.

Cell culture

ES cells were cultured on dishes coated with 0.1% gelatin (Sigma) without feeders in 60% conditional Buffalo Rat Liver (BRL) medium, which consisted of 60% BRL medium and 40% standard ES medium. Standard ES cell medium consisted of GMEM (Gibco), 10% fetal calf serum (Sigma), supplemented with 1% non-essential amino acids, 1 mM sodium pyruvate,

L-glutamate, 0.1 M β-mercaptoethanol and 10³ units LIF (all Gibco). BRL medium was derived by filtering (0.2 μM) the supernatant of BRL cells cultured for one week in standard ES cell medium without β-mercaptoethanol or LIF.

Ring1b conditional ES cells or *Ring1b*^{+/+;CreERT2} control ES cells were treated with 200 nM 4-OHT and MEFs with 1 μM 4-OHT for the indicated time. MEFs were isolated from 14.5 day old embryos and cultured as described before (Jacobs et al., 1999). For RA treatment ES cells were cultured in standard ES medium without LIF and in the presence of 500 nM all-trans-RA (ATRA) (Sigma).

Protein isolation and Western blot analysis

Proteins were extracted from whole cells (RIPA lysates, protocol as described previously) (Hernandez-Munoz et al., 2005a) or from the nucleus (nuclear extraction). For nuclear extracts cells were washed with PBS, incubated on ice for 5 min in Triton lysis buffer (0.1 M NaCl, 0.3 M sucrose, 3 mM MgCl₂, 50 mM HEPES pH 6.8, 1 mM EGTA, 0.2% Triton-X100) supplemented with Complete protease inhibitor cocktail and 10 mM N-ethylmaleimide (NEM) followed by spinning at for 5 min 3000 rpm at 4°C to pellet the nuclei. Nucleic proteins were recovered by incubating the nuclei in SDS-lysis buffer (0.1% SDS, 50 mM TrisHCl pH 7.5, 0.15 M NaCl) for 10 min on ice, followed by sonification (10 pulses at 50%, level 4) and spinning for 1 min at 14,000 rpm to remove insoluble material. Protein samples were assayed with SDS-PAGE using pre-cast gradient gels (Invitrogen) and conventional Western blotting techniques.

Immunostaining, alkaline phosphatase, and Annexin V staining

ES cells were cultured four days with 200 nM 4-OHT or three days with 500 nM RA on cover slips coated with 0.1% gelatin. Cells were fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde for 10 min at RT and permeabilization in 0.25% Triton-X100/PBS for 5 min. Cells were then incubated for 30

minutes at RT in blocking solution (5% fetal calf serum (Gibco), 5% normal goat serum (Vector laboratories), 0.02% Triton-X100/PBS). Next, cells were incubated with the 1st antibody for 1 hour at RT in blocking solution and afterwards washed five times 5 minutes with 0.02% Triton-X100/PBS. Hereafter, cells were incubated for 1 hour at RT with fluorescence labeled 2nd antibody in blocking solution, followed by five washes of 5 min each with 0.02% Triton-X100/PBS. Cover slips were mounted on object slides using Vectashield with DAPI (Vector Laboratories). For the uH2A immunostaining cells were permeabilized prior to fixation by in cytoskeletal buffer (100 mM NaCl, 300 mM sucrose, 3 mM MgCl₂, 10 mM PIPES pH6.8) for 30 sec, followed by 30 sec in cytoskeletal buffer containing 0.5% Triton-X100, and 30 sec in cytoskeletal buffer without Triton-X100, all on ice.

For the alkaline phosphatase staining cells were cultured on dishes, followed by fixation and stained according to the manufactures protocol (Sigma).

To determine the level of apoptosis, cells were collected by trypsinization, or first washed twice with PBS to obtain only the adherent cells, followed by staining with FITC-conjugated Annexin V-FITC (Roche) according to the manufactures protocol and analyzed by flow cytometry.

Antibodies

H3K27me3 rabbit polyclonal was a kind gift from T. Jenuwein. EZH2 mouse monoclonal antibody was a kind gift from K. Helin. Ring1b mouse monoclonal and rabbit polyclonal antibodies were obtained from H. Koseki. Oct4 mouse monoclonal antibody C-10 and Lamin-B goat polyclonal antibody M20 from Santa Cruz, Nestin mouse monoclonal antibody from BD, Eed rabbit polyclonal and Bmi1 and uH2A mouse monoclonal antibodies from Upstate. Secondary immunofluorescence antibodies were Alexa 488- or 568-conjugated anti-mouse, 568- or 488-conjugated anti-rabbit

from Molecular Probes.

Image analysis and quantification

To quantify the fluorescence levels of immunofluorescence-labeled proteins in individual cells, we took sequential images of DAPI and the fluorescence labeled protein using a Leica confocal research microscope with a 63x lens and fixed laser settings per protein. Files were saved in TIFF format with 512x512 resolution. The images were analyzed with Image-Pro 5.1 software (Media Cybernetics). In brief, mean fluorescence intensity levels of the immunofluorescence-labeled protein per cell were measured for the nucleic area as was determined by the DAPI staining for on average 250 cells per quantification and three independent stainings. The distribution of the mean intensity per cell is displayed in histogram figures with same x-axis scale.

RNA isolation, real-time qPCR and microarray analysis

Ring1b^{-lox}; *CreER*^{T2} and *Ring1b*^{+/-}; *CreER*^{T2} control ES cells (used as a reference for qPCR and microarray) were cultured under the same conditions and RNA was isolated at the indicated time points. Total RNA was isolated using TRIzol reagent (Invitrogen) according to the manufacturer's protocol followed by DNase treatment and RNA amplification (Invitrogen). Real-time qPCR conditions and primer sequences are as described elsewhere (Boyer et al., 2006). Changes in RNA levels following 4-OHT treatment of *Ring1b*^{-lox}; *CreER*^{T2} relative to *Ring1b*^{+/-}; *CreER*^{T2} ES cells were determined based on the results of three qPCRs.

The oligonucleotide arrays were printed at the CMF core facility of the NKI/AvL with mouse Operon microarray version 3 (<http://microarrays.nki.nl/download/geneid.html>). Detailed information about the labeling and hybridization protocols and array analysis can be found on the NKI/AvL microarray website (<http://microarrays.nki.nl/download/protocols.html>). In brief, amplified RNA was

labeled with ULS Cy5 or Cy3 (Kreatech EA-006, Amsterdam) was pooled and co-hybridized to the microarray (each experiment was performed in dye swap fashion and controlled with self-self hybridization experiments to correct for dye-bias). After 16 hours of hybridization the microarrays were washed and scanned using an Agilent DNA Microarray scanner (Agilent Technologies, Cat# G2505B). ImaGene v6.0 software (BioDiscovery Inc) was used to quantify the RNA expression levels using the tiff images produced by the scanner. The background-corrected intensities from the Cy5 and Cy3 channel were used to calculate log₂ transformed ratios. These ratios were normalized using a lowest fit per subarray (Yang et al., 2002). A weighted average ratio and confidence level (P-value) was calculated per gene by a NKI platform adjusted error model (Hughes et al., 2000), which was fine-tuned by self-self hybridizations. Significantly differentially expressed genes (outliers) between sample and reference were selected based on their P-value (a gene with a P-value <0.05 was considered an outlier). The microarray details and results are submitted

to the ArrayExpress database (<http://www.ebi.ac.uk/arrayexpress/>), reference number E-NCMF-14. Clustering of the microarray data was performed using the bioinformatics software program Genesis (Sturn et al., 2002). GO classification analysis was performed using bioinformatics program BiNGO (Maere et al., 2005). Pathway analysis was performed using the bioinformatics software program DAVID based on the KEGG pathway database available online (<http://david.abcc.ncifcrf.gov>).

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Chapter 4

Ring1b is required for
brain development and
neural stem cell proliferation

DNA neither cares nor knows. DNA just *is*. And we dance to its music.
Richard Dawkins, 'River out of Eden'

Ring1b is required for brain development and neural stem cell proliferation

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Polycomb group proteins are epigenetic chromatin modifiers involved in gene repression. They function in two distinct multimeric protein complexes: the PRC2 complex initiates the silencing that is maintained by the PRC1 complex. Whereas loss of PRC2 genes unequivocally leads to early embryonic lethality, removal of PRC1 genes causes less severe phenotypes. The exception to this is PRC1 member *Ring1b*, which is also essential for mice to survive through embryonic development. We now demonstrate that mice deficient for *Ring1b* exclusively in the central nervous system can survive until birth. However, these animals suffer from neurological malfunctions and die prematurely within the first month of postnatal life. They exhibit defects in neural stem cell proliferation and cerebellar development, possibly due to the deregulation of the *Ink4a/Arf* and *Engrailed* genes.

Introduction

The Polycomb Group (PcG) of proteins constitutes a highly conserved family of gene silencers. Originally, they were discovered in *Drosophila melanogaster* as repressors of the *Homeotic* genes, which are required for the establishment of the body plan and proper segmentation. Accordingly, the vertebrate PcG homologues were found to be involved in *Homeobox (Hox)* gene regulation as well. PcG proteins function in distinct multimeric complexes designated Polycomb repressive complexes 1 and 2 (PRC1 and PRC2) (reviewed in Lund and van Lohuizen, 2004). The PRC2 complex initiates gene silencing and contains histone deacetylases and methyltransferases that adjust the epigenetic histone marks associated with repressive chromatin. Subsequently, PRC1 recognizes the K27 methyl mark placed on histone H3 by PRC2 component EZH2 and associates with the chromatin to maintain the repressive state (reviewed in Valk-Lingbeek et al., 2004). Deletion of PRC2 genes causes early embryonic lethality in mice indicating essential functions in development (Faust et al., 1998; Donohoe et al.,

1999; O'Carroll et al., 2001; Pasini et al., 2004). In contrast, removal of PRC1 genes is compatible with postnatal life, although these animals usually have a shortened lifespan and display signs of *Hox* transformations such as aberrant segmentation of the axial skeleton (van der Lugt et al., 1994; Akasaka et al., 1996; Takihara et al., 1997; Core et al., 1997; Mar Lorente et al., 2000). However, the exception is PRC1 member *Ring1b (Rnf2)*. Deletion of this gene results in embryonic death, suggesting that *Ring1b* has a special role in the PRC1 complex that cannot be compensated for (Voncken et al., 2003). Intriguingly, recent evidence showed that *Ring1b* has an enzymatic function as it acts as an E3 ubiquitin ligase for histone H2A (de Napoles et al., 2004; Wang et al., 2004). Monoubiquitinated H2A (uH2A) represents approximately one tenth of all H2A and is enriched on the inactivated X chromosome (X_i) of female cells, suggestive of a function in repression. Both PRC2 and PRC1 are involved in X chromosome silencing and removal of *Ring1b* leads to loss of global uH2A levels (de Napoles et al., 2004; Fang et al., 2004; Wang et al., 2004; Hernandez-Munoz et al., 2005). Interestingly, the E3 ligase activity of

Ring1b may be enhanced by binding to PRC1 protein Bmi1 through interactions between their N-terminal Ring fingers (Cao et al., 2005; Buchwald et al., 2006; Li et al., 2006). Bmi1 itself does not appear to have E3 ligase activity. Instead, it stabilizes Ring1b and modulates Ring1b self-ubiquitination required for H2A monoubiquitination (Ben Saadon et al., 2006). Even though the *in vivo* relevance of H2A ubiquitination by the Bmi1/Ring1b heterodimer remains to be elucidated, it is clear that these PcG genes interact genetically. *Bmi1* deficient mice suffer from a range of developmental defects (van der Lugt et al., 1994). One striking feature is a severe reduction in size and cellularity of the cerebellum, which is aggravated in a *Ring1b* heterozygous background (Voncken et al., 2003). As mentioned, homozygous deletion of *Ring1b* is early embryonic lethal and no *Ring1b*^{-/-} embryos can be found after embryonic day 10.5 (E10.5). Close inspection of the null embryos revealed an overall delay in development and abnormal gastrulation (Voncken et al., 2003). Notably, a *Ring1b* hypomorphic mouse was viable and exhibited only mild posterior *Hox* transformations, underlining the importance of gene dosage (Suzuki et al., 2002). One possible explanation for the gastrulation defect may be that Ring1b is required for the proper execution of differentiation programs. *Ring1b* conditional knockout embryonic stem (ES) cells show a strong reduction in proliferation and increase in cell death (Leeb and Wutz, 2007; Van der Stoop and Boutsma et al., 2008). The remaining cells are extremely sensitive to stress and prone to undergo differentiation, as illustrated by the untimely derepression of developmental genes. Concomitantly, they are impaired in the formation and differentiation of embryoid bodies (Leeb and Wutz, 2007).

Given these dramatic effects of *Ring1b* loss on early development, we wanted to address whether Ring1b is required for the formation of tissue and cells at later stages. It has been demonstrated that ectopic expression of *Ring1b*

in the chick embryo causes neural tubes defects (Suzuki et al., 2002). Since heterozygosity for *Ring1b* had an additive effect on the cerebellar phenotype of *Bmi1* null mice, we hypothesized that Ring1b plays a role in the central nervous system (CNS) and set out to investigate *Ring1b* function in this tissue. Hereto, we took advantage of the possibility to ablate *Ring1b* specifically from the CNS by crossing our conditional *Ring1b* knockout mouse (Van der Stoop and Boutsma et al., 2008) with a transgenic mouse expressing the Cre recombinase under the control of the Nestin promoter and enhancer (Tronche et al., 1999). Surprisingly, although born at submendelian ratios, mice lacking *Ring1b* expression in the CNS are viable. They exhibit severe progressive growth retardation, have problems in balance-keeping and die within one month after birth. Similar to *Bmi1* deficiency, *Ring1b* knockout neural stem cell proliferation is impaired and the *Ring1b* null cerebellum has a smaller size. However, the cerebellum also has a unique defect in foliation not described for other PcG mutants. It has been shown that loss of the *Ink4a/Arf* tumor suppressor locus can partially rescue the early arrest in embryonic development of *Ring1b* null embryos (Voncken et al., 2003). Here we demonstrate that deletion of *Ink4a/Arf* rescues the neural stem cell proliferation defect. But in line with recent findings that PcG genes control numerous genes involved in cell fate determination (Boyer et al., 2006; Bracken et al., 2006; Lee et al., 2006; Negre et al., 2006; Tolhuis et al., 2006; Pasini et al., 2007), we also provide evidence that the *Engrailed* genes, which are implicated in cerebellar development and foliation, are deregulated in the absence of *Ring1b*.

Results

Generation of nervous system specific Ring1b knockout mice

We first analyzed Ring1b protein expression in the wild type brain. In the adult, Ring1b is

Figure 1

Figure 1. Generation of nervous system specific *Ring1b* deficient mice

(A) Ring1b protein immunolabeling in different areas of the adult and neonatal wild type brain (SVZ=subventricular zone, P=postnatal day).

(B) Immunolabeling for Ring1b in the *NCre;Ring1b^{-/lox}* brain demonstrates that Ring1b protein is absent.

(C) Targeting constructs used to generate the Ring1b knockout (R1b KO) and the Ring1b conditional knockout allele (R1b lox). Targeted for deletion are exons 3 and 4 containing the Ring finger domain (H=HindIII restriction site, E=EcoRI, X=XhoI, Blue E=exon, WT=wild type).

(D) Ratios of pups born with specific genotypes; according to Mendelian inheritance, equal ratios were expected.

(E) Photographs of three weeks old control and *NCre;Ring1b^{-/lox}* (black arrowhead) littermates.

(F) Western blot analysis demonstrating absence of Ring1b protein in different regions of the brain (HC=hippocampus, CX=cortex, CB=cerebellum, WT= wild type, KO=*Ring1b* knockout).

(G) qRT-PCR demonstrating absence of *Ring1b* mRNA in the *NCre;Ring1b^{-/lox}* brain.

(H) Chart representing the total body weight of *Ring1b* knockout and control littermates.

(I) Chart representing the total brain weight of *Ring1b* knockout and control littermates.

widely expressed throughout the brain and is detected in the vast majority of cells (Figure 1A). Based on morphology and location, these cells represent both neurons and glia. In the P8 (postnatal day 8) cerebellum, Ring1b seems more strongly expressed in specific areas.

To achieve the nervous system specific removal of *Ring1b*, we made use of a transgenic mouse line (NCre) that expresses the Cre recombinase under the control of the Nestin promoter and second intron enhancer (Tronche et al., 1999). This transgene has been reported to be highly specific for the CNS and is expressed from E10.5 onwards (Graus-Porta et al., 2001; Knoepfler et al., 2002). We crossed NCre transgenic mice heterozygous for the *Ring1b* knockout allele (Voncken et al., 2003), or NCre mice heterozygous for the conditional *Ring1b* allele (referred to as *Ring1b^{lox}*), with mice carrying two copies of the *Ring1b^{lox}* allele. The floxed region in the *Ring1b* conditional allele is similar to the deleted region of the knockout allele, such that Cre expression causes not only the excision of the Ring finger domain, which is located in exons 3 and 4 (Figure 1C), but also introduces several in-frame stop codons. Exact details of the targeting strategy of the conditional *Ring1b* allele is described in chapter 3 of this thesis.

NCre;Ring1b^{-lox} (or *NCre;Ring1b^{lox/lox}*) mice were born at submendelian ratios, indicating the occurrence of some pre- or perinatal death (Figure 1D). We could not detect any Ring1b protein in the brain of *NCre;Ring1b^{-lox}* mice by immunohistochemical staining, demonstrating that recombination of the floxed allele was very efficient (Figure 1B). Western blot (Figure 1F) or quantitative real-time PCR (qRT-PCR) analysis (Figure 1G) confirmed the absence of Ring1b protein or mRNA in the knockout brain. Of note, inspection of other organs revealed no differences in *Ring1b* expression corroborating the nervous system specificity of the transgene (data not shown). Interestingly, *Ring1b* CNS knockout mice were significantly

smaller than wild type littermates, a phenotype that became progressively stronger in time (Figure 1E and 1H). They also had a smaller brain than control animals (Figure 1I). Notably, all pups we dissected (aged between P0 and P16) had milk in their stomachs, making the growth retardation probably not the result of poor suckling. Another striking feature of the *Ring1b* knockout mice was their lack of control of movement. They displayed severe problems in balance-keeping and an ataxic gait, which is suggestive of defects in the cerebellum. Because of as yet unknown reasons, *Ring1b* knockout mice died prematurely. Some survived for approximately one month whereas others already died at earlier time points.

The Ring1b knockout cerebellum has foliation defects

The total size of the entire *Ring1b* knockout brain is greatly reduced, yet the cerebrum did not show any obvious gross abnormalities. The cerebellum on the other hand appeared abnormal macroscopically as some (sub)lobules, which are also called folia, of the vermis and hemispheres were missing (Figure 2A). To decipher which (sub)lobules were absent, we prepared sagittal sections of adult control and *Ring1b* null cerebella. To ensure that a complete overview was obtained, we analyzed haematoxylin and eosin (H&E) stained slides at 100 micron intervals along the entire medial-lateral axis. In few knockout animals complete separation of the hemispherical ansiform sublobules into Crus I and II had not occurred, but this was not reproducibly observed. At the level of the anterior vermis, we found with a high penetrance (5/6 animals) that the precentral fissure had not formed resulting in a fusion between the ventral (II) and dorsal lobules (III) of the central vermian lobe (Figure 2B).

The cerebellum is a favored model for studying cortical development due to its relatively simple histology, but the precise genetic mechanisms underlying the formation of its numerous folia

Figure 2

Figure 2. *Ring1b* deficient mice display anterior defects in cerebellar development

(A) Photographs of *NCre Ring1b^{+/lox}* control and *NCre;Ring1b^{-/lox}* cerebella showing altered foliation of the hemispheres (arrowhead) and reduced cerebellar size. Roman numerals refer to the vermian (sub)lobules (LS=lobulus simplex, C=Crus I and II, PML=paramedial lobule).

(B) H&E stained mid-sagittal sections through the vermis reveal fusion of lobules II and III due to lack of the precentral fissure (indicated by arrowheads).

(C) BrdU staining of the P8 cerebellum of *Ring1b^{+/lox}* control and *NCre;Ring1b^{-/lox}* mice.

(D) Quantification of the BrdU positive nuclei in the P8 cerebellum shows a minor, insignificant reduction in proliferation in the *Ring1b* deficient cerebellum.

(E) Activated Caspase-3 staining in sagittal cerebellar sections containing the EGL and developing IGL reveals no differences in apoptosis.

(F) Calbindin staining marking Purkinje neurons in the P8 cerebellum.

(G) Calbindin staining marking Purkinje and molecular neurons in the P25 cerebellum.

remains unclear. A number of mutations leading to foliation defects is known, but a phenotype identical to the *Ring1b* null cerebella has not yet been reported. The onset of the five cardinal lobes of the cerebellum is present from E18.5, while the extensive formation of (sub)lobules does not occur until after birth and is therefore generally

believed to be the result of the expansion of the granule neuron population (Sillitoe and Joyner, 2007). Therefore, we histologically analyzed the granule neurons in control and *Ring1b* knockout cerebella. In the P8 cerebellum, when cerebellar granule neuron progenitor (CGNP) amplification is at its peak, we measured proliferation by

Figure 3

Figure 3. *Ring1b* deficient neural stem cells have proliferation defects
(A) Microphotographs showing primary neurosphere cultures from *Ring1b*^{lox/lox} control and *NCre;Ring1b*^{lox/lox} knockout SVZ.
(B) Treatment of inducible *Ring1b* knockout NSCs (*CreERT2;Ring1b*^{-/lox}) with 4-hydroxytamoxifen (4-OHT) for 12 days induces a growth arrest.
(C) Western blot analysis demonstrating the absence of Ring1b in 4-OHT treated inducible knockout NSCs (+/lox=*CreERT2;Ring1b*^{+lox}, -/lox=*CreERT2;Ring1b*^{-lox}).
(D) qRT-PCR analysis confirming reduction of *Ring1b* mRNA levels in *CreERT2;Ring1b*^{-lox} NSCs treated with 4-OHT (C=*CreERT2*, +/lox=*Ring1b*^{+lox}, -/lox=*Ring1b*^{-lox}).
(E) Treatment of inducible *Ring1b* knockout NSCs with 4-OHT leads to a reduction in BrdU incorporation (green signal). Nuclei counterstained with DAPI (blue).
(F) Quantification of BrdU positive nuclei demonstrates a strong reduction in proliferation in inducible *Ring1b* knockout NSCs upon 4-OHT treatment.

determining BrdU incorporation (Figure 2C). In the *Ring1b* null cerebellum, BrdU positive cells were located in the outer external granular layer (EGL) like the control cells, indicating that they properly cease proliferation when they migrate into the inner EGL. We did observe a minor, reproducible reduction in the amount of BrdU positive cells, however this difference was not significant (Figure 4D). In the P25 cerebellum, all EGL cells had disappeared and an internal granular layer (IGL) revealing no abnormalities

had developed. We also questioned whether there was increased cell death in the *Ring1b* deficient EGL. We stained P8 sagittal cerebellar sections for activated Caspase-3, but found no evidence for increased apoptosis in the absence of *Ring1b* (Figure 2E). Since the granule neurons appeared unaffected, we next focused on the other cellular layers: the Purkinje neuron and the molecular layer. As revealed by Calbindin staining, there were no defects in Purkinje neuron deposition or arborization either at P8

Figure 4. Deregulation of genes in the absence of *Ring1b*

(A) qRT-PCR analysis demonstrating reduced *Ring1b* mRNA (upper panel) and increased *Ink4a* and *Arf* mRNA levels (lower panel) in various regions of the knockout brain (C=control, KO=NCre;*Ring1b^{-lox}*, HC=hippocampus, CB=cerebellum, DCx=dorsal cortex, FCx=frontal cortex, ST=striatum).

(B) Treatment of *CreER^{T2}; Ring1b^{+/lox}; Ink4a/Arf^{-/-}* and *CreER^{T2}; Ring1b^{-lox}; Ink4a/Arf^{-/-}* NSCs with 4-OHT reveals equal proliferative capacity in the presence and absence of *Ring1b*.

(C) Western blot analysis showing that no Ring1b protein is present in floxed *Ring1b* null NSCs deficient for *Ink4a/Arf* up to 21 days of 4-OHT treatment (IA=*Ink4a/Arf*, Cre=*CreER^{T2}*, R1b=*Ring1b*).

(D) qRT-PCR showing strong transcriptional upregulation of the *Engrailed-1* gene (*En1*) throughout the *Ring1b* knockout brain.

(E) qRT-PCR showing transcriptional upregulation of *Engrailed-2* (*En2*) throughout the *Ring1b* knockout brain.

(F) Immunolabeling for Engrailed-1 and -2 protein in P8 sagittal *Ncre; Ring1b^{+/lox}* and *Ncre; Ring1b^{-lox}* cerebellar sections.

(Figure 2F) or at P25 (Figure 2G). Also the *Ring1b* deficient molecular layer contained normal cell numbers (Figure 2G).

Ring1b deficient neural stem cells have impaired proliferation

To gain further insight into the *Ring1b* null phenotype, we made use of a culture system that provides the opportunity to study proliferation and differentiation *in vitro*. Hereto,

we isolated adult neural stem cells (NSCs) from the subventricular zone (SVZ) of the lateral ventricles of the cerebrum, a region known to have continuous neurogenesis throughout adult life (Alvarez-Buylla and Lim, 2004). These cells can be propagated as floating clusters of stem cells and more differentiated progeny termed neurospheres (Reynolds and Weiss, 1996), or as homogeneous adherent monolayers (Conti et al., 2005). However, as we were readily able

to generate neurosphere cultures from control mice, the few neurospheres that formed from *NCre;Ring1b^{lox/lox}* animals could not self-renew, but instead attached to the plastic and entered a growth arrest (Figure 3A). Since we were not able to retrieve sufficient material from the *NCre Ring1b* null mice, we had to change to a different system that would allow us to conditionally induce *Ring1b* deletion *in vitro*. We did this by crossing the *Ring1b* (conditional) knockout mouse with the *CreER^{T2}* transgenic knockin mouse (Feil et al., 1997; Ate Loonstra and Anton Berns, unpublished). This transgene consists of a Cre recombinase fused to the mutated ligand-binding domain of the Estrogen receptor (ER). Upon addition of 4-hydroxytamoxifen (4-OHT), the *CreER^{T2}* fusion protein translocates to the nucleus and gets access to the genome. We established adherent neural stem cell cultures from *CreER^{T2};Ring1b^{+/-lox}* and *CreER^{T2};Ring1b^{-/-lox}* mice, plated these cells at sub-confluency and treated them with 4-OHT for 12 days (Figure 3B). Again we noticed that NSCs deficient for *Ring1b* ceased proliferation and appeared to undergo cell death. Western blot analysis (Figure 3C) and qRT-PCR (Figure 3D) revealed that *Ring1b* protein and mRNA was completely absent in the *CreER^{T2};Ring1b^{-/-lox}* cells after 4 days of 4-OHT treatment. The reduction in proliferation was confirmed by a strong decline in BrdU incorporation (Figure 3E and 3F).

Deletion of Ring1b causes derepression of the Ink4a/Arf and Engrailed genes

It had been demonstrated that the *Ink4a/Arf* tumor suppressor locus was upregulated in *Ring1b* deficient embryos, and its removal partially alleviated the gastrulation defect (Voncken et al., 2003). We wanted to test if *Ink4a/Arf* derepression was responsible for the *Ring1b* null phenotypes we observed. As determined by qRT-PCR, both *p16^{ink4a}* and *p19^{arf}* mRNA levels in all regions of the *Ring1b* knockout brain were elevated (Figure 4A). Subsequently, we performed additional mice breedings and isolated NSCs

from *CreER^{T2};Ring1b^{-/-lox};Ink4a/Arf^{-/-}* mice. Remarkably, NSCs lacking *Ring1b* and *Ink4a/Arf* continue to proliferate upon 4-OHT treatment for at least 21 days (Figure 4B), even though *Ring1b* protein was already undetectable after 7 days and remained absent for the entire length of the experiment (Figure 4C). This suggests that at least the defect in neural stem cell proliferation is indeed caused by deregulation of *Ink4a/Arf*. But since PcG genes are known to bind and repress a wide variety of developmental genes (Boyer et al., 2006; Lee et al., 2006), we speculated that more genes ought to be deregulated in the absence of *Ring1b*. We took a candidate approach and started to verify expression of genes which have a demonstrable function in cerebellar foliation. Surprisingly, we found strong increases in the expression of the *Engrailed-1* and *-2* genes in many regions of the *Ring1b* knockout brain, except for the cerebellum, where only *Engrailed-1* showed a minor induction (Figure 4D,E). However, when we stained sagittal sections of the *Ring1b* knockout cerebellum with antibodies that recognize both *Engrailed-1* and *-2* (Figure 4F), or only *Engrailed-1* (not shown), we did not detect higher *Engrailed* expression, nor did we find ectopic expression in for instance the Purkinje neurons.

Discussion

The complete removal of the PcG gene *Ring1b* from mice is not compatible with life as *Ring1b* knockout embryos only develop until the second half of embryogenesis (Voncken et al., 2003). These embryos exhibit a general delay in development and gastrulation is abnormal. In line with this, embryonic stem cells and fibroblasts deficient for *Ring1b* are extremely sensitive to stress and prone to differentiate or undergo apoptosis (Leeb and Wutz, 2007; Van der Stoop and Boutsma et al., 2008). Therefore, it is somewhat surprising that mice specifically lacking *Ring1b* expression in the central nervous system can survive until birth

and the first weeks of postnatal life. Although these animals clearly suffer from neurological malfunctions, their smaller yet relatively normal brain does not immediately suggest a myriad of developmental problems nor does it directly expose the origin of the neurological defects. Interestingly, these mice exhibit progressive growth retardation which is also observed in animals deficient for a related PcG gene, *Bmi1*. It has been assumed that *Bmi1* knockout mice are smaller due to systemic *Bmi1* absence. But the nervous system-specific *Ring1b* knockout in fact argues that the sole activity of PcG in brain could determine body size. Such phenomenon is not without precedent. Conditional ablation of *Gli2*, a downstream effector of the developmental morphogen Sonic Hedgehog (*Shh*), in the cerebellum evokes a reduction in the total body weight (Corrales et al., 2006). Additionally, these mice suffer from problems in locomotion like the *Bmi1* and *Ring1b* deficient mice. Notably, *Bmi1* has previously been implicated in Sonic Hedgehog signaling in the cerebellum and in medulloblastoma, a type of brain cancer believed to originate from the granule neuron progenitors (Leung et al., 2004). It is believed that *Bmi1* is induced by *Shh* to prevent expression of the *Ink4a/Arf* genes, which will allow the CGNPs to proliferate (Leung et al., 2004; Bruggeman et al., 2005). A link between *Ring1b* and *Shh* has not yet been demonstrated. However, it is tempting to speculate that such connection exists since there is evidence that cerebellar foliation, which has occurred improperly in *Ring1b* null cerebella, is governed by *Shh* signaling.

Ring1b deficient mice have defects in cerebellar foliation, a *Shh*-guided process

Foliation patterns vary between species and even within different mouse strains (Inouye and Oda, 1980; Cooper et al., 1991; Wahlsten and Anderson, 1991). Since our mice were in a mixed FVB/C57B6 background, the fusion of lobules II and III might have been the

result of combining the foliation patterns of two different strains. However, the control animals never displayed such fusion nor has it been described for any mouse strain, making it highly unlikely that inter-strain differences account for the *Ring1b* phenotype. Presumably, foliation occurs in distinct phases (Corrales et al., 2006). The original smooth surfaced cerebellar anlage is divided by four fissures into the five cardinal lobes. After birth, these lobes separate further into (sub) lobules. In mice, cerebellar development is largely completed within the third postnatal week, but in humans development takes much longer and the EGL persists for approximately fifteen months. Notably, defects in cerebellar foliation in humans are associated with a number of clinical abnormalities underscoring the importance of proper foliation (Demaerel, 2002). The specification of the cardinal lobes and the position of the fissures are determined by an unknown mechanism. But the number and extent of folia that arise are dose-dependently orchestrated by *Shh* induced CGNP proliferation (Dahmane and Altaba, 1999; Wallace, 1999; Wechsler-Reya and Scott, 1999; Corrales et al., 2004; Lewis et al., 2004; Corrales et al., 2006). Since *Shh* is secreted by Purkinje neurons, animals lacking these cells, like the *Lurcher* and *Staggerer* mutants, are impaired in EGL formation and concomitantly in foliation (Sidman et al., 1962; Caddy and Biscoe, 1979; Wetts and Herrup, 1982; Smeyne et al., 1995). *Shh* activates the *D1* and *D2 Cyclins* through the transcriptional induction of *N-Myc*, stimulating progression through the cell cycle (Ciemerych et al., 2002; Kenney et al., 2003; Kenney et al., 2004). Loss of *N-Myc* results in the induction of cell cycle inhibitors *p18^{ink4c}* and *p27^{kip1}* and reduced CGNP proliferation (Knoepfler et al., 2002; Zindy et al., 2006). Curiously, we found that in the absence of *Ring1b*, the tumor suppressor locus *Ink4a/Arf* is derepressed in all areas of the brain including the cerebellum. *p16^{ink4a}*

is a powerful inhibitor of the Cyclin D/Cyclin dependent kinase (CDK) complexes and its ectopic expression might compromise the mitogenic activity of Shh. Additionally, *p19^{arf}* controls proliferation through modulation of *p53* activity and directly regulates the activity of *c-Myc*, an *N-myc* homologue also implicated in cerebellar development, providing yet another path via which *Ring1b* could affect CGNP proliferation and foliation (Datta et al., 2004; Qi et al., 2004; Zindy et al., 2006). Resuming, it would be worthwhile to investigate if a link between Shh signaling and *Ring1b* exists. One could for instance analyze patterns of *Gli1* expression, which is commonly used as readout for active Shh signaling, in the *Ring1b* null cerebellum (Corrales et al., 2004; Corrales et al., 2006). But other mechanisms described to affect foliation and EGL development, like *HGF-Met*, *BDNF-Trk* or *BMP* signaling, and *Math1* or *Zic1* controlled transcription, should be studied as well (Ben Arie et al., 1997; Schwartz et al., 1997; Aruga et al., 1998; Helms et al., 2001; Ieraci et al., 2002; Qin et al., 2006). We recommend these investigations to be conducted in a defined spatial and temporal manner as cerebellar development is highly dynamic. Capturing just one single moment will inevitably lead to clues remaining unnoticed. This might also explain why we so far have only observed minor defects in histology.

Possible role for Engrailed genes in cerebellar proliferation

Position-dependent effects can be anticipated in PcG mutants. PcG proteins are known to repress genes to variable extents at different locations, which is illustrated by the occurrence of ectopic bones in mutant mice, or extremities in *Drosophila*, at fixed places. The most obvious place to expect abnormalities in the *Ring1b* null cerebellum is in the anterior vermis, around the time the precentral fissure normally separates lobules II and III. Intriguingly, in the young

cerebellum, *Ring1b* expression may be locally restricted corroborating spatial specificity. It is interesting that expression of *Engrailed-1* and *2*, two novel *Ring1b* targets that are both implicated in foliation, is also highly localized. *Engrailed-1* (*En-1*) is induced in the region of the cerebellar anlage at the one somite stage whereas *Engrailed-2* (*En-2*) is found slightly later at the five somite stage. Their expression pattern is partially overlapping but after birth, *Engrailed-2* becomes exclusively expressed in the cerebellum. (Davidson et al., 1988; Davis et al., 1988; Davis and Joyner, 1988; McMahon et al., 1992). Mutation in either gene causes a strong reduction in cerebellar size. Specific deletion of *En-1* evokes severe or mild cerebellar defects depending on the mouse strain used (Wurst et al., 1994; Bilovocky et al., 2003). In the mild case, anterior defects in foliation occur together with abnormal projection of mossy fibers (Bilovocky et al., 2003). Removal of *En-2* is associated with defects in the foliation of the vermis and hemispheres and altered parasagittal banding patterns (Millen et al., 1994; Kuemerle et al., 1997; Herrup et al., 2005;). In contrast to *En-1*, the foliation defects of the *En-2* knockout are mostly posterior. Since *Ring1b* represses both *En* genes and the precise mode of action of these genes is not fully understood, it is difficult to predict of which gene the ectopic expression would be more likely to mediate the *Ring1b* foliation defect. Of note, an *En-2* transgenic mouse also has foliation defects and smaller cerebellar size, suggesting that *En-2* upregulation could induce *Ring1b*-like phenotypes (Baader et al., 1998; Baader et al., 1999). Generation of *Ring1b;En-1* or *Ring1b;En-2* compound mutants might unravel whether or not there is a genetic interaction. Furthermore, the *Engrailed* genes have been implicated in other areas of the brain such as in the mesencephalic dopaminergic neurons forming the substantia nigra, and in the serotonergic and noradrenergic neurons of the dorsal raphe nucleus and locus caeruleus,

respectively (Alberi et al., 2004; Simon et al., 2005). Therefore, it would also be interesting to investigate whether these areas are affected in the *Ring1b* knockout brain.

Ink4a/Arf derepression is implicated in *Ring1b* deficient phenotypes

Another obvious question is to what extent derepression of the *Ink4a/Arf* locus is involved in the *Ring1b* phenotypes. Cultured *Ring1b* knockout NSCs undergo a complete growth arrest, the nature of which still awaiting further investigation. This strong effect is rather surprising given the relatively mild *in vivo* phenotype. However, more careful inspection of sites with ongoing neurogenic activity like the SVZ, rostral migratory stream, olfactory bulbs and hippocampus might disclose subtle defects in *in vivo* NSC function. Remarkably, the *Ring1b* null NSC proliferation defect was completely rescued by co-deletion of the *Ink4a/Arf* locus and it would be interesting to test if removal of this locus can also bypass the reduced proliferation and increased differentiation seen in embryonic stem cells. However, it should be taken into consideration that the *Ink4a/Arf* locus is extremely sensitive to stress, especially when cells are transferred from hypoxic *in vivo* conditions to oxygen-rich environments. Hence, the effect of genes controlling *Ink4a/Arf* expression may be somewhat overstated in tissue culture experiments in general. Therefore, it will be essential to cross brain-specific *Ring1b* knockout mice with *Ink4a/Arf* deficient mice, and analyze its relative contribution to the *Ring1b* phenotypes under physiological conditions.

Altogether we have demonstrated that, while early ablation of *Ring1b* from mice is not compatible with embryonic development, nervous-system specific removal of *Ring1b* at later stages of embryogenesis leads to viable animals. However, these mice suffer from progressive growth retardation, a lack

of locomotive control and premature death. These abnormalities may be the result of stem cell self-renewal or cerebellar foliation defects and involve deregulation of the *Ink4a/Arf* and *Engrailed* genes.

Materials and Methods

Mouse breedings and tissue isolation

Ring1b conventional and conditional knockout mice were in an FVB background (Voncken et al., 2003; Van der Stoop and Boutsma et al., 2008). Nestin-Cre (NCre) transgenic mice were originally in a C57/B6 background (Tronche et al., 1999), but they were backcrossed twice into the FVB background. CreER^{T2} transgenic mice (kindly provided by dr. A. Berns) and *Ink4a/Arf* knockout mice (Serrano et al., 1996) were in an FVB background. For timed breedings, presence of a vaginal plug in the morning was considered E0.5. Mice were decapitated or killed with an overdose of CO₂ and tissue was instantly removed. NSCs were isolated and cultured as described before (Bruggeman et al., 2005). They were maintained in defined serum-free NSC medium containing 20 ng/ml EGF and 10 ng/ml bFGF (R&D systems) as neurospheres, or as adherent cultures on poly-L-Ornithine (15 µg/ml) and Laminin (5 µg/ml, both Sigma) coated plates (Conti et al., 2005). All animal experiments were done in agreement with the ethical boards.

Cell culture experiments

For neurosphere cultures, SVZ-derived NSCs were seeded at a density of <1 cell per µl medium into tissue culture treated plastic dishes. For 4-hydroxytamoxifen (4-OHT) induced floxing experiments, 300,000 NSCs were plated onto poly-L-Ornithine and Laminin coated 6 wells plates in NSC medium supplemented with 20 ng/ml EGF and 10 ng/ml bFGF. The following day, 400 nM 4-OHT (Sigma) was added and refreshed every other day. BrdU incorporation experiments were

performed as described before (Bruggeman et al., 2005).

qRT-PCR and Western blot analysis

Quantitative real time PCR (qRT-PCR) and Western blotting were essentially performed as described previously (Bruggeman et al., 2005). Primer sequences were Ring1b-1 sense 5'-AAATGTCTCAGGCTGTGCAG -3', antisense 5'-TTTCCAAGCCATCTGTTATTGCC-3'; Ring1b-2 sense 5'-TCGGTTTTGCGCGGATT-3', antisense 5'-AGTTTTTTCCGACAGGTAGGACACT-3'; Ink4a sense 5'-CGTACCCCGATTACAGTGAT-3', antisense 5'-TTGAGCAGAAGAGCTGCTACGT-3'; Arf sense 5'-GCCGCACCGGAATCCT-3', antisense 5'-TTGAGCAGAAGAGCTGCTACGT-3'; Engrailed1-1 sense 5'-TCGTCCTCTGGTCC ACG-3', antisense 5'-CCTTCTCGTTCTTTTCTTCT TTAGC-3'; Engrailed1-2 sense 5'-AGGCCAG ACTGGTGACAGGT-3', antisense 5'-AGCTCGTGT GCCCAGAGAGT-3'; Engrailed2-1 sense 5'-TGCA CGCGCTATTCTGACC-3', antisense 5'-CTTCTTTG GTTTTCGGGACCT-3'; Engrailed2-2 sense 5'-CTGCCCCGAGGTCCTACAGG-3', antisense 5'-AAGTTGGTGATGCGATGTGG-3'. Loading controls were β -Actin sense 5'-CCTCA TGAAGATCCTGACTGA-3', antisense 5'-TTTAT GTCACGAACAATTTCC-3' and HPRT sense 5'-CTGGTGAAAAGGACCTCTCG-3', antisense 5'-TGAAGTACTCATTATAGTCAAGGGCA-3'.

For Western analysis of Ring1b expression, a mouse monoclonal antibody was used (1:50, a kind gift of dr. Koseki).

Histological analysis

Tissue was formalin fixed, paraffin embedded and processed into 4 μ m thick slices. Antigen was retrieved by boiling in Citrate buffer (100 mM, pH 6.0), and endogenous peroxidase activity was removed by applying 3% H₂O₂ (Merck). Primary antibodies (mouse monoclonal Ring1b, 1:50; Engrail-1, DSHB, 1:500; BrdU, Dako, 1:50; Cleaved Caspase-2, Cell Signaling, 1:50; and rabbit polyclonal Enhb1, kindly provided by dr. A. Joyner, 1:200; Calbindin, Chemicon, 1:400) were added overnight in 5% normal goat serum. Proteins were visualized using secondary biotinylated antibodies in combination with the StreptABCComplex/HRP system according to the manufacturer's protocols (Dako). For BrdU measurements, mice were injected intraperitoneally with 50 mg/kg BrdU two hours prior to sacrifice. The ratio of BrdU positive nuclei per high power field was determined.

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Chapter 5

The highly conserved 5' UTR
of Ring1b harbors
an unusually small
and very efficient IRES

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It is not the strongest of the species that survive, nor the most intelligent, but the one most responsive to change.

Charles Darwin, 'On the Origin of Species by Means of Natural Selection, or the Preservation of Favoured Races in the Struggle for Life'

The highly conserved 5' UTR of Ring1b harbors an unusually small and very efficient IRES

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Ring1b is an essential member of the highly conserved Polycomb group proteins, which orchestrate developmental processes, cell growth and stem cell fate by modifying local chromatin structure. Ring1b was found to be the E3 ligase that monoubiquitinates histone H2A, which adds a new level of chromatin modification to Polycomb group proteins. Here we report that Ring1b belongs to the exclusive group of proteins that for their translation depend on a stable 5' UTR sequence in their mRNA known as an Internal Ribosome Entry Site (IRES). In cell transfection assays the Ring1b IRES confers significantly higher expression levels of Ring1b than a Ring1b cDNA without the IRES. Also, dual luciferase assays show strong activity of the Ring1b IRES. Although our findings indicate Ring1b can be translated under conditions where cap-dependent translation is impaired, we found the Ring1b IRES to be cap-dependent. This raises the possibility that translational control of Ring1b is a multi-layered process and that translation of Ring1b needs to be maintained under varying conditions, which is in line with its essential role as an E3 ligase for monoubiquitination of histone H2A in the PRC1 Polycomb protein complex.

Introduction

The E3 ubiquitin ligase Ring1b is a member of the highly conserved Polycomb group (PcG) protein family, which act as multimeric chromatin modifying complexes. Recent genome-wide analyses by our group and others clearly demonstrated that PcG protein complexes act on large areas of the genome, thereby maintaining selectivity to genes related to growth and development (Tolhuis et al., 2006; Schwartz et al., 2006; Lee et al., 2006; Boyer et al., 2006; Bracken et al., 2006; Endoh et al., 2008). Importantly, PcG protein complexes occupy genes involved in initiation of differentiation in embryonic stem cells (Boyer et al., 2006), and co-occupy a significant subset of genes with embryonic stem cell regulators Nanog, SOX2 and Oct4 (Lee et al., 2006). Recently, it was demonstrated that upon induction of differentiation by GATA6, Ring1b target genes in mouse ES cells are derepressed and Ring1b localization to target loci is decreased (Endoh

et al., 2008). These observations are consistent with our own observations, showing that genetic inactivation of PcG proteins in mouse ES cells facilitated a differentiation-prone phenotype (van der Stoop et al., 2008).

Also, PcG proteins have been suggested to be involved in X-chromosome silencing in female cells. Initial reports suggested that the PcG proteins Eed and EZH2 are involved in initiation of X-chromosome inactivation since they are enriched on the inactive X-chromosome during early stages of inactivation (Chadwick and Willard, 2003; Mak et al., 2002; Silva et al., 2003; Hernandez-Munoz et al., 2005). Then it was shown that mouse embryos deficient for the PcG protein Eed are capable of initiating and maintaining X-chromosome inactivation (Kalantry and Magnuson, 2006; Schoeftner et al., 2006). Instead, it was proposed that PcG proteins might protect the inactive X-chromosome from reactivation as a result of differentiation (Kalantry et al., 2006). Recently, a 1.6 kb non-coding RNA sequence termed RepA was

identified in the inactive X-chromosome that directly binds to Polycomb group protein EZH2 (Zhao et al., 2008). RepA deletion was found to abolish Xist induction and trimethylation on lysine 27 of histone H3 of the X-chromosome, indicating Polycomb group proteins do play a pivotal role in initiation of X-inactivation. Composition of PcG complexes varies among cell types and in time, but in general one can distinguish at least two biochemically distinct complexes. Polycomb Repressive Complex 2 (PRC2), also termed the initiation complex, harbors Eed, EZH1 and EZH2 (Sewalt et al., 1998; van Lohuizen et al., 1998). The other complex is also termed maintenance complex or PRC1, and consists of Ring1b/Rnf2, Bmi1, M33, MPh1, RYBP and homologues, but also transcription factors such as YY1 and E2F6 (Trimarchi et al., 2001; Levine et al., 2002). Recently, several enzymatic functions have been linked to Polycomb complexes, among which are histone deacetylation (Tie et al., 2001; van der Vlag and Otte, 1999; Xia et al., 2003), histone methylation (Cao and Zhang, 2004; Cao et al., 2002; Kuzmichev et al., 2002) and histone ubiquitination (Fang et al., 2004; Wang et al., 2004). It is thought that extensive modification of histone tails determines local chromatin structure, either by influencing chromatin structure directly or by recruitment of modifying factors, such as PcG proteins. Ring1b was found to be responsible for the long-known monoubiquitination of histone H2A at K116 or K119 (Wang et al., 2004). It was proposed that this chromatin mark may be involved in transcriptional repression by Polycomb proteins (Wang et al., 2004; Cao et al., 2005). Experimental evidence to support this idea came when loss of Ring1b mediated monoubiquitination of H2A was linked to the release of poised RNA polymerase II and subsequent derepression of target genes (Stock et al., 2007). This finding may provide an explanation for the mechanism of gene repression by PcG proteins via histone modification. A more recent association of

the H2A monoubiquitin mark with repression is the finding that in early embryos, the paternally imprinted Kcnq1 cluster organizes a higher-order repressive nuclear compartment, characterized by the local presence of the non-coding RNA (ncRNA) Kcnq1ot1, both PRC1 and PRC2 proteins, and the repressive histone mark H3K27me3 (Terranova et al., 2008). In addition, recent findings in *Drosophila melanogaster* showed that H2A monoubiquitination by Ring1b homolog dRING requires dKDM2, a demethylase that normally mediates H3K36me2 demethylation, an effect that is associated with repression of target genes (Lagarou et al., 2008).

Ring1b is the only member of PRC1 that seems to be essential for life, since *Ring1b* knockout mice die during gestation after a gastrulation arrest (Voncken et al., 2003). This is in contrast to the relatively mild phenotypes of knockout mice of other PRC1 members, like *Bmi1* (van der Lugt et al., 1994), *Mel18* (Akasaka et al., 1996), *M33* (Core et al., 1997) and *MPh1* (Takahara et al., 1997), which exhibit developmental defects that can in part be related to deregulation of *Hox* genes. The Ring1b interacting protein Bmi1 also has an established role in stem cells of both the haematopoietic system (Iwama et al., 2004; Lessard and Sauvageau, 2003) as well as the CNS (Leung et al., 2004; Molofsky et al., 2003), linking PcG complexes to stem cell self-renewal (reviewed in Valk-Lingbeek et al., 2004).

To date, little is known about the regulation of PcG proteins via inhibiting factors, stimulating factors or on transcriptional, translational or post-translational levels. Nonetheless, it is known that hierarchical recruitment of PcG members is crucial in many situations, suggesting there must be extensive regulation of PcG protein levels. Especially data on post-transcriptional regulation of PcG protein levels is limited, though our previous work revealed the cell-cycle dependent phosphorylation of Bmi1, which we found to correlate with its

dissociation from chromatin (Voncken et al., 1999). Also, we recently showed Bmi1 can be monoubiquitinated, as a part of the E3 ubiquitin ligase complex consisting of Spop and Cullin3 that together ubiquitinate variant histone MacroH2A (Hernandez-Munoz et al., 2005). Monoubiquitination of PcG members could have a signaling function, for example related to its localization, providing a post-translational level of regulation. Here, we report a novel mechanism through which Ring1b is regulated. We identified a functional IRES in the 5' UTR of the Ring1b transcript and demonstrate strong activity of the IRES in several experimental settings, which indicates Ring1b protein levels are (also) regulated by this alternative translation initiation mode.

IRESEs represent highly structured 5' UTR sequences capable of recruiting the translational machinery independent of a cap site. IRES-dependent translation is relatively rare; the vast majority of all eukaryotic proteins are translated via the well-characterized mechanism of cap-dependent translation. This mechanism is dependent on binding of the cap-binding subunit eIF4E of the eIF4F initiation complex to the 5' m⁷guanosine cap of the mature RNA transcript. The mechanism of recruitment of the initiation complex by an IRES is largely unknown, although several cellular proteins, termed ITAFs for IRES TransActing Factors (i.e. PTB, hnRNP A1 and several initiation factors), have been found to interact with IRESEs (Bonnal et al., 2004; Lopez de Quinto et al., 2001; Pickering et al., 2003). Most IRES-dependent translation does not need functional eIF4E or the eIF4E-binding domain of eIF4G, which are the main targets for inhibition of cap-dependent translation. Taking advantage of this, several conditions are now known which favor IRES-dependent translation over cap-dependent translation. For example, oxidative stress induces the IRES activity of VEGF (Stein et al., 1998) and Hif1 α (Lang et al., 2002), amino acid starvation induces IRES-mediated translation of cat-1 (Fernandez et al., 2001),

and the c-myc IRES is specifically active during apoptosis (Stoneley et al., 2000), genotoxic stress (Subkhankulova et al., 2001) as well as G₂M transition (Kim et al., 2003). Infection with certain viruses, such as picornaviruses, can also result in impaired translational activity of the host cell. This is a result of cleavage of the cap-binding domain of eIF4G by viral proteases 2A and 3B (Hambidge and Sarnow, 1992; Perales et al., 2003). Since viral proteins themselves are often translated via IRESEs, expression of these proteases favors viral protein translation and dramatically decreases translational activity of the host cell. Viral IRESEs are widely used as tools in molecular and cellular biology, providing a means to translate two or more different proteins from a single transcript.

The here described finding that Ring1b harbors a highly active IRES in its 5' UTR is, to our knowledge, the first time that this alternative translational mechanism is implicated in the regulation of Polycomb group proteins. This adds a new mechanism by which PcG protein levels are regulated in the cell.

Results

The Ring1b IRES is highly conserved between mammals

The *Ring1b* gene is conserved throughout evolution and homologues can be found in mammals, but also for example fruit fly (*Drosophila melanogaster*), zebra fish (*Danio rerio*) and frog (*Xenopus tropicanus*). The mammalian *Ring1b* gene has an unusual structure, which has not been observed in non-mammals. In mice, the first exon is followed by a 22 kb intron, leaving approximately 7.5 kb for the 6 remaining exons (figure 1A). The ORF starts in the second exon and is 1011 bp long, resulting in a 336 aa peptide which can be visualized as a 42 kDa protein on Western blots. Ring1b is ubiquitously expressed *in vivo* in the mouse embryo (Mar Lorente et al., 2000) and highly expressed in a wide range of human,

Figure 1

A

B

hsapiens	AGTCTCTCATGAATATTGAGCGGCCCTGTTGTATTTCCC	40
mmusculus	AGTCTCTCATGAATATTGAGCGGCCCTGTTGTATTTCCC	40
rnorvegicus	AGTCTCTCATGAATATTGAGCGGCCCTGTTGTATTTCCC	40
sscrofa	GCTCTCTCATGAATATTGAGCGGCCCTGTTGTATTTCCC	40
Consensus	gtctctcatgaatattgagcggccctggtgtattccc	
hsapiens	GAGCTCCATTGCGGAAGCCTGAGCTCGCCATATTGTGCGG	80
mmusculus	GAGCTCCATTGCGGAAGCCTGAGCTCGCCATATTGTGCGG	80
rnorvegicus	GAGCTCCATTGCGGAAGCCTGAGCTCGCCATATTGTGCGG	80
sscrofa	GAGCTCCATTGCGGAAGCCTGAGCTCGCCATATTGTGCGG	80
Consensus	gagctccattgcggaagcctgagctcgccatattgtgcgg	
hsapiens	CGGCCCCGGCGTCCCGCCACCTCATACAGACTCTTCT	120
mmusculus	CGGCCCCGGCGTTC.....ATCTCGAGTCTCGCT	111
rnorvegicus	CGGCCCCGGCGTTC.....ATCTCGAGTCTCGCT	111
sscrofa	CGGCCCCGGCGTTCCTCCCGTCTCTCACT	120
Consensus	cggc cggcg g t c g g t c t	
hsapiens	CCGGCCCGCCAGCGGACCCCTGGCTGGGGCGGAGCC	160
mmusculus	CCGGCCCGCCAGCGGACCCCGGCTGGGGCGGAGCC	151
rnorvegicus	CCGGCCCGCCAGCGGACCCCGGCTGGGGCGGAGCC	151
sscrofa	CCGGCCCGCCAGCGGACCCCGGCTGGGGCGGAGCC	160
Consensus	ccggcc c gccagcg a ccc gg ctggggc gggagcc	
hsapiens	GCAATC	166
mmusculus	GAAATC	157
rnorvegicus	GCAATC	157

Figure 1. *Ring1b* has a remarkable genomic structure

(A) The genomic structure of *Ring1b* is depicted in the upper pane, the approximate sizes of exons in the middle pane and introns in the lower pane, as well as the translational start and stop codons. Exon 7 greatly varies in length, sometimes measuring up to 3,5 kb.

(B) Apart from a 12 nucleotide stretch in the middle, which is only seen in human and pig *Ring1b*, IRESes of different mammals are virtually identical. The exact mouse sequence depicted, comprising the entire IRES until the translational start, is used in all our assays.

rat and mouse cell types tested, both primary cells and tumor cell lines (data not shown). The genomic sequence in which the first exon is located is very GC-rich, with >80% GC content stretching over several kbs, indicative of a CpG island acting as a promoter. This first exon is very highly conserved between mammalian

species, which is unusual for a noncoding sequence (figure 1B).

ESTs in the online databases seem to indicate there are different transcription start sites in this area, sometimes resulting in a transcript with a large 5' UTR and sometimes in a transcript with a much smaller one. To

Figure 1 (continued)

(C) A 5' RLM-RACE was performed to determine the main transcriptional start. In lane 5 a 100 bp marker was loaded, with the most prominent band being 600 bp. In ES cells (lane 1), primary MEFs (lane 2) and 293 cells (lane 3) the most abundant fragment is approximately 380 bp long. This suggests a transcriptional start at approximately 154 bp 5' of the 3' splice site of the first exon, which was verified after sequencing the fragments. Lane 4 shows an internal control PCR, using the same 3' Ring1b inner primer, but with a Ring1b 5' primer instead of an adapter primer. The Ring1b 5' primer is located downstream of the translational start, so this PCR serves as an internal control for RNA quality and primer specificity.

determine the predominant transcription start site we performed a 5' RLM-RACE on capped RNA from mouse embryonic stem cells (ES), primary mouse embryonic fibroblasts (MEF) and 293 cells. We found that the majority of the transcripts in all three cell types start at position -154 of the known 3' splice site of the first exon (figure 1C). Since the translational start is located in the second exon, 2 nucleotides downstream of the 5' splice site of the second exon, this results in a 5' UTR of 156 bp. The 5' UTR has a 70.2% GC content and harbors an out-of-frame alternative start codon. The first in-frame stop codon is found in the second exon, 34 nucleotides downstream of the translational start codon. We cannot rule out that this small ORF plays a regulatory role in Ring1b translation. However, it is unlikely that this ORF is translated efficiently, since it has a very poor Kozak consensus sequence as opposed to the very good Kozak consensus sequence of the Ring1b translational start

codon. Moreover, Ring1b constructs lacking the alternative start codon and used in the same experiments described in this paper, gave the same results in our assays (data not shown).

The high degree of sequence conservation suggests there are regulatory sequences located in the Ring1b 5' UTR. UTRscan, an online source for predicting UTR structures and domains, finds a putative Internal Ribosome Entry Site (IRES) in the 5' UTR of Ring1b, consisting of 91 nucleotides directly 5' of the translational start codon.

The Ring1b 5' UTR contains a functional IRES sequence

We cloned the 154 bp Ring1b 5' UTR harboring the putative IRES, based on the results with the RLM-RACE, in front of the Ring1b translational start codon. This resulted in a Ring1b cDNA sequence that also exists as an RNA transcript *in vivo*, apart from the C-terminal flag tag to discriminate it from endogenous Ring1b. As a positive control, we took along N-terminal myc-tagged Ring1b (figure 2A). Expression of Ring1b was readily observed from different vectors, after transient transfection as well as after retroviral infection (figure 2B). Presence of the IRES seemed to increase Ring1b protein levels (figure 2B, lane 3 versus lane 2). Since our construct consist of the entire, most common 5' UTR, it is slightly larger than the predicted IRES (154 bp versus 91 bp) and harbors the start codon of the small ORF that terminates in the second exon, spanning 186 bp in total.

To rule out a possible effect of this small ORF on translation efficiency, we also tested a construct that consisted of only the Ring1b IRES; there was no significant difference in the results (data not shown). Also, it is unlikely that the differences in Ring1b protein levels are due to differences in transcription efficiency of the plasmids, since we performed quantitative real-time PCR on RNA from these same cells, showing Ring1b RNA levels (both endogenous and transfected were measured together) were

Figure 2. Expression of Ring1b is influenced by the 5' UTR

(A) An overview of the Ring1b IRES validation constructs used in our assays, depicting the position of the CMV promoter, the flag and myc tags, the Ring1b ORF, the 140 bp hairpin structure (hp), the Ring1b IRES, the SV40 polyadenylation signal and the MSCV-Puro LTRs.

(B) Numbers in this Western blot correspond to the constructs in figure 2A. All constructs were based on pcDNA3.1 and expression analyses were done with transient transfections in 293 cells, except construct #4, which was based on the retroviral vector MSCV-Puro and was infected in primary MEFs. 50 ng of EGFP-expressing plasmid was cotransfected to check whether transfection was comparably efficient. One can clearly appreciate the increased exogenous Ring1b protein levels relative to tubulin when the 5' UTR is present, as well as the decreased protein levels when the stem-loop is cloned in front of the 5' UTR, and the absence of exogenous Ring1b protein when the CMV promoter was removed from the vector.

(C) Ring1b RNA levels (both endogenous and transfected measured together) in the same cell populations as in figure 2B were very much alike, ruling out that the differences in protein levels could be accounted for by differences in transcription efficiency. RNA levels in this graph were typical for several independent experiments and normalized against beta-actin; normalization against Hprt gave the same result. Ring1b (1) and Ring1b (2) indicate different primer sets. Bar numbers correspond to figure 2A.

Figure 3. The Ring1b 5' UTR harbors IRES activity in expression constructs

(A) In this overview of the dual luciferase constructs used in the assays below, the CMV promoter, the Renilla (RLuc) and Firefly (FLuc) luciferase ORFs, the IRESes of EMCV (E.IRES) and Ring1b (R.IRES) and the SV40 polyadenylation signal are depicted.

The diagrams show activity assays of the cellular IRESes of Ring1b (pLRL), PDGF (pLPL), VEGF (pLVL), c-myc (pLML) and the viral IRES of EMCV (pLEL). The assays were done in COS7 (B), 293 (C), U2OS (D), HACAT (E) and HeLa (F) cells. On the y-axis, the relative activity of the IRES is depicted by dividing the Firefly counts of the sample over the Firefly counts of the empty vector (pLL, which has no IRES between both luciferase ORFs). All samples are corrected for their relative Renilla counts, since Renilla luciferase translation is cap-dependent and generally a readout of transfection efficiency. All experiments were done in duplo and repeated several times. The assays show the varying activity of the IRESes in different cell types. Whereas the EMCV IRES is known to be highly active in most cell types, cellular IRESes are generally much less active. Nevertheless, the Ring1b IRES is as active as the EMCV IRES in COS7 and HeLa cells, and in every cell type the most active IRES among the cellular IRESes.

very much alike in all transfections (figure 2C). To further explore the putative IRES function of the Ring1b 5' UTR, we also made a construct with a small (about 140 bp) synthetic stem-loop-stem structure 3' of the transcription start site

but 5' of the IRES (figure 2A, construct nr. 1). This hairpin loop, consisting of 8 HindIII restriction sites followed by 10 non-complementary nucleotides and again 8 HindIII restriction sites, is expected to make the cap-dependent 40S

Figure 4. The Ring1b 5' UTR does not have cryptic promoter activity

(A) To test cryptic promoter activity of the Ring1b 5' UTR, the Ring1b and EMCV IRES dual luciferase constructs were cloned into a pcDNA3.1 vector without CMV promoter. The constructs correspond to the constructs depicted in figure 3A, with Renilla luciferase 5' of the IRES and Firefly luciferase 3' of the IRES. The y-axis shows the absolute counts of Firefly luciferase (cap-dependent) and Renilla luciferase (IRES-dependent) after transient transfection in COS7 cells. In the constructs without promoter, no mRNA is produced, therefore no translation occurs and no luciferase activity can be measured, indicating the Ring1b 5' UTR does not contain a cryptic promoter. pEGFP vector was cotransfected in COS7 cells and showed equal fluorescence in every transfection.

In a bicistronic construct with the EGFP ORF downstream of the Ring1b IRES we could clearly detect EGFP fluorescence with fluorescent microscopy (B, Ring1b IRES only) as well as EGFP protein on Western blot (C). The Ring1b IRES (IRES^R) seems to give a slightly higher expression than the EMCV IRES (IRES^E), but we did observe some variation in this in our different experiments. On average we would say the EGFP levels were equal. pEGFP served as a positive control, empty pcDNA3.1 as a negative control, and tubulin as a loading control.

scanning subunit of the ribosome dissociate from the transcript, since the eIF4A helicase subunit of the eIF4F translation initiation complex is unable to unwind this highly stable hairpin loop (Hernandez-Munoz et al., 2003). Thus, in this construct, translation of Ring1b is supposed to be exclusively mediated by non-cap-dependent mechanisms. Indeed we could show Ring1b protein in the presence of the hairpin loop, albeit slightly less than without it (figure 2B, lane 3 versus lane 1). This could be explained by assuming the stem-loop-stem structure causes at least partial disruption of the IRES secondary structure

The Ring1b IRES is highly active in many cell lines

IRESes have the characteristic feature to be able to recruit the translational machinery independent of its position in a transcript,

allowing translation of downstream ORFs. To test the Ring1b IRES in this setting, we cloned it in between a Renilla luciferase ORF and a Firefly luciferase ORF (figure 3A). The resulting construct, pLRL, was expressed from a CMV promoter. We used identical constructs with the cellular IRESes of c-myc (pLML), VEGF (pLVL), PDGF (pLPL) and the viral IRES from the encephalomyocarditis virus (pLEL) as controls. Expression of Renilla is exclusively cap-dependent and is supposed to vary only with varying transfection efficiencies. Therefore, all Firefly readouts were normalized to Renilla luciferase levels. Firefly luciferase activity was the readout of the experiment since it is dependent on the ability of the IRES to recruit the translational machinery. Firefly activity of experimental constructs was divided by the Firefly activity of the construct without IRES (pLL).

Figure 5. The Ring1b 5' UTR is sensitive to 2A protease activity

(A) Western blot showing cleaved eIF4GI isoforms upon transfection of viral protease 2A (lane 1) in 293 cells, whereas eIF4GI remains intact in the absence of 2A (lane 2). Molecular weight markers are indicated. This Western blot was done on the same lysates we used in one of the experiments in figure 4B. Results are representative of three independent experiments.

The graphs depict the absolute counts of Renilla and Firefly luciferase activity (B) and the ratio of the Firefly luciferase counts over the Renilla luciferase counts (C). Ring1b IRES-dependent Firefly luciferase is clearly affected by the protease to a similar extent as the cap-dependent Renilla luciferase, showing no difference in their relative activity and therefore no difference in the ratio. As a control, in the presence of 2A protease the EMCV IRES-dependent Firefly luciferase is equally active whereas the cap-dependent Renilla luciferase activity is reduced over two-fold, resulting in an over two-fold increase in the ratio. This experiment clearly shows the remarkable apparent cap-dependency of the Ring1b IRES. pIND-2A, the protease-expressing plasmid, was co-transfected at 5 µg per transfection, without muristerone-A induction. Experiments were performed four times. Transfection efficiencies were checked to be comparable between samples by cotransfection of 50 ng EGFP-expressing plasmid.

In this well-established dual-luciferase assay we compared the activity of the Ring1b IRES by performing transient transfections in COS7, 293, U₂OS, HACAT and HeLa cells. In all cell types the Ring1b IRES was equally or more active than the control cellular IRESes (figure 3B - F). The EMCV IRES was, with a relative activity between twofold and tenfold over the cellular IRESes, the most active IRES in all but COS7 cells. COS7 cells were the only cell type where a cellular IRES, the Ring1b IRES, was as active as the EMCV IRES. We reproducibly observed that in HeLa cells the EMCV IRES was much less active than in other cell types.

The Ring1b 5' UTR does not contain a cryptic promoter

Several recent publications state it is hard to discern IRES activity from cryptic promoter activity in GC-rich leader sequences (Bert et

al., 2006; Van Eden et al., 2004). To exclude this possibility, we cut out the CMV promoter from our Ring1b expression constructs (figure 2A, construct nr. 5) and tested these for Ring1b expression. As expected, no Ring1b protein could be detected on Western blot (figure 2B, lane 5). In addition, we cloned the dual luciferase construct including the Ring1b and, as a control, EMCV IRES in a promoterless pcDNA3.1 construct to test cryptic promoter activity (figure 3A, construct 3). As in our experiment with the promoterless Ring1b construct, which gave no Ring1b expression, the promoterless dual luciferase constructs gave neither Renilla luciferase activity nor Firefly luciferase activity (figure 4A).

Finally, we analyzed the Ring1b IRES and the EMCV IRES in a bicistronic construct with an EGFP coding sequence downstream of the IRES, instead of Firefly luciferase. EGFP fluorescence

Figure 6. Mouse and human Ring1b 5' UTRs show a striking structural resemblance

(A) Secondary structure prediction of the Ring1b IRES of human and mouse origin, showing a striking structure similarity. The first nucleotide is indicated with a black circle around it, the last triplet is the translational start. Loop numbers are indicated with filled black circles. In mutant IRES*1 and IRES*2 the indicated cytosines are replaced by adenines, creating mismatches. In mutant IRES*3 the indicated uracil is replaced by a cytosine, creating a matching nucleotide and therefore stabilizing the structure. Mutant IRES*4 lacks the entire second loop.

(B) Luciferase assays show the remaining activity of the mutant IRESes and the stabilized activity in case of the matching mutation. The same construct as in figure 3a, construct number 1, was used, but with the mutations introduced. The way of interpreting the graph is identical to figure 3b-f. The mismatch point mutations almost completely abolish the IRES activity, whereas IRES*3 is, as expected, not affected by its stabilizing point mutation. Surprisingly, the IRES lacking the entire second loop still has some residual activity, indicating the relative importance of the remaining structure.

(figure 4B) as well as EGFP expression (figure 4C) could readily be observed upon transient transfection of the bicistronic constructs, indicating the Ring1b IRES preceding a marker

gene could in principle be used as a tool in biological assays to verify transduction efficiency or as a much smaller alternative to viral IRESes.

Ring1b IRES needs intact eIF4G to function properly

Next, we tested the sensitivity of the Ring1b IRES to viral protease 2A. This protease, isolated from picornaviruses, cleaves off the eIF4E binding domain of eIF4G. Since the binding of eIF4E to the cap site and subsequently to eIF4G is a key step in translation initiation, cap-dependent translation efficiency is greatly reduced in the presence of protease 2A. However, since transcripts harboring an IRES generally do not need a cap site for translation initiation, IRES-dependent translation could still occur. In our assay with the dual luciferase construct, this should result in reduced Renilla luciferase activity but not in reduced Firefly luciferase activity. This is not what we observed upon cotransfection of an inducible protease 2A encoding plasmid, which results in cleaved eIF4G (figure 5A). IRES-dependent Firefly luciferase expression is clearly decreased to a similar extent as cap-dependent Renilla luciferase activity. So whereas the absolute counts dropped, the ratio for both experiments remained equal (figure 5B). The EMCV IRES more than doubles its ratio of IRES-dependent translation over cap-dependent translation with 2A present. This indicates that the Ring1b IRES needs intact eIF4G to function properly.

Effects of point mutations in the Ring1b IRES correspond to secondary structure prediction

Next, we analyzed the predicted structure of the 91 bp Ring1b IRES. Although there is no general consensus sequence or structure for IRESes, to know the predicted structure could be of interest to make specific mutants to further validate the IRES or to understand which motifs are important. We used the secondary structure prediction software RNAdraw (Matzura and Wennborg, 1996) to analyze the IRES structure of human and mouse origin. In both species, the structure is highly similar and contains three distinct loops (figure 6A). We designed mutations that should result in either loss of

IRES function or should be neutral, based on the predicted structure.

IRES*1 and IRES*2 have point mutations in the first and the third stem, respectively, which should, according to RNAdraw, favor a secondary structure very different from the predicted wildtype structure. IRES*3 is predicted to have an even more stable wildtype structure, since a nucleotide introducing a mismatch in the third stem is replaced by a complementary nucleotide. IRES*4 lacks the entire second stem-loop. As expected, the disrupting point mutations almost completely abolished IRES activity, whereas the point mutation strengthening the structure had no significant effect (figure 6B). Surprisingly, deleting the entire second stem-loop didn't completely abolish IRES activity, suggesting the remaining structure is sufficient to give at least partial IRES function.

Discussion

In this publication we demonstrate the first Polycomb group protein that harbors an IRES in its 5' UTR, providing a new level of post-transcriptional regulation of a PcG protein complex member. Being only 91 bp in length, the IRES is unusually small yet more active than several other cellular IRESes known to date. Ring1b seems to be largely dependent on the presence of the IRES for its translation, as Ring1b translation is clearly impaired when the IRES is not present. Cryptic promoter activity was excluded by showing lack of expression of downstream ORFs in promoterless constructs. Finally, we show with disrupting and stabilizing point mutations in the IRES sequence that the software-predicted secondary structure is likely to be correct and functional with regard to the IRES activity. Confirming such a regulatory function, the secondary structure is strikingly homologous between mouse and human. Remarkably, the Ring1b IRES seems to be sensitive to the absence of a translation

initiation complex, since it is much less active when the eIF4E binding domain is cleaved off eIF4G by viral protease 2A. This event prevents the formation of an initiation complex and therefore inhibits translational start. Under these conditions, IRES-dependent translation could be the only mechanism for any mRNA to be translated. This observation suggests the Ring1b IRES is to some extent dependent on cap-dependent translational mechanisms. The reason for this could be indirect, in that the Ring1b IRES needs a trans-acting factor that is translated in a cap-dependent manner, but it is currently unclear which factor this could be. Another possible explanation comes from ribosome shunting, a discontinuous scanning mechanism that in result resembles IRES activity but requires a m⁷guanosine cap. However, shunting requires shunt donor and acceptor sequences to enable scanning ribosomes to bypass mRNA sequences in the 5' UTR, none of which were found in the Ring1b 5' UTR. Of note, cap-dependent IRES translation is not unprecedented: the eIF4GI-variant of eIF4G itself was recently found to harbor a cap-dependent IRES, with no clear shunt donor and acceptor sequences (Byrd et al., 2005). Taken together, this suggests that the IRESes of eIF4G and Ring1b may represent a special subclass of IRES sequences which in part require cap-translation initiation factors for optimal translation.

We speculate that the reason why Ring1b mRNA harbors an IRES, is because Ring1b protein needs to be present in a cell under all circumstances. After testing many primary cell types, tumor cell lines and live tissue, we found no cell type with low levels or lack of Ring1b protein (unpublished observations). All cell types tested have readily detectable levels of Ring1b protein. Also, our previous work indicated that Ring1b knockout mice die early in gestation, with severe defects in the mesoderm and deregulated hox gene expression (Voncken et al., 2003), suggesting a vital function for Ring1b in early embryo development. The

presence of an IRES might ensure translation of Ring1b in the early embryo under stress conditions such as low oxygen or limited amino acid availability.

An alternative possible explanation comes from differentiation studies with mouse embryonic stem (ES) cells. Recent genome-wide studies show that PcG proteins are critically involved in keeping differentiation-related genes silent in ES cells (Endoh et al., 2008; Boyer et al., 2006; Lee et al., 2006). Since Ring1b seems to play an essential role in PRC1 and early embryo survival (Voncken et al., 2003), lack of Ring1b might compromise PRC1 function, leading to unregulated differentiation of stem cells, possibly resulting in cell death. This stem cell based explanation is further supported by the many reports that implicate Bmi1, a Ring1b interaction partner and regulator of Ring1b's ubiquitin E3 ligase activity, in stem cell self-renewal (Iwama et al., 2004; Lessard and Sauvageau, 2003; Leung et al., 2004; Molofsky et al., 2003). Intriguingly, Terranova *et al* reported that Ring1b appears to be critically involved in directing monoallelic silencing of the (paternal) *Kcnq1* cluster *cis* genes in extraembryonic tissues, probably by genomic compaction of the locus (Terranova et al., 2008). They report loss of silencing in Ring1b null trophoectoderm cells, and relate this to the repressive histone mark H3K27me3 and monoubiquitination of H2A. This finding, together with the many reports of the involvement of PRC2 members in the maintenance of stem cell identity, might point to a general role of Ring1b in early development: a critical core member of PRC2, involved in higher-order chromatin silencing mechanisms during early development.

The apparent permanent need for Ring1b could be related to its known enzymatic function at the heart of PRC1, acting as a E3 ubiquitin ligase for monoubiquitination of histone H2A. We and others have shown by protein crystallography, that Ring1b and Bmi1 strongly interact via their RING finger

domains as well as the Ring1b N-terminal tail, which wraps around Bmi1 (Buchwald et al., 2006; Li et al., 2006). Together these proteins form an active E3 ligase heterodimer, capable of monoubiquitinating H2A more efficiently than Ring1b alone. Truncated versions of both proteins, including the RING finger domains and small adjacent sequences, were shown to be sufficient for heterodimerization, catalytic activity and substrate recognition (Buchwald et al., 2006), which leaves more than half of each protein for interaction with other proteins. Since PcG proteins act in large multimeric complexes, it is likely PcG members other than Bmi1 also provide a layer of regulation of Ring1b's E3 ligase activity. This is supported by the finding that an *in vitro* translated PRC1 containing Ring1a, Ring1b, Bmi1 and Pc3 leads to higher levels of uH2A than Ring1b alone (Cao et al., 2005), suggesting a synergistic effect of PRC1 on H2A monoubiquitination. Importantly, only lack of Ring1b abolishes H2A monoubiquitination (Wang et al., 2004), indicating PRC1 without Ring1b cannot monoubiquitinate H2A. Indeed, loss of Ring1b results in rapid deubiquitination of H2A and apoptosis (Endoh et al., 2008, Van der Stoop and Boutsma, unpublished observations). There has been a long-standing correlation between decreased levels of uH2A and apoptosis (Mimnaugh et al., 2001; Marushige and Marushige, 1995), which might point to the idea that a minimal level of uH2A is necessary for cell survival. This again supports the idea that Ring1b protein needs to be present under all circumstances, a requirement that could possibly be met by the presence of the newly found IRES.

Another possibility is that the IRES in the 5' UTR increases the stability of the mRNA. This is a common phenomenon to highly structured RNA, both with specific sequences in the 5' untranslated region as well as in the 3' untranslated region (Suay et al., 2005). Indeed, the Ring1b 3' UTR can be very large, fragments of up to 3.5 kb were found in the online databases,

and its sequence is remarkably conserved between mouse and human, just as its 5' UTR. Increasing Ring1b mRNA stability in this way could point to a mechanism through which the presence of Ring1b protein is secured by very different means than by maintaining translation, namely by providing a pool of Ring1b mRNA when general transcription is halted.

Taken together, we believe it is very likely that Ring1b protein needs to be present under virtually all circumstances. This idea is now strongly supported by the fact that Ring1b can be translated via its IRES under conditions when traditional cap-dependent translation is impaired, but also by the possibility that the presence of highly structured UTRs in the Ring1b mRNA contribute to its stability and therefore provide a stock of Ring1b mRNA when transcription is impaired. Further experiments on the exact events following the disappearance of Ring1b protein from a cell, preferably via a controlled experimental setup using conditional genetic inactivation, should give more insights into the role of Ring1b in the cell.

Materials and Methods

Plasmid construction

The pLL, pLML, pLVL, pLPL and pLEL vectors were a kind gift from Orna Elroy-Stein and have been described previously (Gerlitz et al., 2002). pIND-2A was a kind gift from Chaim Kahana and has also been described earlier (Goldstaub et al., 2000). The Ring1b IRES was obtained by PCR from Image Clone BG076521, using primers mRing1b-BgIII-IRES-fw (5-GAAGATCTAGTCTCTCATGAATATTGAGCG-3) and mRing1b-exon1-rev (5-GGGCTGGGGCAGGAGCCGAA-3). This fragment was cloned blunt in the EcoRV site in between both Luciferase coding sequences of pLL, resulting in pLRL. A 5' part of the Ring1b cDNA, but 3' of the IRES, was then obtained by PCR using primers mRing1b-exon2-fw (5-GGGCTGGGGCAGGAGCCGAAATGT

CTCAGGCTGTGCAGAC-3) and mRing1b-ApaI-rev (5-GAAGCGGGCCCCGAGTAACA-3). This fragment was combined with the PCR IRES fragment and because of their 20 base pair overlap, a new fragment was obtained by PCR containing the first four exons, including the IRES in the first exon. This fragment was cloned into Ring1b expression constructs (see below) using BglIII and ApaI, resulting in expression constructs harboring the Ring1b IRES. pcDNA3.1 (Invitrogen) and MSCVPuro (Clontech) based Ring1b expression constructs were made by cutting both vectors with BglIII and XhoI and cloning in a Ring1b cDNA with a BglIII site immediately upstream of the translational start and an XhoI site immediately downstream of the translational stop. A C-terminal flag tag was introduced in both constructs by ligation of an NcoI-HpaI PCR-fragment (obtained with primers Ring1b-NcoI-fw (5-GAACAAACCCATGGAACCTTATTATG-3) and Ring1b-flag-stop-XhE-rev (5-CACCCACCAAGGAGCACAAGACTACAAAGACGATGACGACAAGTGACTCGAGGGAATTCC-3).

5'RLM-RACE

Amplification and identification of 5' cDNA ends was done following the manufacturer's instructions (Ambion). The fragments were amplified by PCR using 5' adapter primers provided by the manufacturer and a 3' Ring1b outer primer (5-GGTCTGGCCTTAGTGATCTT-3) and subsequently a 3' Ring1b inner primer (5-TCTTTGTTGCCACTTCTAAGG-3). The extension time of the nested PCR was increased to 2 minutes and the annealing temperature was increased to 62 degrees. Fragments were separated on 2% agarose gels and ligated into the TA-vector following the manufacturer's instructions (Invitrogen).

Cell culture

Cells were cultured in DMEM (GibcoBRL), supplemented with penicillin/streptomycin (GibcoBRL) and 10% FBS (Hyclone). Transfections

were done with the calcium phosphate method in 60 cm² dishes with 25 µg plasmid DNA at 60% confluency. 50 ng of pEGFP was co-transfected to verify by fluorescent microscopy whether transfection was efficient and similar between samples within the same experiment. Infections were done with fresh undiluted supernatant from Phoenix producer cells, taken at 48 hours and 72 hours post-transfection, in the presence of polybreen. Induction of pIND-2A with muristerone-A proved to be unnecessary, since the leakiness of the vector's promoter provided enough 2A protein for our assays. 5 µg pIND-2A was cotransfected with the dual luciferase constructs.

Western blot analysis

Cells were collected in Eppendorf tubes, washed with PBS and lysed in RIPA buffer (1% NP40, 1% SDS, 0.5% DOC, 50 mM Tris-HCl pH 8, 2 mM EDTA) supplemented with N-ethylmaleimide (NEM, Sigma) and protease inhibitor cocktail (Roche). After measuring concentrations using the Bradford method, equal amounts of protein were loaded onto precast gradient gels (NuPage, Invitrogen) and subjected to SDS-PAGE. Samples were then transferred to nitrocellulose membranes (Schleicher & Schuel). The membranes were blocked for 1 hour with casein blocking buffer (Roche) which was 1:10 diluted in PBS, and incubated with primary antibodies for 1 hour. After three washes in PBS-Tween (0.5%), secondary antibodies were applied (Zymed goat anti-mouse 1:20000 diluted, BioSource goat anti-rabbit 1:10000 diluted) for 30 minutes. After three washes with PBS supplemented with 0.5% Tween-20, the membranes were incubated with ECL Western Blotting detection reagent (Amersham) and exposed to films (Kodak).

Luciferase assay

48 hours after transfection cells were harvested, lysed and incubated with luciferase substrates as described in the protocol of the Dual

Luciferase kit (Promega). Readout of luciferase activity was done with a luminometer (Turner Designs TD-20/20) for three seconds. Lysates were generally diluted ten to a hundred times before subjecting to the assay, to not exceed the measurable range of the luminometer. If undiluted samples had less than one hundred counts, they were considered to be insignificant. Every experiment was at least done three times and with two significant samples per experiment.

RNA isolation and quantitative real-time PCR (qPCR)

Total RNA was extracted using TRIzol reagent (Invitrogen), followed by DNase treatment and first strand cDNA synthesis using Superscript II reverse transcriptase (Invitrogen). qPCR was performed on 50 ng cDNA on an ABI Prism 7000 using SYBR Green PCR mastermix (Applied Biosystems). We used two different primer sets: Ring1b-1-fw (5-AAATGTCTCAGGCTGTGCAG-3) and Ring1b-

1-rev (5-TTCCAAGCCATCTGTTATTGCC-3), and Ring1b-2-fw (5-TCGGTTTTGCGCGGATT-3) and Ring1b-2-rev (5-AGTTTTTCCGACAGGTAGGACACT-3). Ring1b values were normalized against both Hprt and beta-actin, resulting in the same relative levels.

Software

Screening of putative IRESes in DNA sequences was done with the web-based software of UTRscan (<http://bighost.area.ba.cnr.it/BIG/UTRScan>) (Pesole and Liuni, 1999). Structure prediction of RNA sequences was done with RNAdraw, version 1.1 (Matzura and Wennborg, 1996).

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Chapter 6

Summary

The evolutionary importance of the fact that genes control embryonic development is this: it means that genes are at least partly responsible for their own survival in the future, because their survival depends on the efficiency of the bodies in which they live and which they helped to build.

Richard Dawkins, 'The Selfish Gene'

Summary

A lot is known about the order and timing of important events in embryonic development, as well as about the macroscopic formation of the body plan. However, the mechanisms behind the subtle changes in gene expression that orchestrate these events, is something we have only begun to understand over the past few decades. This thesis describes some of the remarkable characteristics of Ring1b, a protein that is critically involved in regulating gene expression during embryonic development.

One set of genes that has a relatively well-characterized role in the developing embryo, are the *homeobox* or *hox* genes. The specific timing of when these genes are expressed and when they're not, as well as where they are expressed and where they are not, is crucial to the formation of a proper body plan. They were first studied in *Drosophila melanogaster*, the fruit fly, but they have homologues in mammalian species that act in a comparable manner. One group of proteins that plays an important role in the regulation of expression of *hox* genes is the Polycomb group (PcG). They mainly exercise their function on *hox* genes by means of chromatin remodeling.

The structure of chromatin is correlated with the expression status of local genes. Tightly packed chromatin is largely inaccessible to transcription factors leading to silent genes, whereas open chromatin is associated with active genes. One way of remodeling chromatin is by chemically modifying the N-terminal tails of histones, the proteins around which DNA is wrapped. Dozens of different types of histones exist, and many of them have been demonstrated to undergo chemical modifications on different amino acid residues located in the N-terminal tail. Among these chemical modifications are methylation, dimethylation, trimethylation, ubiquitination, acetylation and phosphorylation. Each modification, combination of modifications and location of the modification tells the local

chromatin structure to behave in a certain way. Together they are referred to as 'the histone code'. Some marks are associated with actively transcribed genes ('H3K4me3', trimethylation of lysine 4 of histone H3), whereas other modifications are generally found near inactive genes ('H3K27', trimethylation of lysine 27 of histone H3). The latter mark is set by EZH2, the catalytic subunit of Polycomb Repressive Complex 2 (PRC2), and is thought to recruit other PcG members. PcG protein Ring1b, the subject of the research presented in this thesis, is an E3 ubiquitin ligase: it attaches a small ubiquitin peptide to lysine 119 of a histone variant called H2A. This mark is referred to as 'H2AK119u1'. Loss of Ring1b mediated monoubiquitination of H2A is linked to derepression of target genes.

Since embryonic development requires such a tight control of gene expression, we looked at the role of PcG proteins, and Ring1b in particular, in differentiation, the process of cells becoming more tailored to fulfill a certain function. This is particularly visible during embryonic development. PcG proteins were found to play an important role in keeping these so-called stem cells undifferentiated, until they get the proper signal to start differentiating. Genetic inactivation or RNAi-mediated depletion of several members of the PcG complexes causes derepression of target genes. In **chapter 3** we demonstrate data that is in full agreement with these earlier findings. Our *Ring1b* conditional knockout cell culture system enables us to genetically inactivate Ring1b at a specific time by just adding a well-tolerated chemical compound, tamoxifen. Doing this in mouse embryonic stem cells *in vitro*, differentiation immediately progresses, Ring1b target genes are derepressed and Ring1b localization to target loci is decreased. Therefore, we conclude that genetic inactivation of PcG proteins in mouse ES cells facilitates a differentiation-

prone phenotype. Interestingly, we find that Ring1b is preferentially bound to GC-rich promoter regions harbouring both active and repressive chromatin marks (so-called bivalent genes), and that a considerable number of Ring1b bound genes with an active mark are actually repressed in ES cells. The absence of the repressive Polycomb mark H3K27me3 at these promoters means that Ring1b can apparently be recruited independently from PRC2, the PcG complex that sets the H3K27me3 mark. This suggests that Ring1b acts more like a modulator of transcriptional activity of bivalent genes in embryonic stem cells rather than a silencer.

In **chapter 4** we investigate the role of Ring1b in brain development, using the same conditional knockout model, this time employing it in a whole mouse. Since a full *Ring1b* knockout mouse dies after several days of gestation due to a gastrulation arrest, the conditional knockout mouse – enabling us to delete the *Ring1b* gene in only parts of the body – provides us with a unique tool to study Ring1b function *in vivo*. Upon crossing this mouse with the well-characterized *Nestin-Cre* (NCre) transgenic mouse, the offspring lacked *Ring1b* in the Central Nervous System (CNS) only. We found that this mouse was viable, although born in submendelian ratios. Also, none of the mice survived longer than one month after (normal) birth. The macroscopic phenotype consisted of a severely reduced body mass, reduced activity, an ataxic gait, and difficulty to maintain balance. The latter two characteristics are suggestive of defects in the cerebellum. Also, their brain was markedly smaller and the cerebellum showed missing lobules, also called folia. Looking at the cerebellum microscopically, we found that the precentral fissure had not formed, resulting in a fusion between the ventral and dorsal lobules of the central vermal lobe. Several signaling pathways are known to lead to foliation defects; more investigation is necessary to identify which one is implicated in the *Ring1b* CNS null

mutant. Likely candidates are the *Engrailed* and *Sonic Hedgehog* signaling pathways.

To address the cause of the small size of the *Ring1b* null brains, we cultured Neural Stem Cells (NSCs) from the subventricular zone (SVZ) of the lateral ventricles of the cerebrum – a region known to have continuous neurogenesis – of mice lacking *Ring1b* in the brain, to test whether there was an impairment in these cells' ability to self-renew *in vitro*. The ability to self-renew is an important characteristic of stem cells. Indeed, the few neurospheres that formed from *Ring1b* knockout mice were unable to self-renew and entered a growth arrest. Interestingly, reminiscent of the *in vivo* situation in *Ring1b* knockout mice, the growth defect could be partially rescued by an *Ink4a/Arf* null background. Combined with the fact that p16^{Ink4a} and p19^{Arf} are both derepressed in a *Ring1b* null background, we conclude that the small brain size is at least partially due to derepression of the *Ink4a/Arf* tumor suppressor locus.

Although our understanding of PcG protein function is steadily growing, very little is known about regulation of PcG gene expression and translational control of PcG proteins themselves. In **chapter 5** we describe a novel mechanism through which Ring1b protein levels are regulated. We identified a functional internal ribosome entry site (IRES) in the *Ring1b* transcript. An IRES is a relatively rare, stable, three-dimensional structure in the 5' untranslated region (UTR) of the transcript, capable of recruiting the translational machinery on its own. This occurs independent of the presence of a 5' cap site, normally an absolute requirement for initiation of translation. Since an IRES enables a protein to be translated under conditions where normal proteins cannot be translated, IRES-harboring transcripts provide an clear advantage under stress conditions, where cap-dependent translation is often halted. Among these stress conditions are low oxygen, genotoxic stress, viral infections and amino acid starvation. We tested the activity

of the *Ring1b* IRES under many of these conditions, and in all cases the *Ring1b* IRES was highly active, sometimes even more active than the IRES of the encephalomyocarditis virus (EMCV), which is known to be very active under various circumstances and therefore often used in experimental settings. Unfortunately, we have not yet been able to find a functional purpose for the fact that *Ring1b* harbors an IRES. However, it is tempting to speculate that *Ring1b* has acquired the IRES to ensure that the protein is present in the cell nucleus at all times, even under severe and very different sorts of stress conditions. This putative necessity of *Ring1b* presence is in line with some of our other work, showing that deletion of the *Ring1b* gene leads to embryonic death, that somatic cells

go into apoptosis upon genetic inactivation of *Ring1b*, and that stem cells first activate random differentiation programs before going into apoptosis. This effect can not be rescued by chemical apoptosis inhibitors, immortalizing oncogenes or rich culture media.

Together, the data presented in this thesis paints a complex picture of a remarkable Polycomb group protein, being a key regulator of embryonic stem cell identity and a critical factor in cerebellar development, and employing an intriguing strategy to make sure it remains present in the cell. The availability of our efficient *Ring1b* conditional knockout system provides future investigators with a unique tool to study PcG in general and *Ring1b* in particular, both *in vivo* as well as *in vitro*.

Nederlandstalige samenvatting

Dat homeopathie er slecht vanaf komt in een vergelijking met reguliere geneeswijzen in het onderzoek van Shang, is niet verwonderlijk. Interessanter is het feit dat deze discussie voortduurt, ondanks honderdvijftig jaar van gebrek aan bewijs. Hoe meer het bewijs voor de werking van homeopathie wordt verdund, hoe populairder het lijkt te worden.

Hoofredactioneel commentaar in The Lancet over de tot op heden grootste metastudie naar de effecten van homeopathie (The Lancet, Volume 366, Issue 9487, p. 690; 27 augustus 2005)

Nederlandstalige Samenvatting

Eris veel bekend over de volgorde en het precieze moment waarop belangrijke gebeurtenissen tijdens de embryonale ontwikkeling plaatsvinden. Ook de macroscopische formatie van het lichaamsplan is tamelijk goed in kaart gebracht. Echter, de moleculaire mechanismen achter de subtiele veranderingen in genexpressie die de regie voeren over deze gebeurtenissen zijn pas de laatste decennia wat duidelijker geworden. Dit proefschrift beschrijft enkele van de opmerkelijke eigenschappen van Ring1b, een eiwit dat een cruciale rol speelt bij het reguleren van de genexpressie tijdens de embryonale ontwikkeling.

Eén familie van genen die een relatief goed beschreven rol spelen in het zich ontwikkelende embryo, zijn de *homeobox* of *hox* genen. De specifieke timing wanneer deze genen aan- of uitgeschakeld worden, alsook de precieze plaats in het embryo waar dit gebeurt, zijn cruciaal voor de vorming van een lichaam en organen waarin alles op de juiste plaats zit. *Homeobox*-genen zijn voor het eerst bestudeerd in *Drosophila melanogaster*, het fruitvliegje, maar ze hebben homologen die op een vergelijkbare manier werken in zoogdieren. Een groep eiwitten die een belangrijke rol speelt bij het reguleren van expressie van *homeobox*-genen zijn de Polycomb-eiwitten (Polycomb Group, PcG). Zij oefenen hun functie op *Homeobox*-genen vooral uit door middel van het veranderen van de driedimensionale structuur van chromatine, het geheel van DNA en de eiwitten die eraan verbonden zijn.

De specifieke chromatinestructuur houdt direct verband met de expressiestatus van genen die op dat stuk chromatine liggen. Dicht opeen gepakt chromatine is over het algemeen ontoegankelijk voor transcriptiefactoren, wat leidt tot niet-geëxprimeerde (inactieve) genen, terwijl chromatine met een meer open structuur in verband gebracht wordt met actieve genen. Een effectieve manier om chromatine te

herstructureren is door de 'staart' van histonen – de eiwitten waar DNA omheen is gewikkeld – te modificeren. Er zijn inmiddels tientallen verschillende soorten histonen ontdekt, en van velen daarvan is aangetoond dat ze chemische veranderingen kunnen ondergaan op specifieke aminozuurresiduen in de N-terminale staart. Deze chemische veranderingen bestaan uit methylatie, dimethylatie, trimethylatie, ubiquitinatie, acetylatie en fosforylatie. Elke modificatie, combinatie van modificaties en locatie van de modificatie maakt dat de lokale structuur van het chromatine zich op een bepaalde manier gedraagt. Het geheel van deze modificaties noemt men de 'histoncode'. Van sommige modificaties is bekend dat ze vooral worden aangetroffen nabij actieve genen ('H3K4me3', trimethylatie van lysine 4 van histon H4), andere vooral bij inactieve genen ('H3K27me3', trimethylatie van lysine 27 van histon H3). Deze laatste modificatie – aangebracht door EZH2, de katalytische subunit van Polycomb Repressive Complex 2 (PRC2) – recruteert vermoedelijk andere PcG-eiwitten naar die locatie. PcG-eiwit Ring1b, het onderwerp van het onderzoek dat in dit proefschrift is beschreven, is een E3 ubiquitine ligase: het hecht één klein ubiquitine-peptide aan lysine 119 in de staart van een histonvariant die bekend staat als H2A. Deze modificatie noemt men 'H2AK119u1'. Verlies van monoubiquitinatie van H2A door Ring1b leidt tot activatie van genen die daarvoor inactief waren.

Omdat regulatie van genexpressie tijdens de embryonale ontwikkeling zo nauw luistert, hebben we gekeken naar de rol van PcG-eiwitten – en Ring1b in het bijzonder – in differentiatie, het proces waarbij een cel steeds gespecialiseerder wordt om een bepaalde functie te gaan vervullen. Dit proces vindt met name plaats tijdens de embryonale ontwikkeling. Onlangs is bekend geworden

dat PcG-eiwitten de belangrijke functie vervullen om deze zogenaamde stamcellen ongedifferentieerd te houden, totdat ze het juist signaal krijgen om te beginnen met differentiëren. Genetische inactivatie of RNAi-gemedieerde depletie van verschillende PcG-eiwitten veroorzaakt derepressie van genen waarvan bekend is dat ze een doel van PcG-complexen zijn. In **hoofdstuk 3** presenteren we data die volledig in overeenstemming is met deze eerdere bevindingen. Ons *Ring1b* conditionele knockout celkweekstelsel stelt ons in staat om *Ring1b* genetisch te inactiveren op een specifiek moment door alleen tamoxifen, een voor gekweekte cellen onschadelijke chemische verbinding, aan het kweekmedium toe te voegen. Als we dit *in vitro* in embryonale stamcellen van muizen doen, start differentiatie onmiddellijk, vindt er derepressie plaats van bekende *Ring1b*-doelgenen, en vermindert *Ring1b*-localisatie naar bekende *Ring1b*-doelloci. Op basis van deze waarnemingen concluderen we dat genetische inactivatie van PcG-eiwitten in embryonale stamcellen leidt tot een gedifferentieerd fenotype. Interessant is, dat we vonden dat *Ring1b* vooral gebonden is aan GC-rijke promotoren die zowel actieve als inactieve chromatinemodificaties (zogenaamde bivalente genen) hebben, en dat een aanzienlijk deel van de *Ring1b*-gebonden genen met inactieve chromatinemodificaties in feite actief tot expressie komen. De afwezigheid van de inactieve, PcG-gemedieerde chromatinemodificatie H3K27me3 bij deze promotors betekent dat *Ring1b* blijikbaar onafhankelijk van PRC2 – het PcG-complex dat de H3K27me3-modificatie verzorgt – naar het chromatine gerecrueteerd kan worden. Dit suggereert dat *Ring1b* meer een modulator van transcriptionele activiteit van bivalente genen in embryonale stamcellen is, dan een repressor.

In **hoofdstuk 4** onderzochten we de rol van *Ring1b* in de hersenontwikkeling, gebruik makend van hetzelfde conditionele knockout-

model, ditmaal met een levende muis. Omdat de volledige *Ring1b*-knockout sterft tijdens de embryonale ontwikkeling vanwege een gastrulatie-defect, vormt de conditionele knockout muis – die ons in staat stelt *Ring1b* te verwijderen in slechts delen van het lichaam – een uniek model om verlies van *Ring1b* *in vivo* te kunnen onderzoeken. Na kruising van de muis met de goed gekarakteriseerde *Nestin-Cre* (NCre) transgene muis, missen de nakomelingen *Ring1b* in alleen het centrale zenuwstelsel (CNS). Deze nakomelingen bleken levensvatbaar, maar werden geboren met een submendeliaanse ratio. Geen van deze muizen overleefde langer dan een maand na (een normale) geboorte. Het macroscopische fenotype bestond uit een sterk gereduceerd gewicht, een verminderde activiteit, ataxia en een onvermogen om in evenwicht te blijven tijdens het lopen. De laatste twee kenmerken lijken te wijzen op een defect in het cerebellum. Daarnaast bleek de hersenmassa aanmerkelijk kleiner en miste het cerebellum enkele kwabben, ook wel folia genoemd. Op microscopisch niveau kijkend naar het cerebellum, vonden we dat de precentrale kwab niet was gevormd, wat resulteerde in een fusie van de ventrale en dorsale kwabben van de vermische kwab. Van verschillendesignaaltransductieroutes is bekend dat zij leiden tot dergelijke defecten tijdens de aanleg van het cerebellum; meer onderzoek is vereist om vast te kunnen stellen welke daarvan verantwoordelijk is voor de waargenomen defecten in de *Ring1b* CNS knockout. Voor de hand liggende kandidaten zijn de *Engrailed* en *Sonic Hedgehog* signaaltransductieroutes.

Om een beter inzicht te krijgen in de oorzaak van de geringe hersenmassa van de *Ring1b* knockout hersenen, kweekten we neurale stamcellen (NSC's) verkregen uit de subventriculaire zone van de laterale ventrikels van het cerebrum – een gebied waarvan we weten dat er continue neurogenese plaatsvindt – van muizen die *Ring1b* misten in het CNS, om te testen of deze cellen verminderd in

staat waren tot zelfvernieuwing *in vitro*. De eigenschap van zelfvernieuwing is een belangrijk kenmerk van stamcellen. Inderdaad bleek dat de – weinige – neurospheres die vormden uit de neurale stamcellen van Ring1b knockout muizen, vrijwel niet in staat waren tot zelfvernieuwing en stopten met groeien. Het was interessant te zien dat dit groeidefekt deels kon worden opgeheven wanneer de cellen ook *Ink4a/Arf* misten, wat vergelijkbaar is met de waarnemingen *in vivo*. Gevoegd bij het feit dat p16^{Ink4a} en p19^{Arf} beide geactiveerd zijn in de *Ring1b* knockout hersenen, concluderen we dat de geringe hersenmassa in ieder geval deels voor rekening komt van heractivatie van het *Ink4a/Arf* tumor suppressor locus.

Ofschoon ons begrip van de functie van PcG-eiwitten gestaag groeit, is er erg weinig bekend over de regulatie van expressie van PcG-genen en hun translationele regulatie. In **hoofdstuk 5** beschrijven we een nieuw mechanisme dat de hoeveelheid Ring1b-eiwit in de cel reguleert. We ontdekten een functionele *internal ribosome entry site* (IRES) in het Ring1b-transcript. Een IRES in een cellulair transcript is een relatief zeldzame, stabiele, driedimensionale structuur in het 5' niet-getransleerde gebied (UTR) van het transcript, dat zelf in staat is om de translatiecomplexen te recrutereren. Dit gebeurt onafhankelijk van de aanwezigheid van een 5' cap site, een chemische verbinding aan het begin van het transcript die normaliter absoluut noodzakelijk is voor initiatie van translatie. Een IRES stelt een eiwit in staat te worden getransleerd onder omstandigheden waarin normale eiwitten niet kunnen worden getransleerd, zodat IRES-dragende transcripten een duidelijk voordeel hebben onder stresscondities, wanneer translatie normaliter door de cel is stilgelegd. Voorbeelden van deze stresscondities zijn een

lage zuurstofconcentratie, genotoxische stress, virale infectie en een gebrek aan aminozuren. We testten de activiteit van de Ring1b IRES onder vele van deze omstandigheden, en in alle gevallen bleek de Ring1b IRES zeer actief, soms zelfs actiever dan de IRES van het encephalomyocarditis virus (EMCV), dat erom bekend staat dat het zeer actief is onder verschillende condities en daarom veel wordt gebruikt in experimenten. Helaas hebben we nog geen functioneel doel kunnen vinden voor het feit dat Ring1b een IRES heeft. Echter, het is aannemelijk dat Ring1b de IRES gedurende de evolutie heeft verkregen om zich ervan te verzekeren dat het eiwit op elk moment in de celkern aanwezig is, zelfs onder ernstige en verschillende soorten stresscondities. Deze veronderstelling is in overeenstemming met veel van ons andere onderzoek, dat laat zien dat deletie van het Ring1b-gen leidt tot peri-embryonale sterfte, dat somatische cellen apoptose ondergaan na genetische inactivatie van Ring1b, en dat stamcellen eerst willekeurige differentiatieprogramma's lijken op te starten voordat ze ook apoptose ondergaan. Dit effect kan niet worden tegengegaan met apoptoseremmers, immortaliserende oncogenen of rijke kweekmedia.

Samenvattend kunnen we zeggen dat de data gepresenteerd in dit proefschrift een complex plaatje schetsen van een opmerkelijk Polycomb-eiwit dat een sleutelrol speelt in het behoud van stamcelidentiteit en in de ontwikkeling van de kleine hersenen, en dat een intrigerende tactiek toepast om ervoor te zorgen dat het ten allen tijde aanwezig is in de cel. De beschikbaarheid van ons Ring1b conditionele knockout systeem geeft toekomstig onderzoek een uniek gereedschap om PcG-functie in het algemeen en Ring1b-functie in het bijzonder te onderzoeken, zowel *in vivo* als *in vitro*.

List of Publications

There is a theory which states that if ever anybody discovers exactly what the universe is for and why it is here, it will instantly disappear and be replaced by something even more bizarre and inexplicable. There is another theory which states that this has already happened.

Douglas Adams, 'The Hitch Hiker's Guide To The Galaxy'

List of Publications

Muyrers-Chen I, Hernández-Muñoz I, Lund AH, Valk-Lingbeek ME, van der Stoop P, Boutsma E, Tolhuis B, Bruggeman SW, Taghavi P, Verhoeven E, Hulsman D, Noback S, Tanger E, Theunissen H, van Lohuizen M.

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Stable X chromosome inactivation involves the PRC1 Polycomb complex and requires histone MACROH2A1 and the CULLIN3/SPOP ubiquitin E3 ligase
Proc Natl Acad Sci USA; 2005 May 24; 102 (21): 7635-40

Puschendorf M, Terranova R, Boutsma E, Mao X, Isono K, Brykczynska U, Kolb C, Otte AP, Koseki H, Orkin SH, van Lohuizen M, Peters AH

PRC1 and Suv39h specify parental asymmetry at constitutive heterochromatin in early mouse embryos
Nat Genetics; 2008 Apr; 40 (4): 411-20

Van der Stoop P, Boutsma EA, Hulsman D, Noback S, Heimerikx M, Kerkhoven RM, Voncken JW, Wessels LF, van Lohuizen M.

Ubiquitin E3 ligase Ring1b/Rnf2 of polycomb repressive complex 1 contributes to stable maintenance of mouse embryonic stem cells
PLoS ONE; 2008 May 21; 3 (5): e2235

Boutsma E, Noback S, van Lohuizen M.

The Polycomb protein and E3 ubiquitin ligase Ring1B harbors an IRES in its highly conserved 5' UTR
PLoS ONE; 2008 Jun 4; 3 (6): e2322

Curriculum Vitae

Even if there is only one possible unified theory [of everything], it is just a set of rules and equations. What is it that breathes fire into the equations and makes a universe for them to describe?

Stephen Hawking, 'A Brief History Of Time'

Curriculum Vitae

Erwin Alexander Boutsma was born on 1 November in 1976 in Zaandam (Zaanstad), the Netherlands. In 1989 he went to Blaise Pascal College in Zaandam for six years, after which he received his athenaeum diploma. In 1995 he started a Master's study in biology at the Free University (VU) in Amsterdam. After one year, he chose medical biology with an emphasis on genetics as his Master's thesis. His first internship was concluded in 1997 at the Free University Medical Center, in the department of clinical genetics and antropogenetics, in the research group of prof.dr. Hans Joenje. Supervised by dr. Quinten Waisfisz, he worked on the genetic characteristics of *FANCA* and *FANCC*, genes involved in Fanconi Anemia, a rare hereditary DNA repair disorder. This internship was followed by a second internship in 1997/1998, which took place at the editorial office of Technisch Weekblad, a weekly newspaper for professionals in engineering and technology.

Supervised by chief editor Wilbert van der Heijden, he worked as an editor in popular science writing. Shortly after that, on the 16th of September in 1999, he graduated from the Free University and received his Master's degree. For six months, he worked as a freelance journalist and popular science writer. On the 3rd of March in 2000, he started his PhD research at the Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI) in Amsterdam, in the group of prof.dr. Maarten van Lohuizen. Subject of his research was the characterization of Polycomb group gene *Ring1b/Rnf2*, using a new conditional knockout mouse model. His work on *Ring1b* is described in this thesis. On the 4th of March 2006 he started a job as editor of Technisch Weekblad, now part of Bèta Publishers, a publishing company specialized in popular science and technology magazines. During the first two years at Technisch Weekblad, he finished his thesis. Currently, he is assistant chief editor at Technisch Weekblad.

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Hofstadter's Law states that everything takes longer than you think it will, even when you take into account Hofstadter's Law.

Douglas Hofstadter

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Singapore met Mathijs; ik ben, als alles loopt zoals nu gepland, over twee jaar in de buurt, dan wip ik wel even langs! Maria, thanks for all your helpful discussions; in the end we managed to combine parts of our research after all, resulting in a very nice PNAS paper. Good luck in sunny Barça! Bas, je harde werk en vasthoudendheid hebben uiteindelijk een prachtig Nature-paper opgeleverd dat je volgens mij ten volle verdient. Voor jou geldt hetzelfde als voor Els: heel knap hoe je een drukke baan combineert met het vaderschap. Lund, thanks for being in an infectiously good mood all the time and for sharing your library-like amount of knowledge with all of us. And for continuously reminding us that we should know this-and-that by now, including the molecular mechanisms of a Moloney retrovirus replication cycle ('It's in every high school textbook!'). Good luck as an assistant-prof in Copenhagen! Bart, je ging érg voortvarend aan de slag en trad qua aantal projecten moeiteloos in Lunds voetsporen. Ik zal nooit Ellens gezicht vergeten toen we na een snelle berekening ontdekten dat jouw 'kleinschalige pilot-experiment' ongeveer 630 muizen zou vergen. Laat het me vooral weten als je weer bier gebrouwen hebt! Koen, je stapte in op het dalende deel van de golf die 'screens' heet, maar jarenlang verifieerde je onvermoeibaar de ene na de andere potentiële hit. Dat er weinig is uitgekomen, kan niet aan je ijver en vasthoudendheid hebben gelegen! Het ga je goed op je nieuwe plek, waar je het volgens mij veel beter naar je zin hebt. Anna and Yme, you joined the group in my last couple of months at the institute, bringing the fish as yet another model organism to the NKI. I'm confident that they will prove to be a great asset to Maarten's research! Joep, na een afwezigheid van een paar jaar keerde je als OIO terug; jammer dat dat na mijn vertrek was, we hadden ongetwijfeld een hoop lol kunnen hebben! Succes met je laatste jaren als OIO. Elisabetta, you joined the group after I left, but fortunately we still

managed to talk a couple of times about Ring1b. Good luck! (You'll need it, Ring1b is a tough little gene to work on...) En Roeland en Benno, jullie horen eigenlijk ook in dit rijtje; bedankt dat jullie me de kans en de tijd gaven dit alles af te maken, al duurde het onbedoeld veel langer dan ik jullie tijdens het sollicitatiegesprek heb voorgespiegeld...

Tenslotte wil ook ook nog iedereen bedanken die het werken op wat voor manier dan ook makkelijker maakte. Minze, bedankt voor het onvermoeibaar invriezen en uit de vaten halen van mijn ampullen. Arnout, Cor, Nico, en Mo, bedankt dat jullie mijn muizen al die jaren van eten, drinken en schitterend gezang voorzagen. Rahmen, thanks for your help with the B6 blastocysts and our many – failed, unfortunately – attempts to derive ES cells from them. Lenny, Lauran en Tom, bedankt voor jullie hulp met de CCD-microscoop en de confocale microscoop. All the people from the Berns, Peeper and Sixma labs, and, much earlier, the Bernards and Te Riele labs: thanks for all the stimulating scientific and non-scientific discussions we've had over the years!

En dat was het dan! Wat ik nu doe, ligt me beter en doe ik met meer overtuiging dan wetenschappelijk onderzoek, al zal ik dat laatste altijd het mooiste blijven vinden wat er is. Maar ik laat dat vanaf nu graag en met heel veel respect over aan anderen. Ik zal dan proberen om die ontdekkingen toegankelijk te maken voor niet-wetenschappers. Teveel maatschappelijke discussies met een wetenschappelijke component – homeopathie, Intelligent Design, klonen, etc. – worden gevoerd op basis van foutieve en onwetenschappelijke informatie, wat mijns inziens voor een belangrijk deel te wijten is aan gebrekkige kennis en voorlichting. (Daarom is het ook zo jammer dat het mij niet werd toegestaan een lekensamenvatting als extra hoofdstuk in dit proefschrift op te nemen. Elk proefschrift zou zo'n hoofdstuk moeten

hebben; het is een unieke kans om een klein beetje wetenschappelijk onderzoek begrijpelijk te maken voor niet-wetenschappers, en om wetenschappers te dwingen erover na te denken hoe ze hun werk op een begrijpelijke manier kunnen uitleggen. Nu blijft ook dit proefschrift een stoffig boekje waarvan door 99 procent van de eigenaars alleen dit dankwoord wordt gelezen.)

Ik zal me daarom de komende jaren als wetenschapsjournalist blijven inzetten voor het toegankelijk maken van wetenschap voor een groter publiek. Dat ik zelf zes jaar wetenschappelijk onderzoek heb mogen doen, zal me daarbij zeker niet in de weg zitten. Of,

zoals evolutiebioloog Richard Dawkins het enigszins arrogant, maar ondubbelzinnig verwoordde in een boekbespreking van 'Ever Since Darwin' van Stephen J. Gould: 'This book reinforces my feeling that scientific journalism is too important to be left to journalists, and encourages my hope that scientists may be better at it than journalists anyway.'

Om elke keer de grenzen van wat we begrijpen van de onvoorstelbare complexiteit van de natuur verder te willen opschuiven, is wat ons definieert als wetenschappelijk onderzoekers. Maar de natuur is veel te mooi om haar slechts toegankelijk te laten zijn voor een kleine groep.

Erwin, april 2009

There was this one useful technique I learned which I still use today. They taught us how to hold a test tube and take its cap off with one hand, while leaving the other hand free to do something else. Now, I can hold my toothbrush in one hand, and with the other hand, hold the tube of toothpaste, twist the cap off, and put it back on.

Physicist and Nobel Prize winner Richard Feynman, taking graduate courses in biology during his time as a physics student at MIT (quoted from 'Surely You Must Be Joking, Mr. Feynman!')

Right:

Translational

Control and

Knockout

Phenotypes

of a **PCG**

Core Protein

Erwin A. Bonczma